

**AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING AND
IMPROVING MENSTRUAL HEALTH AND SUPPORT AVAILABLE TO
FEMALE FOOTBALLERS**

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Abstract

Female athletes widely report perceived impacts to their health, wellbeing and sporting performance as a result of their menstrual cycle (MC), and subsequent symptoms experienced. There remains a lack of understanding of menstrual health and cycle characteristics within a youth environment, along with limited evidence to highlight the current menstrual support to athletes within football. This PhD research therefore aimed to understand the current landscape of MC experiences and perceptions within football from both players and coaches, and to develop and assess the effectiveness of targeted menstrual health education (MHE) resources in improving the knowledge and support from football coaches. Following a review of the literature to assess the current landscape of menstrual health, performance associations, and support available to women and girls within Chapter 2, Chapter 3 explored the role of age in the experiences and perceptions of the MC. This was performed by analysing questionnaire data pertaining to adolescent and adult elite football players. The questionnaire explored experiences and perceptions of the MC and the perceived impact on performance, and communication practices and perceived support to players. This chapter showed that significant associations existed between the age category of athletes and the perception of the MC impacting performance. Furthermore, with limitations in communication identified both generally in athletes' personal lives, but also within sport, Chapter 4 sought to further investigate the available support to athletes within sport. This was performed by interviewing football coaches to understand their awareness and perceptions of the MC relative to football performance, and explore their lived experience and the influence this has on MC knowledge and communication between coach and athlete. Chapter 4 showed that coaches perceived a culture of secrecy and limited visibility influenced their communication with athletes and their ability to develop their knowledge. The communication which did happen was impacted by the dynamic between coach and athlete, further influenced by various inter-personal factors. Importantly, coaches perceived themselves to have limited knowledge on the MC, impacting their ability to support players. Chapters 5 and 6 aimed to target this knowledge through developing a protocol to improve coach education, aiding the culture of discussion within sport and in turn widening the support accessible to athletes. Chapter 5 identified key determinants worthy of inclusion within education, such as the need for practical information focused on communication to athletes, and the development of education resources following a design-thinking model. This

framework included feedback to model the concise nature of information to provide simple visual guides for coaches to make actionable steps towards improving support. Chapter 6 assessed the effectiveness of this education, finding that whilst total assessed knowledge did not significantly improve following education, football coaches' ratings of confidence in providing practical support strategies did. In summary, the work in this PhD provides a significant and original contribution to the literature by establishing the importance of considering athlete age when developing our understanding of menstrual health and the culture influencing the support available. Furthermore, this research provides clear and novel documentation of developing menstrual health support resources, creating a vital step forward within both academia to improve understanding of sport-specific support, but also within practice to ensure athletes and coaches are offered relevant provision to improve discussion and support strategies. Collectively, this research aims to not only fill a notable gap within the literature, but also to provide a practical toolkit to embed menstrual health within athlete support systems.

Table of Contents

<i>AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING AND IMPROVING MENSTRUAL HEALTH AND SUPPORT AVAILABLE TO FEMALE FOOTBALLERS</i>	<i>I</i>
<i>Abstract</i>	<i>II</i>
<i>Acknowledgements</i>	<i>VIII</i>
<i>List of Figures</i>	<i>IX</i>
<i>List of Tables</i>	<i>X</i>
<i>List of Abbreviations</i>	<i>XI</i>
<i>Publications</i>	<i>XIII</i>
<i>Statement of Originality</i>	<i>XIV</i>
<i>Chapter 1 - Introduction</i>	<i>1</i>
1.1 Introduction	<i>2</i>
<i>Chapter 2- Literature Review</i>	<i>7</i>
2.1 Introduction to Literature Review	<i>8</i>
2.2 Menstrual Cycle Biology and Physiological Considerations	<i>8</i>
2.2.1 The Menstrual Cycle	<i>8</i>
2.2.2 Menstrual Cycle Symptomology	<i>11</i>
2.2.3 Menstrual Disorders	<i>14</i>
2.2.4 Hormonal Contraceptives: Altering Female Physiology.....	<i>18</i>
2.3 Menstrual Cycle Impacts	<i>20</i>
2.3.1 Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Daily Wellbeing and Activities	<i>20</i>
2.3.2 Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Objective Markers of Athletic Performance	<i>22</i>
2.3.3 Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Self-Reported Markers of Athletic Performance.....	<i>26</i>
2.4 Adolescent Considerations	<i>30</i>
2.4.1 Adolescent Physiology	<i>30</i>
2.4.2 Adolescent Menstrual Cycle Symptomology and Cycle Disturbances	<i>31</i>
2.4.3 Adolescent Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Daily Wellbeing and Activities	<i>32</i>
2.4.4 Adolescent Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Athletic Performance.....	<i>34</i>
2.5 Menstrual Health Management	<i>36</i>
2.5.1 Menstrual Product Use	<i>36</i>
2.5.2 Medicative Management Methods	<i>37</i>
2.5.3 Non- Medicative Management Methods	<i>38</i>
2.5.4 Contraceptive Management Methods.....	<i>40</i>
2.6 Societal Perspectives of the Menstrual Cycle	<i>42</i>
2.6.1 Historical Menstrual Stigmas	<i>43</i>
2.6.2 Manifestation of Menstrual Stigmas	<i>43</i>
2.6.3 Modern Day Menstrual Stigmas.....	<i>46</i>
2.7 Menstrual Health Education	<i>47</i>
2.7.1 Menstrual Health Literacy Assessment	<i>49</i>
2.7.2 Menstrual Health Literacy of Women and Girls	<i>50</i>

2.7.3 Athlete Menstrual Health Literacy	52
2.7.4 Coach Menstrual Health Literacy.....	53
2.7.5 Menstrual Health Literacy Assessment In Sport	55
2.8 Menstrual Health Support	55
2.8.1 Menstrual Health Support to Women and Girls	55
2.8.2 Menstrual Health Support to Athletes	57
2.9 Contextual Considerations of Thesis	67
2.9.1 Language Utilised Throughout.....	67
2.9.2 Theoretical Underpinning of Work	68
2.10 Aims and Objectives of Thesis.....	70
3. Chapter 3; Study 1	73
<i>Perceptions and Experiences of the Menstrual Cycle amongst Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players.</i>	73
3.1 Introduction	75
3.2 Methods	76
3.2.1 Participant Information.....	76
3.2.2 Data Collection.....	77
3.2.3 Analysis	77
3.3 Results.....	78
3.3.1 Personal MC Characteristics	78
3.3.2 Symptom Frequency and Severity.....	82
3.3.3 Symptom Management and Perceived Impact of the MC.....	84
3.3.4 Support Available and Support Preferences	85
3.3.5 Pre-menarcheal Perceptions	87
3.4 Discussion.....	87
3.5 Limitations and Future Work	91
3.6 Conclusions	92
4. Chapter 4; Study 2	93
<i>Coaches' Ability to Support Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players Throughout their Menstrual Cycle.</i>	93
4.1 Introduction	95
4.2 Methods	97
4.2.1 Participant Information.....	97
4.2.2 Data Collection.....	98
4.2.3 Analysis	98
4.2.4 Research Quality and Rigour.....	99
4.3 Results and Discussion	99
4.3.1 Environment and Culture	101
4.3.2 Coach-Athlete Dynamic	103
4.3.3 Coach Support	108
4.4 Conclusions	113

4.5 Limitations	113
4.6 Practical Applications	114
5. Chapter 5; Study 3	116
<i>Utilising a Design-Thinking Approach to Develop a Menstrual Health Literacy Programme for Coaches of Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players</i>	<i>116</i>
5.1 Introduction	117
5.2 Methods	120
5.2.1 Theoretical Framework	121
5.2.2 Data Collection and Analysis Methodologies	122
5.3 Results.....	126
(1) 5.3.1 Needs Analysis	126
(2) 5.3.2 Player Interviews	128
(3) 5.3.3 Initial Stakeholder Engagement.....	130
(4) 5.3.4 Research Creation.....	133
(5) 5.3.5 Stakeholder Feedback.....	135
(6) 5.3.6 Pilot Education.....	140
(6) 5.3.6 Iteration (and Reflection).....	140
5.4 Discussion.....	141
5.5 Limitations.....	144
5.5 Conclusions	144
6. Chapter 6; Study 4	146
<i>Evaluating the Effectiveness of a Pilot Menstrual Health Education Intervention in Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Coaches</i>	<i>146</i>
6.1 Introduction	147
6.2 Methods	148
6.2.1 Participant Information.....	148
6.2.2 Data Collection.....	149
6.2.3 Analysis	151
6.3 Results.....	152
6.3.1 Perceived Knowledge Pre-Post Intervention.....	152
6.3.2 Assessed Knowledge Pre-Post Intervention.....	155
6.3.3 Comfort in Communication and Supportive Practices Pre-Post Intervention.....	155
.....	156
6.3.4 Recognition of Myths and Misconceptions Pre-Post Intervention.....	156
6.3.5 Post Intervention Coach Feedback	157
6.4 Discussion.....	158
6.5 Limitations and Future Work	163
6.6 Conclusions	164
7. Chapter 7.....	166
<i>General Discussion.....</i>	<i>166</i>

7.1 Introduction	167
7.2 Summary of Study Findings	167
Chapter 3, Study 1:	167
Chapter 4, Study 2:	168
Chapter 5, Study 3:	169
Chapter 6, Study 4:	170
7.3 General Discussion Summary	170
7.3.1 Interpretation of Findings	171
7.4 Significance of Research	177
7.5 Practical Recommendations	178
7.6 Limitations	179
7.6 Future Work	180
7.7 Conclusions	181
8. References	184
9. Appendices	240
Appendix A	240
Chapter 3: Player Questionnaire regarding MC characteristics, experiences and perceptions upon performance.	240
Appendix B. Chapter 3: Symptom frequency reported by adults and adolescents who were naturally menstruating	263
Appendix C. Chapter 3: Symptom severity reported by adults and adolescents who were naturally menstruating	271
Appendix D. Chapter 3: Content analysis of symptom management methods	279
Appendix E. Chapter 3: Content Analysis on participants responses to MC performance impacts.	280
Appendix F. Chapter 3: Comfort in communication of players, and perceived support strategies offered. ..	281
Appendix G. Chapter 3: Findings from open-text responses on whether gender impacts comfort in communication	283
Appendix H. Chapter 4: Researcher Interview Guide for Semi-Structured Interviews	284
Appendix I. Chapter 4: Further supportive evidence including example data regarding categorisation of themes and sub-themes	285
Appendix J	296
Chapter 5: Design Thinking Model: Player Interview Script	296
Appendix K	297
Chapter 5: Design Thinking Model: Stakeholder Questionnaire	297
Appendix L	299
Chapter 5: Design Thinking Model: Initial Stakeholder Feedback	299
Appendix M.	300
Chapter 5: Design Thinking Model: Final Resource Creation	300
Appendix N.	301
Chapter 6: Participant Pre-Post MC Knowledge and Experiences Questionnaire	301

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Once City, Always City.

List of Figures

Chapter 2

- Figure 2.1 The menstrual cycle characterised by phases and hormones. As found in Draper et al. (2018)..... 9
- Figure 2.2 Flow diagram highlighting diagnostic routes for amenorrhoea. Adapted from The Practice Committee of the American Society for Reproductive Medicine (2004)..... 15
- Figure 2.3 Current influences to support for athletes regarding their menstrual health and experiences..... 58
- Figure 2.4 Model of the coach-athlete relationship from Jowett and Poczwardowski (2007) 62

Chapter 3

- Figure 3.1 Symptom frequency for NM A) adolescents and B) adults. 81
- Figure 3.2 Symptom severity for NM A) adolescents and B) adults..... 83

Chapter 5

- Figure 5.1 Design thinking approach depicting each stage of the authors process, whilst detailing each data collection method. This includes the (1) needs analysis of literature, (2) player interviews, (3) initial stakeholder engagement, (4) design of resources, (5) attain stakeholder feedback, (6) pilot education, and finally (7) user feedback..... 122

Chapter 6

- Figure 6.1 Boxplot highlighting pre-post participant responses regarding perceived knowledge of the MC. * denotes significance, set as $p < 0.05$ 153
- Figure 6.2 Boxplot highlighting pre-post responses regarding coaches perceived comfort in communication, and resultant supportive practices for MC experiences in football players. * denotes significance, set as $p < 0.05$ 156

List of Tables

Chapter 2

Table 2.1 Examples of symptoms experienced as a result of the MC as described by Hantsoo et al. (2022); Ponzo et al. (2022); Cunningham et al. (2024).	12
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Chapter 3

Table 3.1 Self-reported MC characteristics of adolescent and adult football players.	79
Table 3.2 Self-reported menstrual bleeding characteristics of adolescent and adult football players	80
Table 3.3 Adolescent and adult football players MC-related communication and support.....	85

Chapter 4

Table 4.1 Breakdown of key themes following coach interviews, with sub-themes and higher order codes.	100
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Chapter 5

Table 5.1 Outline of all stages utilised throughout the design-thinking model, in reference to data collected and analysis performed.....	123
Table 5.2 Findings following conceptual frequency analysis on initial stakeholder engagement regarding a) aims of education, b) content of education and c) format and delivery of the sessions.	130
Table 5.3 Education resource outline including lesson focus and learning outcomes.....	134
Table 5.4 Matrix of stakeholder feedback following initial draft of education resources	136

Chapter 6

Table 6.1 Question Formatting for the Pre-Post Education Questionnaire assessing MC knowledge, perceived knowledge and comfort in communication, and post-education evaluation.....	151
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List of Abbreviations

AUB	Abnormal uterine bleeding
COC	Combined hormonal contraception
GnRH	Gonadotropin releasing hormone
HC	Hormonal contraception
HIC	High-income country
HL	Health literacy
HMB	Heavy menstrual bleeding
HPO	Hypothalamic- pituitary-ovarian
FIGO	International Federation of Gynaecology and Obstetrics
FSH	Follicle-stimulating hormone
ID	Iron deficiency
IDA	Iron deficiency anaemia
LH	Luteinizing hormone
LMIC	Low-middle-income country
MBI	Magnitude based inference
MC	Menstrual cycle
MHH	Menstrual health and hygiene
MHL	Menstrual health literacy
MSi	Menstrual Symptom Index
OCP	Oral contraceptive pill
PA	Physical activity
PCOS	Polycystic ovarian syndrome
PMDD	Pre-menstrual dysphoric disorder
PMS	Pre-menstrual syndrome
PRL	Prolactin
RED-S	Relative energy deficiency in sport
SD	Standard deviation
SWPL	Scottish Women’s Premier League
NSAID	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug

WHO World Health Organisation

WSL Women's Super League

Publications

Peer-reviewed publications arising from this thesis:

Chapter 3: Donnelly, J., Valentin, S., White, A., Easton, C., & Forrest (née Whyte), L. J. (2025). Perceptions and Experiences of the Menstrual Cycle amongst Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players. *Science and Medicine in Football* pp1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2025.2476485>

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*presenting author.

Statement of Originality

The work in this thesis is the sole work of the candidate. This work has not previously been submitted for award at any other institution. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the thesis contains no material previously published by another person except where due reference is made in the thesis itself.

Julia Donnelly

13/04/2025

Date

Chapter 1 - Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Over the past decade, women's football has witnessed significant growth. Year-on-year improvements in revenue and match attendances has positioned the sport as one of the fastest growing globally (FIFA, 2022). Within the U.K., national success at the 2022 European Championships resulted in positive advancements domestically, particularly within the Women's Super League (WSL), improving the professional standards of match play, and player care (Deloitte Sports Business Group, 2024). Despite this growth, research within women's sport is still in its relative infancy, with women under-represented across sport and exercise science literature (Costello, Bieuzen and Bleakley, 2014; Cowley *et al.*, 2021, 2023). The disparity in the gender representation of participants within research has been outlined, with only 6% of total publications within sport and exercise science focusing solely on female participants (Cowley *et al.*, 2021). Given the fundamental disparities in anatomy, physiology and metabolism (Ansdell *et al.*, 2020), the dearth of research to develop evidence-based practice limits the advancement of female health and performance. This issue can be partially attributed to historical barriers that have hindered the acceptance, participation, and professionalism of women in sport (Roberts *et al.*, 2002; Youth Sports Trust, 2018; Johnston-Robledo and Chrisler, 2020). Additionally, one of the key challenges contributing to this data gap includes the need to account for female-specific factors, deemed difficult to measure and control within research (Emmonds, Heyward and Jones, 2019). This includes the menstrual cycle (MC), a crucial component of female reproductive health that influences the functioning of essential physiological systems and health indicators. However, the lack of recognition of MC-related impacts within the literature results in limited conclusions about its true effects on health, wellbeing and athletic performance.

The MC refers to a physiological process which underpins the ovulatory and reproductive systems within females. MC phases can broadly be outlined as the follicular and luteal phase, split by a period of ovulation. These phases are depicted by key steroidal and gonadotropin hormonal fluctuations to promote reproductive and regulatory functions and have significant implications upon markers of health, wellbeing and performance. The influence of the MC within sport is poorly understood or considered within the literature. A meta-analysis assessing the impact of the MC on markers of performance found that the ability to discern the true effects of menstrual phase

upon performance remains difficult due to the volume of methodological inconsistencies and overall poor quality of work performed to date (McNulty *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, to improve the understanding of MC impacts, there has been growing research focusing on the athlete perspective, allowing for information to be collated regarding menstrual characteristics, symptomology, and perceived impacts upon wellbeing and athletic performance. Active women have on average reported 11 MC related symptoms, with the number of symptoms positively associated with negative outcomes such as missing training, competition, or sporting events (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021). In addition, 36-100% of elite sportswomen perceive menstrual symptoms to be linked to sporting performance (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Heather *et al.*, 2021; Read *et al.*, 2021; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). For example, a common symptom, heavy bleeding, reported by 30% of athletes, resulted in them being more likely to report increased fatigue (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021), which in turn may cause further performance impact. The psychological impact has also been reported, with perceived reduced attentional focus on sporting tasks during menstruation, and a reduction in mental sharpness with increased menstrual related pain (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Read *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022). Thus, whilst research to date fails to show overwhelming evidence that exercise performance is altered by the physiological menstrual state, self-reported information from sportswomen highlights the perceived effect of the MC upon performance.

The majority of studies to date investigating the MC have focused on adult athletes, with a notable lack of research including adolescents. As a result, little is known about the extent to which findings can be transferred across age demographics. Sport England has reported growth in girls' participation in football (4%) in the past four years, although note several barriers still limit gender parity to physical activity involvement (Sport England, 2023). Furthermore, the rise in women's football throughout the U.K. has led to improvements in academy infrastructure and facilities, improving the opportunity for girls to pursue an elite footballing education (The Football Association, 2023). It is crucial to acknowledge that female adolescents exhibit clear physiological differences from adults, which must be explicitly considered in both research and practice. This includes the potential for irregular menstrual patterns due to the immaturity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis (American Academy of Pediatrics *et al.*, 2006), with cycle lengths typically longer in the early developmental years. Further impacts as a result of adolescent

physiology include that of high rates of dysmenorrhoea, impacting 71% of those aged 13-23 (Armour *et al.*, 2019b). Increasing age is seen to reduce the prevalence of dysmenorrhoea (Lidh *et al.*, 2012; Parker *et al.*, 2010), highlighting the need for consideration of potential symptomology differences when accounting for adolescents within research. With the differences in hormonal profiles, it is therefore important to understand the experiences girls have during their adolescent years as they navigate the maturation of their MC on health and performance. Firstly, periods are viewed as a barrier to physical education involvement by 37% of schoolgirls, with embarrassment experienced around managing bleeding within a school environment such as changing facilities, fear around leaking through menstrual products, and feelings of being unable to communicate these feelings to family or teachers (Youth Sports Trust, 2018). Symptomology is often expressed through pain or discomfort, yet the teaching of coping strategies around menstrual management are often limited, leaving girls feeling underprepared for the experiences they have (Youth Sports Trust, 2018; Brown *et al.*, 2022a, 2024a). For the adolescents that progress within sport there is little evidence to document their experiences of managing their MC within sport. One study focused on Singaporean athletes from a range of sporting backgrounds and found that 67% of players who cited not using hormonal contraception (HC) believed their MC impacted their ability to compete (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). However, with little known in regard to adolescent footballers, further research is warranted.

With MC impacts noted within both adult and adolescent sporting environments, it is essential to understand the current support available to manage these effects. This understanding will help to create targeted support structures to address the areas identified by athletes and researchers. However, several barriers limit the ability for coaches to convey practical support to athletes. Firstly, a lack of knowledge of menstrual health topics has been cited within both athletes (Larsen *et al.*, 2020; Anderson *et al.*, 2023) and coaches (Anderson *et al.*, 2023; Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023). For example, within English football, an assessment of menstrual health literacy (MHL) amongst coaches found a total knowledge score of 48% on average, with the author highlighting this requires improvement through further education on the topic (Anderson *et al.*, 2023). The limited discussion of menstrual health is well recognised within general society due to historical stigmas, leading to shame, gender discrimination and cultural taboos (McHugh, 2020; Olson *et al.*, 2022), and remains evident within sport (Kolić *et al.*, 2024). Gender is still identified as a

limitation within sport, with 44% of athletes communicating about their MC to a female coach versus 22% to a male coach (Solli *et al.*, 2020), with relatability and perceived greater knowledge cited as key reasons behind this (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021). Athletes regularly highlight the perceived limited knowledge of their coach prevents them from engaging in discussion or sharing their experiences (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022). Coaches within sport have identified they would like more education on the MC to ensure they can adequately support players (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). Education has been found to significantly improve markers of knowledge on menstrual health (Clarke *et al.*, 2024). However, with the lack of documented education within football, and the little work to date detailing efforts to improve MHL and subsequent support to athletes, further research within this topic is needed.

It is evident that more research must be performed to facilitate a greater understanding of the current landscape of MC health and support within football. Many practitioners and coaches have limited knowledge of the MC, limiting the ability to provide informed and appropriate support in this area. With adolescent athletes at a crucial stage in their development and pubertal maturation, ensuring adequate athlete and coach knowledge is critical. The overarching aim of this PhD was to contribute to the body of knowledge pertaining to menstrual health and support within sport, through firstly reviewing the literature to date within Chapter 2. Next, Chapter 3 investigates the experiences and perceptions of adolescent and adult football players regarding the MC. Chapter 4 focuses on football coaches, exploring their experiences and perceptions of the MC, and the ability to support players within the performance environment. Chapter 5 details the development of menstrual-health education (MHE) resources, created through a design-thinking approach targeted to football coaches, and Chapter 6 assesses the effectiveness of a MHE intervention on knowledge and comfort in communication within football coaches. Finally, Chapter 7 provides a discussion of the thesis, considering chapter specific outcomes and the broader findings and implications within the academic and practical landscape of women's sport. Furthermore, this chapter will explore the relevance of the findings and propose future work within the field before concluding this thesis. Collectively, this thesis represents a contribution to the understanding of menstrual health within women and girl's football, addressing key gaps in

knowledge and support, and offering practical solutions to improve the discussion between coaches and athletes within sport.

Chapter 2- Literature Review

2.1 Introduction to Literature Review

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the existing literature regarding the impact of the MC upon health, wellbeing, and athletic performance, in addition to the support available to women, girls, and athletes for managing the MC and its' associated effects. *Section 2.2* introduces the MC in regard to its physiological foundations and the relevant considerations of this hormonal profile within healthcare and performance. The impacts upon wellbeing, daily activities, and performance outcomes are outlined in *Section 2.3*, with symptomology detailed in relation to the role played upon quality of life, absenteeism and exercise participation, in addition to the objective and self-reported measures of performance underpinning the current understanding of the MC within sport. The considerations upon adolescent girls, and athletes, are outlined in *Section 2.4*. Moreover, the management strategies of women and girls both within and outwith sport is covered in *Section 2.5*. Next, *Section 2.6* introduces the menstrual stigmas promoted throughout history and into modern day society, influencing support available to women and girls. One repercussion of the menstrual stigma is the education received on the topic of menstrual health and management, discussed in *Section 2.7*. This culminates in support available to women and girls, and then within sport (*Section 2.8*). Contextual considerations to highlight the positionality of the PhD are outlined in *Section 2.9*. Lastly, the aims and hypothesis of this thesis and each study are outlined in *Section 2.10*.

2.2 Menstrual Cycle Biology and Physiological Considerations

2.2.1 The Menstrual Cycle

Female physiology is governed by the complex interactions of hormones and systems which drive key events throughout a female's life, for example, within reproductive functioning. Endogenous sex hormones, such as oestrogen and progesterone, exert biological effects in a cyclical nature to control sexual differentiation and maturation, through to pregnancy and latterly menopause. The MC marks a pivotal aspect of this physiology, and refers to a physiological process which, dictated by the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis, prepares the body for egg fertilisation and implantation, and thus pregnancy. The MC is often divided into two discrete phases: 1) the follicular phase, and 2) the luteal phase (Figure 2.1). The two phases occur cyclically, typically

over a 21 – 35-day period (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2013). In a ‘normal’, or eumenorrheic cycle, the HPO axis controls the release of gonadotropins, namely luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) from the pituitary gland in response to the hypothalamus releasing gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) (Davis and Hackney, 2017). Oestrogen and progesterone are then produced by the ovaries in response to such signals of FSH and LH from the pituitary, and subsequently impact the ovulatory functioning of the cycle through the positive and negative feedback upon the hypothalamus and pituitary, respectively (Nippoldt *et al.*, 1989; Davis and Hackney, 2017). This cyclical feedback loop is known to dictate key physiological changes within the female body resulting in impacts to health, wellbeing and potentially performance, explained throughout this thesis.

Figure 2.1 The menstrual cycle characterised by phases and hormones. As found in Draper *et al.* (2018)

The MC begins on day 1 of bleeding, or menstruation, and thus the start of the follicular phase, which is characterised by blood loss due to the shedding of the endometrial lining in the absence of pregnancy for a duration of 2 – 7 days (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2013; Bull *et al.*, 2019). The steroid hormones oestrogen and progesterone are low

during this time. The remainder of the follicular phase includes the maturation of ovarian follicles, stimulated by the release of FSH by the pituitary gland in response to the release of signals upon the hypothalamus, namely the production of GnRH. The follicles mature throughout this phase and increase the concentration of oestradiol, as seen in Figure 2.1. Furthermore, FSH falls following menses due to the negative feedback of oestrogen on the pituitary gland. The increase in oestrogen stimulates a surge in LH and regarded as the trigger for ovulation, the release of an egg from the mature dominant follicle within the ovaries (Pauerstein *et al.*, 1978). Ovulation is a critical point for the development of eggs for fertilisation and thus development into embryos for childbirth, assuming the cycle is ovulatory. This typically occurs between days 12 – 14 within a cycle, assuming a cycle of 28 days (Davis and Hackney, 2017). This follicle, once the egg has been released and luteinised, is termed the corpus luteum and is known to promote increases in oestradiol and progesterone into the luteal (secondary) phase of the MC. Increases in progesterone to the highest peak of the cycle is crucial to facilitate the thickening of the endometrial lining in preparation for egg implantation following fertilisation (Davis and Hackney, 2017). This occurs until the structure becomes inactive and subsequent steroid hormones fall on the occasion pregnancy does not occur. This is typically accompanied by a rise in basal body temperature (BBT) until the structure ceases (Forman, Chapman and Steptoe, 1987; de Jonge, 2003). This fall in hormones is detected and allows FSH production by the pituitary and thus continuing the cyclical pattern and the endometrial lining to once again shed (Welt *et al.*, 2003).

Whilst information regarding the physiological process of the MC remains undisputed and well supported within the literature, it is important to highlight that even aspects of the definitions surrounding the MC remain contested within academia. The classification of menstrual phases can often differ between researchers, leaving ‘gold standard’ data collection difficult to attain. For example, whilst the information above outlines a distinct two-phase cycle, some academics state that this is too simplified when considering the role of undulating hormones within each phase. Some laboratory studies separate the menstrual bleeding, or menstrual ‘phase’, when collecting data (Pallavi, D Souza and Shivaprakash, 2017), or divide the follicular phase into two to create three phases (Oosthuysen, Bosch and Jackson, 2005). Moreover, some split each key phase into two to generate five key points (i.e. early follicular, late follicular, ovulation, mid-luteal and late luteal) (Tenan, Hackney and Griffin, 2016; McNulty *et al.*, 2020). This five-phase model is

thought to consider four key hormone profiles to consider to ensure accurate portrayal of hormonal changes, namely, oestrogen: progesterone ratios (Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021). This also requires more sampling throughout a cycle, and thus provide further complications to data collection. However, without a universal consensus on key labelling and categorisation, supporting evidence on the effects of the MC may be misinterpreted and potentially inaccurate when compared.

2.2.2 Menstrual Cycle Symptomology

The MC commonly results in a variety of physical, or somatic, and psychological symptoms, known to vary greatly and be highly individual within naturally menstruating women. These symptoms can change within or between cycles. The reporting of MC symptoms is widespread within the general population, with significant effects upon health, wellbeing and overall quality of life (Lustyk *et al.*, 2004; Slade, Haywood and King, 2009; Schoep *et al.*, 2019a). The top six most logged symptoms within a common MC tracking app (n = 1801, age = 28.7 ± 6.7 years) were all physical/ somatic symptoms, such as cramps (91%), fatigue (85%) and bloating (81%) (Ponzo *et al.*, 2022). Following this, emotional symptoms such as irritability (73%), mood swings (73%) and cravings (71%) were all highly prevalent. This list is not exhaustive, however Table 2.1 displays results from three studies utilising tracking apps, categorising symptoms reported by women globally into somatic and psychological/ emotional symptoms (Hantsoo *et al.*, 2022; Ponzo *et al.*, 2022; Cunningham *et al.*, 2024). These symptoms can present at any point within the cycle, however, there has been research to show symptoms may be related to menstrual phase. For example, a study by Ross, Coleman and Stojanovska (2003) involved a cohort of women (n = 181) completing daily questionnaires for 70 days to track symptoms across self-reported menstrual phases. All symptoms were found to fluctuate significantly across the menstrual phase, with the pre-menstrual/ late luteal phase and menstrual phase seeing the greatest prevalence of symptoms. Pre-menstrual syndrome (PMS) is known to affect a significant amount of women and there is debate over its categorisation as a typical ‘symptom’, or instead a menstrual disorder (Taim *et al.*, 2023a) (Chapter 2.2.3). Moreover, age is found to be an influential factor upon symptom prevalence. Logged entries of cramps and acne into a mobile app decreased in frequency with increased age in a cohort of women aged 18 – 55 years (Cunningham *et al.*, 2024), however backache and headaches had an inverse relationship with age. Each symptom varies in the impact

it has and how it manifested within women in regard to wellbeing, productivity, and exercise adherence (Chapter 2.3).

Table 2.1 Examples of symptoms experienced as a result of the MC as described by Hantsoo et al. (2022); Ponzo et al. (2022); Cunningham et al. (2024).

Somatic (Physical)	Psychological/ Emotional
Stomach cramps	Calm
Fatigue	Anxious
Bloating	Depressed
Backache	Obsessive Thoughts
Headache	Stress
Acne	Irritated
Nausea	Mood Swings
Diarrhoea	Cravings/ Appetite changes
Vomiting	Sad
Sleep Changes	Happy
Libido changes	Confused
Breast Tenderness	Energetic
Constipation	
Sweating/ Hot Flashes	
Weight Gain	

Studies investigating MC experiences have reported the majority of elite athletes report symptoms related to their MC. A meta-analysis of MC symptomology in female athletes during the pre-menstrual and menstrual phases found the most commonly reported symptoms to be abdominal cramps (59%), insomnia or hypersomnia (53%), anger or irritability (49%) and anxiety or tension (46%) (Taim *et al.*, 2023a). However, it is important to note that these data were collected from a maximum of four studies for some values, highlighting the limited evidence available to be able to compare symptomology to the general public and allow us to understand if there are significantly different experiences dependent upon sporting background. A study on elite rowers found that more symptoms were reported at the end of the cycle (mid-luteal and pre-menstrual), with fewer symptoms reported during the follicular phase (Antero *et al.*, 2023).

Conversely, two studies (Martin *et al.*, 2018; Parker *et al.*, 2022) found more athletes to report symptoms on the initial days of menstruation (59%, 82%, respectively) than the pre-menstrual phase (17%, 25%, respectively). It can therefore be considered there is overwhelming evidence to show women, girls and athletes alike experience symptoms as a result of their MC. Bruinvels *et al.* (2021) reports that active women on average experience 11 MC symptoms, however, to further classify symptoms proposed the use of a Menstrual Symptom Index (MSi) to form a singular 'score' to understand the impact upon performance (Chapter 2.3.3), yet this vitally did not include a method to quantify symptom severity, arguable the key indicator of impacts upon wellbeing and performance outcomes. Self-reported rankings of symptom severity within active exercisers was utilised within work from Kiemle-Gabbay and colleagues (2024). Abdominal cramps were reported as 'severe' or 'very severe' from 39% participants, with other symptoms logged as mood changes (25%), tiredness (26%) and feeling irritable/ angry (22%), highlighting the severity of psychological symptoms. MC symptom severity is positively associated to reported impact upon wellbeing and performance, to be discussed later within this thesis (Chapter 2.3.3).

A factor rarely considered in studies collecting data on MC symptoms is the format through which symptoms are identified. While some studies utilised close-ended formats, offering participants a predefined list of symptoms to choose from (Hantsoo *et al.*, 2022; Ponzo *et al.*, 2022), others utilise open-ended text responses for the participant to log their own symptoms without any prompt (de Carvalho *et al.*, 2023). These methodological differences are not alluded to in the above studies referenced, however may significantly impact the type and range of symptom data generated. Whilst the studies identified above allow large cohort comparison in a standardised format, they may constrain responses to those identified by the researchers, and therefore potentially biased, or overlooking individual considerations. The self-reported symptom data allows for an individualised approach, yet relies on information recall and provides complexity in quantifying. Whilst, to the author's knowledge, this has not been studied within this field, research within mental health has identified that data collection methods influence participant responses, with much higher selection on close-versus-open-ended responses (Friborg and Rosenvinge, 2013). Friborg and Rosenvinge also conclude that open-text options may be more suitable considering the highly sensitive or stigmatising questions due to the embarrassment or stress which may be invoked if someone experiences something not covered within pre-

determined categories. Given the historically stigmatised topic of the MC, to be discussed within this thesis, this is a worthwhile consideration for future research.

2.2.3 Menstrual Disorders

2.2.3.1 Dysmenorrhoea

Dysmenorrhoea refers to the phenomenon of painful menstruation caused by stomach cramps associated with the MC. This is thought to impact 45 – 95% of females, with the wide range in prevalence attributed to inconsistent definitions and diagnostic criteria (Proctor and Farquhar, 2006; Iacovides, Avidon and Baker, 2015). However, it is considered to be the most prevalent gynaecological disorder (Iacovides, Avidon and Baker, 2015). This can be classified into two distinct types: primary dysmenorrhoea and secondary dysmenorrhoea. Primary dysmenorrhoea is menstrual pain caused by excess prostaglandin production (PGF2a and PGE2), thought to increase myometrial contractions and vasoconstriction within the uterus, producing anaerobic metabolites and experienced by females due to the hypersensitisation of pain fibres (Itani *et al.*, 2022). This is often experienced upon the onset of menses due to the drop in progesterone immediately prior, allowing prostaglandin levels to rise. Secondary dysmenorrhoea is a side effect of underlying health conditions, typically also related to reproductive health, in conditions such as endometriosis and adenomyosis. Within adult athletes, a recent systematic analysis of 60 studies found dysmenorrhoea to be the most prevalent disorder (30%), however still ranging greatly (range 8 – 86%), and many studies failing to differentiate between primary and secondary dysmenorrhoea (Taim *et al.*, 2023a).

2.2.3.2 Amenorrhoea

Amenorrhoea is the absence of menstruation within a female of reproductive age. This can be classified as primary amenorrhoea, defined by having no menstruation by the time a female turns 15 years (with the presence of otherwise normal development) (Munro *et al.*, 2022), or secondary amenorrhoea, the absence of menses for three consecutive periods or more, despite having previously regular menstruation (McIver, Romanski and Nippoldt, 1997). There can be a variety of underlying causes to explain either branch of amenorrhoea which prevents bleeding, as referenced upon the route of diagnosis in Figure 2-2. Furthermore, secondary amenorrhoea can often be presented similarly to primary amenorrhoea (The Practice Committee of the American Society for Reproductive Medicine, 2004). The causes of amenorrhoea are often associated with

disorders of the uterus and vagina, ovary, anterior pituitary, and hypothalamus, each of which has its own set of potential causes (Samal and Habeebullah, 2017). This includes Mullerian agenesis (absence of uterus and vagina), Gonadal dysgenesis (impaired gonad development, Hyperprolactinaemia (presence of tumour adenoma causing overproduction of prolactin (PRL)), and functional disorders of the HPO axis, such as a decrease in GnRH activity (Figure 2.2; (The Practice Committee of the American Society for Reproductive Medicine, 2004; Samal and Habeebullah, 2017). The complex pathophysiology of underlying conditions often leaves diagnosis a difficult process, with the condition having further impacts upon markers of health and wellbeing.

Figure 2.2 Flow diagram highlighting diagnostic routes for amenorrhoea. Adapted from The Practice Committee of the American Society for Reproductive Medicine (2004)

Secondary amenorrhoea can also include further considerations due to the role in lifestyle factors in inducing missed menstruation. Within athletes and women in the general population, elements of their lifestyle, such as nutritional intake, physical activity levels, stress and body composition are known to contribute to potential menstrual disturbances such as secondary amenorrhoea (McIver, Romanski and Nippoldt, 1997; Golden, 2002; The Practice Committee of the American Society for Reproductive Medicine, 2004).

Primary amenorrhoea is documented as being prevalent in 0 – 32% of adult athletes, with a wider range experiencing secondary amenorrhoea (0 – 62%) (Taim *et al.*, 2023a). There is the potential for this to be higher than the general population due to the pressures of scheduling, training load, and for some, the weight categorisations their sport requires (Golden, 2002; Mountjoy *et al.*, 2014, 2023). One particularly relevant framework for understanding the physiological consequences of amenorrhoea in athletes is the model of Relative Energy Deficiency in Sport, or RED-S, with the case of inadequate energy intake versus expenditure known to cause significant issues upon a range of physiological functions, which may negatively impact menstrual health (Mountjoy *et al.*, 2014). Low energy availability affects the hypothalamus and thus impacts the release of gonadotropins, termed Functional Hypothalamic Amenorrhoea (Figure 2.2). Further impacts as a result of RED-S include changes to bone health due to the reduced role of oestrogen in calcium uptake into the bone (Mountjoy *et al.*, 2023), alongside a range of metabolic, cardiovascular, endocrine and immunological impairments (Mountjoy *et al.*, 2014). Despite growing recognition of RED-S and its' potential consequences, there remains a lack of consistency in screening, diagnosis and support practices. This may contribute to under-reporting and delayed treatment, which can be impactful upon sporting performance.

There are a number of barriers to prevent clarity in providing conclusive data regarding menstrual health characteristics. For example, there are conflicting definitions of primary amenorrhoea. While some define diagnosis as a lack of menstruation by age 15 (Oxfeldt *et al.*, 2020; Munro *et al.*, 2022), others opt for age 16 (Nichols *et al.*, 2006; Samal and Habeebullah, 2017), which may impact the ability for girls to gain a diagnosis and subsequent support. Additionally, alternative definitions of secondary amenorrhoea focus on timescales as opposed to periods, e.g. three months or 90 days (Ihalainen *et al.*, 2021; Taim *et al.*, 2023a). Furthermore, the diagnostic tools utilised within research is a crucial issue currently; a meta-analysis of 56 studies assessing MC disorders within sportswomen found two to be of methodological quality to be considered in the 'gold' tier, diagnosed by a medical professional. One of the two studies found primary (10%) and secondary (35%) amenorrhoea, yet the participants were categorised as 'local competitive', and thus not elite (Melin *et al.*, 2015). Not considering the additional stressors of elite athletes, as detailed above, may leave these findings unable to transfer across populations.

2.2.3.3 Heavy Menstrual Bleeding (HMB)

Heavy menstrual bleeding (HMB), also known as menorrhagia, is menstrual bleeding which is found to be abnormally heavy, or prolonged, with blood loss significantly greater than the average female menses, with 80ml being a typical marker of HMB (Munro *et al.*, 2023). HMB can be a side effect of underlying causes. Abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) has been classified further to encompass the related bleeding issues due to the confusing nomenclature and thus utilised within healthcare to clarify investigative methods. Therefore, the International Federation of Gynaecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) presented a model inclusive of nine AUB considerations: coined PALM-COEIN, to include Polyp, Adenomyosis, Leiomyoma, Malignancy and hyperplasia, Coagulopathy, Ovulatory dysfunction, Endometrial, Iatrogenic and Not yet classified within the acronym (Munro *et al.*, 2011). Each included category can be differentiated by its diagnostic methods, pathophysiology and has subsequent impacts upon health, highlighting the complicated pathophysiology of HMB presentation. This is thought to affect 3 – 42% of adult athletes (Taim *et al.*, 2023a), with the self-reported nature of information regarding MC characteristics often drawing large ranges due to the self-diagnoses given.

2.2.3.4 Pre-menstrual Syndrome (PMS)

PMS is a menstrual disorder in which physical, psychological and emotional symptoms increase in severity especially in the days leading up to menstruation. The pathophysiology of PMS is unclear due to the volume of symptoms which can be attributed within this time frame. Whilst progesterone is considered to be key regulatory indicator of PMS symptoms due to the lack of somatology in those with anovulatory cycles or pregnancy, however, there fails to be evidence to quantify any rise in progesterone with symptoms. However, key impacts of PMS are that of emotional health, often validated through a reduction in serotonin transmission, which has been found to be the case with PMS prevalence. The luteal phase of the MC is seen to have a decreased serotonin volume and thus may help to explain the severity of symptoms often experienced in the lead up to menstruation (Rapkin and Akopians, 2012). Within adult athletes, PMS is thought to impact 8.6 – 59.6% (Taim *et al.*, 2023a). Studies within the lower end of this range utilised retrospective questionnaires, relying on participants recall (Takeda *et al.*, 2015, 2018), whereas those with higher reported prevalence followed daily monitoring to report upon the occasion of each symptom (Foster *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, one study specifically asked whether participants

experienced to choose from a close-ended list of symptoms they experience prior to menstruation, however did not ask regarding any other point in the cycle, a key differentiator between PMS and 'regular' menstrual symptoms (Takeda *et al.*, 2015). PMS is not diagnosed through any objective means and thus requires the medical professional to interpret experiences and diagnose where suitable. This reason, coupled with the known hesitation in women seeking medical help with their menstrual symptoms (Chapter 2.8.1) provides context to the large prevalence range identified.

2.2.4 Hormonal Contraceptives: Altering Female Physiology

Hormonal contraception (HC) is primarily a method of birth control, by which synthetic hormones override typical menstrual functioning to elicit desired responses, such as the prevention of ovulation. The mechanisms differ depending on the type of HC utilised and subsequent hormones. Categorised HCs can include combined, progestin only, and bi-tri-phasic, and delivered orally via oral contraceptive pills (OCPs), injections, implants and patches (Martin *et al.*, 2018; Cabre *et al.*, 2024).

Literature focusing on elite athletes has estimated the prevalence of HC users to be between 28% - 68% (Torstveit and Sundgot-Borgen, 2005; Martin *et al.*, 2018; Clarke *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Engseth *et al.*, 2022; Heyward *et al.*, 2022; Nolan, Elliott-Sale and Egan, 2022; Parker *et al.*, 2022). This includes a range of sporting backgrounds, including studies focusing on individual athletes such as cross-country skiers and biathletes (68%; (Engseth *et al.*, 2022), and also team sports such as rugby (36%; Heyward *et al.*, 2022, 54%; Nolan, Elliott-Sale and Egan, 2022). One study directly compared HC usage to a control group, finding significantly more athletes (40%) utilise HC than non-athletes (28%) (Torstveit and Sundgot-Borgen, 2005), however there have been no other studies to understand whether this has changed in the 20-years since this research. The lower end of the prevalence range was identified in WSL footballers (n = 75). Within those utilising HC, oral contraception was the popular choice (62%), with intra-uterine systems (24%), injections (10%) and implant (5%) also utilised (Parker *et al.*, 2022). The large variance in HC prevalence in sport is multifactorial, outlined later within this thesis (Chapter 2.5.4).

2.2.4.1 Combined Contraceptive Methods

Firstly, combined hormonal contraceptives are named as such due to the inclusion of both oestrogen and progesterone. Their mechanism of contraception is due to the antigonadotrophic effects from synthetic hormones (typically ethinyl oestradiol and synthetic progesterone's such as gestodene, norethisterone, desogestrel amongst others), resulting in the downregulation of endogenous sex hormones (Elliott, Cable and Reilly, 2005) to reduce gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) from the hypothalamus, which controls LH and FSH secretion from the pituitary, thus inhibiting ovulation (Rivera, Yacobson and Grimes, 1999). The pathophysiology of combined HCs differs through the methods of use. Typically, these HCs are taken in pill-form, names combined oral contraceptives (COCs) with a 21-day pill taking period followed by seven pill free, or placebo pill use, days (Bennell, White and Crossley, 1999). Pill free days provide rises in oestradiol concentrations, yet still fail to reflect normal MC phases, hormonal fluctuations or pathophysiology at any point (Masama *et al.*, 2022). Further prevention of ovulation includes the thickening of cervical mucus and thinning of the uterine lining to create an inhospitable environment for potential implantation.

2.2.4.2 Progestin-only Contraceptive Methods

Other HC methods include that of progestin-only contraception. While progestin (synthetic analogue of progesterone derived from testosterone) can function similarly to inhibit the release of FSH and LH, progestin-only contraceptives do not always prevent ovulation. However, when they do, they do so without corpus luteum, preventing subsequent effects such as fertilisation (Hatcher, 2007; Jacobstein and Polis, 2014). Primarily, progestin aims to thicken the cervical mucus to prevent sperm being able to reach and thus fertilise the corpus luteum. One may opt to utilise progestin only means over that of combined hormonal contraceptive methods due to contraindications with combined contraceptives (discussed below), or during breastfeeding.

2.2.4.3 Bi-Tri-phasic Contraceptive Methods

Finally, bi-phasic and tri-phasic HCs refer to COCs which provide either two or three different doses of oestrogen and progestin throughout the pill cycle, with the goal of mimicking natural hormonal fluctuations. The bi-phasic HCs typically split into a “follicular” phase, whereby both synthetic hormone quantities are reduced, and then rise to mimic a “luteal phase”. Tri-phasic

differs slightly to provide a more gradual increase in hormones throughout the pill packet (split into three different doses) (Van Vliet *et al.*, 2006; Hatcher, 2007). These hormones work using similar mechanisms to that outlined above yet do so in a format that aims to closely follow the hormonal profile (Van Vliet *et al.*, 2006).

2.3 Menstrual Cycle Impacts

MC symptoms are prevalent within both general society and athletes (Chapter 2.2.2), making it crucial to understand how these symptoms manifest into impact upon daily wellbeing and activities (Chapter 2.3.1), and objective (Chapter 2.3.2) and self-reported (Chapter 2.3.3) markers of exercise performance within athletes.

2.3.1 Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Daily Wellbeing and Activities

Menstrual symptoms have a significant impact upon markers assessing quality of life, through both daily disturbances, and long term economic, health and social impacts. For example, 38% of women reported performing fewer activities or being unable to do anything during their period within a large cohort study ($n = 42,879$; (Schoep *et al.*, 2019a). This included being unable to complete household tasks, or utilising pain medication to complete them. Financial burdens are often discussed by women, with costs attributed to period products, pain medication, healthcare visits and productivity losses as a result of absenteeism (Rapkin and Winer, 2009; Jensen *et al.*, 2012). With the number of associated menstrual symptoms and disorders, it is likely the true impact of the MC is under-reported (Schoep *et al.*, 2019b). For example, HMB is associated with iron deficiencies (ID) and anaemia (IDA). HMB has been found to be significantly influential upon markers of quality of life (Shankar, Chi and Kadir, 2008), with increases in monthly expenses (97%) and work impairment (67%) found within an observational study of women aged 35 – 52 years ($n = 58$) (de Souza *et al.*, 2010). The meta-analysis from Shankar, Chi and Kadir (2008) failed to separate perceived impact by participant demographics, as understanding whether this was compounded by those within lower income countries is a worthwhile future observation. PMS has also been seen to result in more perceived stress from women compared to those without (Lustyk *et al.*, 2004), leading to subsequently lower quality of life measures.

Absenteeism from work caused by menstrual related symptoms was 11% from a large cohort of women (Schoep *et al.*, 2019a). Furthermore, for those that remained present, the reported productivity loss averaged 8.4 ± 10.6 days per year (Schoep *et al.*, 2019a). Within those with menstrual disorders such as dysmenorrhoea (Fooladi *et al.*, 2023) and endometriosis (Soliman *et al.*, 2017), absenteeism was significantly greater than in women without diagnoses. A study of 3555 Australian women (age 18 – 39 years) found those with dysmenorrhoea were 50% more likely to report a poorer performance at work, and double the number of sick days within the past year compared to those without (Fooladi *et al.*, 2023). This study did not define what was meant by ‘poorer’ performance, thus further qualitative evidence would be valuable in future research. A study of women using the ‘Flo’ menstrual app (n = 1867) found that the most frequently reported symptoms of those who missed work due to their MC were cramps (93%), fatigue (85%) and bloating (81%) (Ponzo *et al.*, 2022). Despite reporting absence to work, 50% women felt like they could not talk freely about their symptoms/ impact of symptoms to their manager, nor receive any support from their manager (48%; (Ponzo *et al.*, 2022). The mentioned study by Ponzo and colleagues failed to ask participants on the gender of their manager, or compare between those who had male versus female managers, and whether that impacted likelihood of discussion. This is a worthwhile discussion when assessing support available for women and girls, discussed later in this literature review (Chapter 2.8). Other life activities affected are relationships with family, partner, sexual activity, and social activities (Ponzo *et al.*, 2022).

Lastly, sports or exercise participation within the general population was found to be significantly impacted by the symptoms experienced associated with the MC (Prince and Annison, 2023; Law *et al.*, 2024; Srinivasa Gopalan, Mann and Rhodes, 2024). A systematic review assessing the impact of MC upon physical activity (PA) found that nearly 50% of females restrict PA either during or prior to menstruation (Srinivasa Gopalan, Mann and Rhodes, 2024). This is firstly due to the symptoms experienced, and the perception these prevent a barrier to PA due to pain and discomfort. This is especially true in those with dysfunctions such as dysmenorrhoea with a study providing qualitative information on those with dysmenorrhoea who found that their ability to exercise was reduced regardless of pain severity experienced. This was noted to have subsequent impacts upon weight gain (Stokes *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, focus groups highlighted the need to change exercise activity or intensity due to management of period products, invoking

a fear of leaking in activities which may require more movement and leading to behaviours such as planning clothes to minimise any potential effects (Kolić *et al.*, 2023). The mental burden of concealing menstruation, anxiety of leaking and behaviour to pretend they are not affected is commonly noted by women within general society as a “menstrual etiquette” (Kolić *et al.*, 2024). The systematic review by Srinivasa Gopalan, Mann and Rhodes (2024) did not split findings by study country, or religion of participant, which may be worthwhile to consider in future research (Heather *et al.*, 2021). For example, studies in Hong Kong (60%; Chia *et al.*, 2013) and Malaysia (62%; Wong and Khoo, 2011) seen participants restricting PA due to their MC or symptoms, higher than average values collected (50%; Srinivasa Gopalan, Mann and Rhodes, 2024). Therefore, it can be concluded there is sufficient evidence to intimate that women and girls are impacted by their MC within daily life, and is therefore essential to ensure women receive appropriate support to manage these effects and improve their overall quality of life.

2.3.2 Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Objective Markers of Athletic Performance

Whilst self-reported data highlights that the perception of the MC impacting health, wellbeing and performance is conclusive, the objective evidence to support this remains contested. As discussed, the hormonal fluctuations throughout the MC can have a considerable impact on several physiological systems (e.g. metabolism, cardiovascular function and immune responses) and in turn pose the potential to have consequences upon exercise performance. With these systems having a crucial role in the regulation and influence upon exercise performance, understanding the current evidence linking the MC to exercise performance is required. Firstly, endurance exercise was originally suggested to be susceptible to hormonal fluctuations due to the role played upon substrate utilisation and thermoregulation (Lebrun *et al.*, 1995; de Jonge, 2003; Carmichael *et al.*, 2021a). However, conflicting evidence on ventilatory responses, plasma volume, heart rate and maximal oxygen consumption have all been reported when accounting for hormonal changes in other studies (Dombovy *et al.*, 1987; De Souza *et al.*, 1990; Burrows and Bird, 2005). As mentioned previously, there is a rise in BBT within the luteal phase due to the rise in progesterone, promoting an increased thermoregulatory stress with prolonged activities, thus impacting the cardiovascular strain (de Jonge, 2003). This is compounded with the lack of equivalent increases in sweat rate and skin temperature to regulate these changes (Carmichael *et al.*, 2021a). However, a study in marathon runners saw 57% have their best performance in the luteal phase, significantly

greater than those in the follicular phase (Greenhall *et al.*, 2020). A narrative review from Carmichael *et al.* (2021) highlighted that out of six studies assessing the impact of MC phase to aerobic performances, two highlighted a potential effect on some outcomes, not all, whilst the remaining four found no association. This includes a lack of significant changes maximal heart rate, maximum oxygen uptake, or substrate utilisation with tests to exhaustion in endurance-trained females (Ekberg *et al.*, 2024). This is despite previous suggestions that substrate utilisation may be impacted throughout the MC due to the increase in lipid availability, and enhanced gluconeogenesis with increases in oestradiol (Lebrun *et al.*, 1995). However, the study by Ekberg and colleagues estimated MC phase through self-reporting into a mobile application, and thus cannot draw true conclusions without verifying menstrual status. Through the use of serum hormone analysis to verify MC state, work from Taylor and colleagues (2024) found no definitive influence of serum oestrogen or progesterone concentration upon performance-determining variables through sub-maximal tests, ski ergometry, and maximal treadmill tests across highly trained endurance athletes ($n = 21$). However, with data collected over only two cycles, it is also important to consider these conclusions are based on a maximum of six data collection points (three phases, two cycles), the assessment of correlation is not exhaustive, and concluding that there are no causal effects of hormone concentration on performance without comprehensive supportive evidence may be premature. Findings of a meta-analysis by McNulty *et al.* (2020) propose a trivial effect of MC upon endurance-based outcomes, manifested by a reduction in performance within the early follicular phase/ menses, compared with the other menstrual phases. However, the authors highlight the need for more high-quality research employing valid sampling means to be performed to understand whether such identified changes are meaningful.

The increased BBT has been found to improve key markers of performance in studies assessing the impact of heat stress on short duration sprint activities, due to greater muscle contractility and force production, and thus there is the potential for the luteal phase to positively impact strength, sprint and power activities (Carmichael *et al.*, 2021a). Further work considered that oestrogen may strengthen skeletal muscle (Sarwar, Niclos and Rutherford, 1996), however, studies have since found no correlation between oestrogen and progesterone concentration and muscle contractile characteristics (de Jonge *et al.*, 2001). This, however, does not remove the potential for any causal effects of the factors studied, or secondary influences. Peak power has

been found to increase during the ovulatory phase (validated by self-collected salivary samples), assessed by repeated cycle ergometry sprints. However, this phase also found the highest reported motivation rankings by athletes (Cook, Kilduff and Crewther, 2018), highlighting the multifactorial considerations to make upon performance improvements or reductions, and evidence cannot always account for the human nature of elite athletes.

To the author's knowledge, three studies to date have assessed the impact of the MC upon markers of performance within football (Julian *et al.*, 2017, 2021; Tounsi *et al.*, 2018), two of which were graded as good quality (Julian *et al.*, 2017, 2021) within a recent meta-analysis (Meignié *et al.*, 2021). First, Julian and colleagues (2017) performed a study in which players logged menses and performed blood collection on the day prior to testing to quantify oestrogen and progesterone over an eight-week period. The study found, as expected, oestrogen and progesterone levels to be higher in mid luteal phase compared to follicular. For sprint speed (5m, 10m, 30m) and counter-movement jump (CMJ) no significant difference was found in recorded values between menstrual phases. Magnitude based inferences (MBI) identified a potential harmful effect of performance within the Yo-Yo intermittent endurance test within the luteal phase, highlighting the potential reduction in aerobic fitness during this phase (as indicators of maximal effort were achieved through heart rate, lactate and rate of perceived exertion). Furthermore, higher blood lactate levels at 3- and 5-mins post Yo-Yo were found during the follicular phase, with MBIs considering this a very harmful effect. This was attributed to potential changes in substrate utilisation dependent upon menstrual phase, as suggested by Oosthuyse and Bosch (2010), who proposed a lower rate of anaerobic glycolysis to occur within the luteal phase. Determining a causal relationship between MC phase and field performance markers is not an easy task, as a multitude of influential factors such as motivation, fatigue, cumulated training load, weather, diet amongst others can all impact results. Further work from the same author within football focused on interpreting match data to assess if outcomes could be attributed to MC phase (Julian *et al.*, 2021). Whilst the value indicating very-high running distance was significantly greater during the luteal phase, large variations upon performance metrics were identified throughout the phases, leaving it difficult to draw firm conclusions on this matter. With the number of influential variables during a match impacting distances covered (i.e. team formation and

tactics), including that of individual playing position, fitness and capabilities (Datson *et al.*, 2024), drawing conclusions on this matter will remain a difficult task.

In addition, there is limited evidence to highlight the impact of HC upon exercise outcomes. Elliot-Sale and colleagues (Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2020) found within a meta-analysis that OCP use may result in an inferior exercise performance when compared to non-OCP use, however the substantial between-group effects were found to be trivial, and 83% of studies reviewed were graded as moderate, low or very low quality, leaving limited conclusions to be drawn. Furthermore, no studies focused primarily on football players. Furthermore, Nolan *et al.* (2024) focused solely on OCP use within a meta-analysis, and found a lack of significant effects upon indicators of hypertrophy or strength. With HCs used for a variety of reasons, including the perceived effect of aiding performance (Chapter 2.3), understanding the effects of other HC means is crucial in aiding the support available for athletes to make informed decisions over their MC management strategies, outwith contraceptive means.

As discussed, it is difficult to form definite conclusions on the impact of the MC, or HC on exercise performance outcomes, due to the volume of conflicting evidence available. There are a number of reasons behind this. Firstly, the volume of markers of exercise performance which can be utilised is dependent on the nature of the sport (and thus physiological systems utilised), the topic researched, and on ease of measurement, which can pose significant difficulties in forming decisive conclusions. Next, the validity of MC state in regard to the measurement of phases, oestrogen and progesterone levels, or other hormonal markers is often highlighted as an issue in limiting the validity of data presented within research as data can often be self-reported (Kishali *et al.*, 2006; Crewther and Cook, 2018). Recent attempts to create clear guidelines to establish processes to profile ovarian hormonal profiles include that of a classification tool (Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2024). This includes a flowchart series to guide practitioners through the required steps dependent on the MC characteristics they may be presented with. Additionally, the laboratory based studies are often used to ensure accuracy and validity, however often leaves a lack of transfer of findings currently available to the practical sports landscape, and too few studies focus on truly elite level (Meigne *et al.*, 2021). It can be difficult to attain athletes of this calibre due to the time and physically invasive nature (e.g. blood sampling) these studies require to obtain accurate data

(Coutts, 2017). The requirement of following numerous cycles to obtain consistent data is also problematic logistically (Elliot-Sale *et al.*, 2020) due to the nature of travel and at times rigorous competitive schedules of athletes. Therefore, the impacts of the MC upon exercise performance are not fully understood, and with conflicting evidence currently available, can make it difficult for practitioners and athletes to understand, relate to, and utilise within practice. Therefore, academics have highlighted that, in the absence of such evidence, the use of adapting training to elicit optimal physical outputs or adaptations is not recommended (Colenso-Semple *et al.*, 2023; Jonge and Thompson, 2023).

2.3.3 Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Self-Reported Markers of Athletic Performance

Whilst objective evidence to date is limited in its findings to elicit substantial evidence to promote the impact of the MC upon performance markers, research focusing on athletes' experiences and reported MC characteristics reveals further variability in conclusions that performance is indeed affected by an athlete's menstrual state (Oester *et al.*, 2024; Carmichael *et al.*, 2021a). A recent review conducted by Oester and colleagues (2024) collated findings from 39 studies to discover that between 3 – 100% of athletes reported their performance was affected as a result of their MC. However, the review also caveated this high degree of variability by the varying methodological approaches utilised throughout the studies to attain self-reported data (e.g. questionnaires and interviews). Additionally, the wording of these questions to generate a response also differs, adding to the complexity of understanding the true perception amongst athletes. For example, the meta-analysis discussed stated they reported the perceived impact of the MC, however values included were both from questions directly asking regarding the perception of the MC upon performance, whilst some purely noted performance implications when asked to list general MC symptoms experienced (de Carvalho *et al.*, 2023). Upon closer assessment, the value at the lower end of the reported range (3%), was that of HC users, and highlights the need for clarity in assessed values (Nolan, Elliott-Sale and Egan, 2022). Furthermore, the inclusion of participants and the categorisation of 'athlete' often differs between studies. The standard of which an athlete competes at could potentially be an influential factor upon their perception of their MC being impactful, however studies reporting this have found mixed evidence. A mixed methods survey utilised participants ranging from local to international level, and did not find any discernment between MC experiences and playing level (Adam *et al.*, 2022). Contrastingly, work within rugby found

those playing within a lower division reported a greater perception of the MC negatively impacting performance (Hayward *et al.*, 2024). This is potentially due to a better infrastructure around elite athletes, for example club medical teams who provide support in the management of symptoms to elite athletes. Interestingly, despite high prevalence of perceived impacts to performance, rates of absenteeism from athletes was low (Oester *et al.*, 2024). For example, semi-structured interviews within elite rugby (n = 15; Findlay *et al.*, 2020), and survey data within elite female athletes from a range of sports (n = 430; Martin *et al.*, 2018) highlighted that 67% and 77% of athletes perceived their MC impaired performance, respectively. This provides equivocal findings that elite athletes perceive their MC impacts their sporting performance. However, the subsequent behaviours this prompts is not always significant. For example, both studies mentioned reported a small cohort had refrained from exercise due to their cycle (e.g. 4%; Martin *et al.*, 2018). Suggested reasons include the viewpoint that athletes are under internal and external pressures to perform, and often state there is no option other than to 'deal with' the symptoms (Read *et al.*, 2021). However, these studies did not detail the exact experiences that led athletes to have this perception, whilst Bruinvels *et al.* (2021) found a correlation between MSi to missing training or competition (although participants were not deemed elite athletes).

A number of survey studies (Martin *et al.*, 2018; Solli *et al.*, 2020; Heather *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Engseth *et al.*, 2022; McNamara, Harris and Minahan, 2022; Hayward *et al.*, 2024; Armour *et al.*, 2020a) and studies utilising semi-structured interviews (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Read *et al.*, 2021) have been performed with elite and/or highly competitive adult athletes in the past decade, with 51–100% reporting a solely negative perception upon performance as a result of their MC. The primary reason often identified behind this perception are the symptoms experienced as a result of the MC (Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; McNulty *et al.*, 2023; Oester *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, number of symptoms experienced positively correlates with a greater negative perception (Antero *et al.*, 2023). This impact is found to be manifested in a number of ways. A perceived lack of power, speed, fitness, coordination, and greater muscular fatigue were all identified as physical repercussions of the MC (Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Read *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). For example, 71% of Australian athletes perceived they felt fatigued more easily on match day (Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Oester *et al.* (2024) reported in a meta-analysis that

feeling less strong, and being slower, was reported by 1 - 52%, and 1 - 53%, respectively, highlighting the large variation in responses, potentially down to the importance of such qualities for the appropriate sport. Psychological symptoms such as motivation and mental sharpness can directly impact performances, for example, not being alert to opposition, or poor reactions (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Read *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022). Finally, the distraction, inconvenience, or worry of bleeding was commonly recognised as directly impacting performance (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Adam *et al.*, 2022; Hyde and Zipp, 2023; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Kit colours were often referenced as a key influence within this (Findlay *et al.*, 2020).

Work within football (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024) found that of the 40% of elite and junior players who reported their training or competition to be impacted as a result of their MC, symptom prevalence, pelvic pain and HMB were all positively correlated. The vast majority (89%) reported this disruption to be whilst menstruating. This study failed to distinguish in responses between elite and junior athletes, nor between level of competition (domestic versus international). Furthermore, the detail of performance disruption was dictated through a close-ended multiple-choice question for participants to select from pre-determined categories (i.e. coordination, speed, strength), and not outlined which direction they perceived this relationship to be (positive or negative). This potentially limits the richness of data received, and a truer understanding of individual experiences. Self-reported menstrual phase has been noted within other studies (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; G. Brown *et al.*, 2024; Armour *et al.*, 2020a), however results within these studies differed. This is considered to be due to the lived experience of the athlete, with McNamara and colleagues (2022) utilising a survey within Olympic and Paralympic athletes (n = 195), and qualitative data reinforcing the fact that gold medals are won in every phase of the cycle, including menstruation. This recognises the fact positives have been noted by athletes, with even some athletes reporting their best results whilst competing during menstruation (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; McNamara, Harris and Minahan, 2022). The most desirable point in the cycle by 42% of Olympic and Paralympic athletes (n = 195) was deemed to be in the period just after menstruation (McNamara, Harris and Minahan, 2022). With the MC a key indicator of health (American Academy of Pediatrics *et al.*, 2006), it is crucial to consider the

wording of studies investigating the impact upon performance, to ensure it is not bias towards promoting a negative response.

The impact of HC use, and therefore potential side effects, upon performance values is found to be mixed within the literature. Work within rugby (Brown *et al.*, 2023) found fewer players reporting performance impacts (10%) compared to the ranges outlined above related to MC effects. However, work within football did not find HC use to significantly affect the perceived training and performance disruption (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024). This study however did not outline HC use in the detail recommended by recent research to ensure clarity upon comparison (Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2013, 2020). Moreover, 47% of athletes within a multi-sport cohort using OCPs reported a variation in performance over their pill-cycle, with the most perceived negative point to be in the inactive/ pill-free stage (Ekenros *et al.*, 2022). No significant differences were found in symptom prevalence between HC users and naturally menstruating athletes (Clarke *et al.*, 2021), yet work from Martin *et al.* (Martin *et al.*, 2018) found HC users were significantly more likely to report positive effects of HCs than negative effects. Therefore, the large variation in responses highlights the highly individual nature of HC use, with other factors such as reasons for use and menstrual history to play a significant role upon HC use within athletes.

To conclude, there is overwhelming evidence to suggest both active women, and elite athletes, perceive significant impacts to their training and competitive performances as a result of their menstrual characteristics or experiences. This may be further reinforced by the information they receive through media or other means in which the societal discourse pushes the negative attitudes regarding menstruation (Chapter 2.6). Ensuring women receive adequate support to manage their symptoms and performances is crucial, whilst work must also be ongoing within the culture of support to improve the visibility, education and discussion regarding menstrual health.

2.4 Adolescent Considerations

2.4.1 Adolescent Physiology

In addition to the physiological model of the MC outlined in Chapter 2.2.1, there are a number of considerations to be made when discussing the pre, mid and post-pubertal influences. The onset of maturation marks a critical timepoint in the development of adolescents and has significant implications upon the physical and psychological health. The initial phase of puberty is thelarche, or breast development, followed by other indicators of pubertal maturation such as pubic hair development, growth spurt, and finally menarche. A study of U.S. adolescents ($n = 610$) found average age of thelarche to be 9.7 years (Cabrera *et al.*, 2014). Menarche is the first menstrual period, typically occurring between 10 – 16 years (average = 12.4 years), and happens 2-3 years post-thelarche when Tanner stage IV is achieved (Cabrera *et al.*, 2014). The first indicator of menarche is the rise of oestradiol, which eventually rises to promote a surge in LH and promote the cyclical menstrual response. Carlson and Shaw (2019) state that the majority of early cycles are anovulatory, however there is a lack of evidence to conclusively show when indeed these cycles become ovulatory. This anovulatory status is considered to be due to the inability of oestradiol to promote the LH surge consistently, and this therefore not causing ovulation and the dominant follicle does not transform into corpus luteum and trigger progesterone production (Calcaterra *et al.*, 2024). There is difficulty in measuring this, or for diagnosing menstrual abnormalities as cycle length can typically be utilised as a first-stage diagnostic tool for ovulation in women, yet this cannot be replicated in adolescents (Calcaterra *et al.*, 2024). Early work by Apter and Vihko (1977) upon 200 girls aged 7 – 17years ($n = 200$) found that 80% developed ovulatory cycles within 5 gynaecological years. This is mirrored in adolescent self-reported data from a large U.S. cohort ($n = 38,916$) where those in the first year post-menarche had lower odds of heavy menstrual flow and increased variability in cycles to those 6+ years post menarche due to the immaturity of the HPA (Harley *et al.*, 2024). Cycle length is known to be variable, with clinical guidelines suggesting 21 – 45 days to be a more appropriate window. By three years post-menarche, cycle length can typically shorten to a 21 – 35 day window in line with adult normal classifications (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2013).

2.4.2 Adolescent Menstrual Cycle Symptomology and Cycle Disturbances

Adolescents, similar to adults, experience a range of symptoms related to their MC, varying in prevalence, severity and duration dependent upon the individual and influenced by personal experiences. However, due to the irregularity of cycles within the years post-menarche, this results in symptoms potentially being more unpredictable and at times, more severe. Physical symptoms reported within adolescents include tiredness (78%), pelvic pain (71%), and feeling down or depressed (65%) within Australian high school girls (n = 1803; Parker, Sneddon and Arbon, 2010). Research has also found significant associations between physical menstrual symptoms with psychological symptoms, such as depressive symptoms (Beal *et al.*, 2014). Dysmenorrhoea is commonly experienced by adolescents, with a meta-analysis from Armour *et al.* (2019) finding the overall prevalence rate within age 13-23 years to be 71%, however this can be as high as 92%, with average severity ratings as moderate to severe (Armour *et al.*, 2020b). Moreover, increasing age is seen to reduce the prevalence of dysmenorrhoea (Parker, Sneddon and Arbon, 2010; Lindh, Ellstrom and Milsom, 2012). This can be as much as ~30% with each year the age of menarche increased within a cohort of Belgian adolescents (Hoppenbrouwers *et al.*, 2016). Early menarcheal age, often termed ‘early maturer’ is considered to be a risk factor for dysmenorrhoea (Harley *et al.*, 2024). Dysmenorrhoea can also be a secondary symptom of other health conditions which may in some cases fail to be recognised well throughout adolescence, such as endometriosis (Harel, 2006; De Sanctis *et al.*, 2015), highlighting the need for further support for young girls, even if their symptoms may fall into what they perceive to be normal. A sample of Australian girls found that 10% reporting that they were ‘sure’ there was something wrong with their period (Parker, Sneddon and Arbon, 2010), yet when prevalences of menstrual disruptions, severe symptoms, and disorders are outlined, the need for education to girls is clear.

Adolescents can also experience a range of disturbances and subsequent health impacts related to their MC. Firstly, HMB is estimated to affect 4 – 63% of adolescent girls according to a recent systematic review (Pouraliroudbaneh *et al.*, 2024) and commonly attributed to anovulatory cycles or underlying bleeding disorders. As stipulated by Zia *et al.* (2020), anovulatory bleeding is often excluded within studies, thus limiting the information available regarding adolescents. Presence of HMB is found to be significantly associated to iron deficiencies (65%) and anaemia (36%) within a large multicentre cohort of adolescent girls (n = 200; Zia *et*

al., 2020). Furthermore, MC disturbances such as polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) have been found to be difficult to recognise in adolescents due to the development of features typical of reproductive maturation, such as irregular cycles, hyperandrogenism and insulin resistance (Rosenfield, 2015; Witchel *et al.*, 2015; Carlson and Shaw, 2019). For example, comedonal acne is a key indicator of androgen excess, and thus difficult to distinguish as a menstrual disorder (American Academy of Pediatrics *et al.*, 2006). Furthermore, conditions such as insulin resistance or obesity have been recommended against being used as PCOS indicators within adolescents due to such difficulties in differentiating against potential developmental markers (Witchel *et al.*, 2015). Primary amenorrhoea is thought to affect a small cohort of individuals, with 98% of girls thought to reach menarche by aged 15 years (Chumlea *et al.*, 2003), however amongst adolescent athletes has been seen to range from 0 – 12% within a recent systematic review (Taim *et al.*, 2023a). Adolescence is a crucial timepoint for bone growth, the consequences of RED-S, of which amenorrhoea plays a vital role, could be problematic for long term health (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Lastly, there is limited understanding of HC use within adolescent athletes. One study within adolescent athletes found 2 of 84 athletes to report HC use, both of which utilising OCPs, one of which was due to PCOS diagnosis (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). There is no study to date investigating the prevalence and perceived effect of HC use on adolescent football players, leaving little support available to players currently to manage their HC use whilst training and competing.

2.4.3 Adolescent Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Daily Wellbeing and Activities

As outlined, there is potential for high prevalence and severity of menstrual symptoms, therefore it is important to understand the impact these can have upon general health, wellbeing and daily activities, and to facilitate means to target future support structures. Firstly, absenteeism from school is found to vary greatly within the literature, and found to be significantly associated to symptom severity, and education levels (Zannoni *et al.*, 2014). Rates of absenteeism from middle or high school included 3% of adolescents in Belgium (n = 254; Hoppenbrouwers *et al.*, 2016), 12% in Italy (n = 254; Zannoni *et al.*, 2014), 20% in Uganda (n = 352; Miiro *et al.*, 2018), and 28% in Ghana (n = 705; Kumbeni *et al.*, 2021). Supporting these findings, a meta-analysis focusing on adolescents with dysmenorrhoea found a trend towards more girls missing school within low-to-middle income countries (LMICs) (26%) to high income countries (HICs) (12%) (Armour *et al.*, 2019a). Furthermore, a 2019 study within a large cohort of women age 15 - 45

years found that age was a significant influence upon absenteeism and presenteeism (productivity loss) during work and study (Schoep *et al.*, 2019b). Further work expanding on the potential reasons behind this include the inability to manage the pain brought on by the MC and thus utilising rest as a coping mechanism/ management method (Allyn *et al.*, 2020). Within LMICs, lack of funds to purchase period products to manage bleeding was considered a key reason behind missing school, alongside symptoms, and embarrassment in hiding menstruation (Jewitt and Ryley, 2014). Many girls are known to drop out of school at an early age due to limited safe and sanitary products (Sharma *et al.*, 2017). Within HICs, the termed ‘period poverty’ (limited access to menstrual hygiene practices due to financial constraints) is prevalent and an important issue for many girls, with 12% of girls having had to improvise sanitary wear due to the affordability of period products (Plan International UK, 2017). For those that do attend school, menses can cause a distraction and thus impact their academic performance. Teachers have mirrored this perception, with Huseth-Zosel and Secor-Turner (2022) reporting survey data within the U.S (n = 209), with 801% believing menstruation to impact upon student learning, through distraction, absence, embarrassment, or symptoms experienced, supported by schoolgirls within the U.K. who noted the first two days of menstruation to be particularly impactful upon learning and engagement (N. Brown *et al.*, 2024a).

Other activities within school have also been seen to be impacted, including that of physical education (PE), with the MC commonly reported as a barrier to PE participation by both girls (N. Brown *et al.*, 2024a; Youth Sports Trust, 2024) and teachers (Brown *et al.*, 2022a). Menstruation was seen to be the primary barrier to being active in school, reported by 49% of schoolgirls (Youth Sport Trust, 2022), due to pain/ discomfort (72%), worry about leaking (61%), low mood (59%), and low energy (55%) during their period amongst key reasons given. Brown and colleagues (2024a) performed focus groups with schoolgirls within the U.K., with pupils noting symptoms such as menstrual-related breast pain to impact sporting participation, alongside the type of exercise to be performed (exercises including running or jumping were not favourable for involvement during menstruation). Some schoolgirls however, either prioritised sporting involvement and participated in PE despite menstrual symptoms, or did not experience MC symptoms to limit their involvement, highlighting the individual nature of experiences from a young age.

The severity of symptoms has also been noted as impactful upon social disturbances amongst adolescent girls. Whilst 25% postmenarcheal girls (n = 342) from Belgium indicated a negative impact of their menstruation upon social activities within the past 3 months of the survey, this rose to 41% in those who experienced painful menstruation (Hoppenbrouwers *et al.*, 2016). In addition, the psychological and emotional symptoms which can occur as a result of the MC, and especially in conditions such as PMS or PMDD, can significantly alter adolescents' behaviours and social skills. The presence of PMS has been found to be significantly associated to the prevalence of depression and anxiety amongst rural adolescent girls (n = 430; Mann and TS, 2023). Furthermore, research has found links between MC phase and perceived body image within adolescent girls (Kaczmarek and Trambacz-Oleszak, 2016), but also that of MC irregularity and high scoring upon key indicators of eating disorders (Drosdzol-Cop *et al.*, 2017), highlighting the range of considerations to make when assessing the impact of the MC upon wellbeing.

2.4.4 Adolescent Menstrual Cycle Impacts upon Athletic Performance

There is mixed evidence upon the role of being physically active from a young age upon subsequent menstrual experiences. Some evidence has shown that intense exercise has the potential to delay menarche, with a meta-analysis from Calthorpe *et al.* (2018) showing later mean age at menarche if training pre-menarche, compared to those who took up sport post-menarche. However, there is a lack of conclusive evidence to support this finding, with recent work in judo (Athayde *et al.*, 2021) and multi-sports (Taim *et al.*, 2023b) reporting a mean age of menarche of 11.8 ± 1.2 years and 11.9 ± 1.3 years, respectively. Furthermore, recent evidence suggests the overall age of menarche is lowering in adolescents globally due to improvements in nutrition and socioeconomic status (Wahab *et al.*, 2020; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). However, rates of menstrual dysfunction can, in some sports, be higher than average. Gymnastics (25%), football (20%) and swimming (19%) were found to have the highest prevalence of primary dysmenorrhoea, within a recent review of 48 studies (Gimunová *et al.*, 2022), however this included studies with values as high as 54% within a cohort of elite Chinese gymnasts, versus 13.2% in recreational athletes (Meng *et al.*, 2020). The issues associated with the female athlete triad extends to adolescent athletes, with 36% of high school athletes experiencing low energy availability, reported via food diaries and self-reported MC information (Hoch *et al.*, 2009). Almost a third (30%) also recorded

secondary amenorrhoea (the absence of menstrual bleeding for three or more months), compared to 15% of non-athletes within the same schools. With self-reported data utilised for energy availability and amenorrheic status, drawing conclusions or comparing across sporting disciplines is limited. With evidence showing the link amenorrhoea can have with negative outcomes such as disordered eating and low bone mineral density (BMD), identification of menstrual dysfunctions and suitable support strategies is critical (Golden, 2002). There is limited longitudinal data to conclude the long-term implications this may have; a 3-year follow up study in adolescent runners (initially aged 15.9 +/-0.2yrs) highlighted that 87% of those originally with low BMD (38% of total sample) still experienced it three-years following (Barrack *et al.*, 2011). Thus, with the known links to RED-S, gathering more supportive evidence, especially in football, to understand the longitudinal effects of RED-S, plus the impact of supportive practices, is required.

The impact of the MC upon sporting performance is understudied within adolescent athletes. To date, two studies have provided evidence to outline the adolescent experience within sport. Singaporean adolescent athletes (n = 90) reported their MC to impact their ability to train (62%) and compete (67%) respectively (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Absenteeism from training was noted by 27% of athletes, yet none had missed a competition. This study did not account for training being modified as a result of the athlete stepping out, or pre-determined load reduction with the coach (which, despite known communication difficulties, may be worth accounting for). Furthermore, menses was perceived to be the stage in their cycle they performed “worst” within. ‘Pain’ was overwhelmingly cited as the reason athletes would ever modify their training (20%) or competition (15%). Further work within adolescent athletes through semi-structured interviews noted that adolescent athletes often adopted a resilient approach to push through any pain to prioritise their sport (Keil, Adam and Neely, 2024). The authors also include athletes’ perceptions of why their performance is impacted, through the loss of motivation due to pain, mental stress, or fear of injury. However, the mental aspect during menses was also seen to be a positive and aid performance, again highlighting the individual nature of experiences and the manifestation of symptomology. Thus far, there has not been a study focusing solely on adolescent footballers in regard to their menstrual characteristics in a performance setting. Understanding MC characteristics from early post-menarcheal years was identified as a key research opportunity

within a recent commentary (McNulty *et al.*, 2024). Without this understanding, it is difficult to conclude what appropriate support may look like within academy structures.

2.5 Menstrual Health Management

With the known impacts of menstrual experiences on daily activities, wellbeing and perceived performance outcomes, women employ a number of means to manage their cycle to maximise their productivity and lessen the impacts they may experience. Management strategies cover a broad range of considerations, from products to manage bleeding, to symptom management, and longer-term options such as HC. These strategies are highly varied dependent on preference, health considerations and previous experiences (Santer, Wyke and Warner, 2008). This rings true within sport, however extra considerations may be required when catering for the demands of the sport. Athletes have been known to utilise internal coping strategies when managing pain or bleeding, with the often referred having to “*deal with it*” commonly reported by athletes (Read *et al.*, 2024; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). However, the inconvenience, severity and frequency of symptoms may lead athletes to exploring ways to minimise any potential impact.

2.5.1 Menstrual Product Use

Firstly, period products are used routinely throughout menstruation to conceal or manage bleeding (van Eijk *et al.*, 2021; Kolić *et al.*, 2023). A self-reported questionnaire from female exercisers (n = 604) found disposable pads (65%) and tampons (64%) (Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.*, 2024) were the most common forms of period products used. Furthermore, this study found 47% participants utilised more than one menstrual product simultaneously, often considered to be driven by potential heavy bleeding, or reassurance of limiting leaks, a common fear amongst athletes (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Adam *et al.*, 2022; Keil, Adam and Neely, 2024). However, other products are becoming increasingly popular, such as menstrual underwear (period pants), or menstrual cups or discs. There is an environmental consideration due to the re-usable nature of these products opposed to single use pads or tampons (Liberty *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, menstrual underwear is potentially a more accessible option for those with visual or mobility impairments (McGregor and Unsworth, 2022). Product use is also dependent on the heaviness of bleeding. A study assessing differences in red blood cell capacity of menstrual

products found on average a menstrual disc to hold the most blood (61mL), and period underwear held the least (2mL) (DeLoughery *et al.*, 2024), however this was highly dependent on branding due to the lack of regulation in absorbency in underwear technology and would therefore require more changes throughout the day (Liberty *et al.*, 2023). Further reasons for product choice may include convenience, skin-irritation, and feasibility of product cleaning (van Eijk *et al.*, 2021; Liberty *et al.*, 2023). The reason for product choice in athletes may be multi-factorial, and dependent upon time training, kit worn, movements within exercise or other matters of personal preference. Moreover, athletes have reported wearing menstrual products despite not being on their period, but in fear of starting menses during their competition (Brown and Knight, 2022). It is also important to consider the subsequent behaviour changes invoked by the need to change period products. Work from Santer, Wyke and Warner (2008) displayed polarising views on this, with one semi-structured interview stating an indifferent view to changing products within public toilets, whereas another would not dispose of products and instead would carry used items in her bag, which then limited her going out during her period. The products utilised, however, were not outlined. There is limited evidence highlighting menstrual product use within an adolescent sporting population, as in the one study known to outline adolescent experiences of the MC, this topic was not covered (Taim *et al.*, 2023b).

2.5.2 Medicative Management Methods

In regard to symptom management, both medicative and non-medicative means are commonly utilised to lessen cramps, headaches, or other symptoms commonly experienced (Warden, 2009; Armour *et al.*, 2021). There is currently no universal approach to treating symptoms, and often management approaches are selected through personal preference and prior experiences. The use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as aspirin or ibuprofen, work through the inhibition of prostaglandin production, thus limiting the inflammatory response often involved in the manifestation of pain (Warden, 2009). Australian adolescent schoolgirls report usage of 49.8% ibuprofen and 54% paracetamol (non-opioid analgesic) to manage MC symptoms, however the recommended dosages were repeatedly undertaken by 37% and 44% participants for each medication, respectively (Armour *et al.*, 2021). Work by Armour and colleagues also reported the perceived effectiveness of analgesics by young women (age 13-25 years), with mefenamic acid (29%) being significantly greater at perceptually relieving pain compared to ibuprofen (13%) and

paracetamol (11%), however may be due to the usage of mefenamic acid prior to pain (Armour *et al.*, 2021). Within the U.K., mefenamic acid is a prescribed pain relief medication which may be a barrier to access. Within sport, 46% of Australian athletes used ibuprofen to combat pain due to their cycle (Armour *et al.*, 2020a), with 21% utilising paracetamol and 12% combining both medications. This can be to remove the symptoms they are affected by, or to reduce pain to a manageable level where they feel they can still perform (Findlay *et al.*, 2020). The long-term usage of NSAIDs is deemed unsafe, and so athletes need to consider alternative approaches available to them (Warden, 2009). Furthermore, the usage of pain medication in youth athletes is not fully understood. A study which included 220 youth female handball players saw 62% utilise some form of pain medication within the past 4 weeks, with non-injury purposes of utilising paracetamol and NSAIDs as 65% and 61%, respectively, however not focused solely on menstrual management purposes (Sari *et al.*, 2021). There remains a need to understand the use of medication to manage pain relief and other menstrual symptoms within an adolescent football association, in order to target suitable alternatives and/or support.

2.5.3 Non- Medicative Management Methods

There is a range of non-medicative symptom management methods employed by women, utilised either instead of or in conjunction with medication. Firstly, the general population identified the limiting of activities was used to manage the impact of their bleeding and/or symptoms, with 28% of women surveyed (n = 622) reported that they had stopped normal activities for at least some of their period (Santer, Wyke and Warner, 2008). This includes changing work patterns and domestic responsibilities. Other management methods utilised within the general population were hot water bottle (46%), rest (32%) and bathing (17%), with exercise noted by 4% of participants (Santer, Wyke and Warner, 2008). The use of heat therapies on minimising menstrual pain has been seen to be beneficial by a meta-analysis, compared to both no treatment, and the use of analgesics, however highlights the limited high-quality evidence currently available to draw broad conclusions in regard to its' efficacy (Jo and Lee, 2018). Heat therapies are also found to be a coping mechanism within elite athletes (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021).

Exercise is also considered a symptom management method within the general population. Exercise, regardless of intensity, is found to promote a reduction in menstrual pain if performed

multiple times within a week (O'Brien *et al.*, 2011; Modzelewski *et al.*, 2024; Armour *et al.*, 2019b). There remains a lack of understanding for how this may be impactful, potentially due to the overwhelming nature of very low to low quality evidence within the field (Armour *et al.*, 2019b). Exercise is thought to be clinically significant upon the reduction of dysmenorrhoea compared to no treatment (Dehnavi, Jafarnejad and Kamali, 2018; Armour *et al.*, 2019b), and is recommended by national guidelines for the management of PMS (The American College of Obstetrics and Gynecologists, 2023). In the broader context, exercise is overwhelmingly found to be beneficial in the treatment and/or regulation of low mood, anxiety, or depressive symptoms often experienced throughout the cycle (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.*, 2024) due to the increased endorphin levels to regulate progesterone and oestrogen synthesis, and reduce cortisol levels (Modzelewski *et al.*, 2024). This is often exacerbated in those with PMS or PMDD, with studies finding exercise to be beneficial to the reduction in psychological symptoms in adults (Kroll-Desrosiers *et al.*, 2017; Mohebbi-Dehnavi *et al.*, 2017). Little evidence to date has focused on the topic within adolescent athletes, despite high levels of menstrual disturbances noted within the literature (Calcaterra *et al.*, 2024; Armour *et al.*, 2019a). Further improvements of exercising to physical health include the potentially positive impact upon fatigue, headaches, and muscle cramps following consistently exercise throughout the MC (Daley, 2008, 2009; Kroll-Desrosiers *et al.*, 2017). A 2017 study highlighted the complexity in recording this data, as those with greater severity of symptoms may have been recommended to utilise exercise as a management strategy for their physical symptoms, and thus the significant effects noted in the literature potentially have a reverse causation effect (Kroll-Desrosiers *et al.*, 2017), leaving it difficult to understand the true effects as 'pain' is highly subjective. Within sport, athletes often refer to training having a positive response on their menstrual symptoms (Findlay *et al.*, 2020). However, there is limited evidence on the use of exercise as a management strategy in adolescents within the general population, and to the author's knowledge, no research including adolescent athletes to understand if this is a useful endeavour to manage symptoms. Furthermore, a systematic review by Daley also highlights the lack of clarity around symptom classification and measurement, inconsistent reporting, and a lack of recent studies limiting the ability to substantiate the true effect of exercise upon menstrual symptoms (Daley, 2008).

There is emerging evidence to promote the use of nutritional strategies in the management of menstrual symptoms. Women and girls often cite food cravings or increased appetite as a menstrual symptom (Hantsoo *et al.*, 2022; Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.*, 2024), as do athletes (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; Heyward *et al.*, 2022; Taim *et al.*, 2023a). However, this is often with the notion these foods referenced are high in sugar, salt and processed foods (Heyward *et al.*, 2020). Dietary recommendations and supplementation are in its infancy of research and show potentially promising findings for those with disorders such as PMS. This includes the use of calcium carbonate (Zarei *et al.*, 2017), zinc (Zekavat *et al.*, 2015; Jafari, Amani and Tarrahi, 2020), and vitamin D (Abdollahi *et al.*, 2019). A recent meta-analysis from Brown and colleagues found that of 28 studies, 23 reported a positive effect. However, there were 18 methods of measuring MC symptoms, highlighted the lack of consistency in methodological approaches often recognised in conjunction with menstrual health studies (N. Brown *et al.*, 2024b). This again highlights the need for a united approach in the measurement of MC status, including symptomology to ensure interventions are efficacious (Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021). Finally, a key method often included in guidance to manage symptoms, especially when severe symptoms arise due to PMS or PMDD, is that of education (O'Brien *et al.*, 2011). Within sport, there remains limited documentation of this education and its efficacy in improving self-management, despite showing promising results in young women in the general population (Armour *et al.*, 2021).

2.5.4 Contraceptive Management Methods

The development of menstrual management strategies is often as a result of prior experiences. Management methods thus far have focused on those with eumenorrhic cycles. The use of HC is a common way to manage, or mitigate bleeding or symptoms experienced throughout the MC. Whilst the primary reason for use remains contraceptive purposes, some HC methods have been widely studied and utilised as a management method for those with menstrual disorders, such as dysmenorrhoea, endometriosis, or PMDD (Pearlstein *et al.*, 2005; Schindler, 2013; Modzelewski *et al.*, 2024). Before prescribing HCs, medical professionals will typically take into a count a number of factors to deem an individual safe to utilise the intended method. For example, upon initial approval of OCPs significant associations upon those with hypertension were highlighted and thus require deliberation upon the safety to each individual when considering the role of hypertension upon cardiovascular disease. This is considered to be due to the synthetic oestrogen

compound, ethinyl oestradiol which possesses vascular and hepatic effects resulting in potentials for inflammation, thrombotic effects and vascular resistance (Curtis *et al.*, 2006; Shufelt and LeVee, 2020). There are multiple other factors to consider, such as age, further health conditions and other lifestyle factors, again contributing to the individual approach to be taken when choosing HC methods (Shufelt and Bairey, 2009).

It has been shown that HCs can be used effectively to manage MC symptoms. This includes COCs, not progesterone only, due to the potential for mood-symptoms to increase for those with mood-disorders such as PMS (Sundström-Poromaa *et al.*, 2020). Conversely, the use of progesterone-only HC methods has shown relief from symptoms in those who suffer from endometriosis, due to the reduction of pelvic pain and size of endometrial lesions (Vercellini *et al.*, 1999; Harada *et al.*, 2008). Adolescents are often prescribed HC upon medical consultation when referencing symptoms such as dysmenorrhoea or acne (Harel, 2006; De Sanctis *et al.*, 2015; Sachedin and Todd, 2020). The use of combined oral contraceptives for acne is thought to be due to the ability to regulate androgen levels, and considered to be efficacious for post-menarcheal adolescents seeking contraception options (Du *et al.*, 2011; Smith *et al.*, 2025). Other symptoms in which HC may be utilised to manage include mastalgia, migraines, and bloating (Berenson *et al.*, 2008). Whilst such management methods have been caused to promote significant relief from menstrual symptoms, there are often side effects which require consideration when deciding upon HC use. These include mood changes, weight gain and inter-menstrual bleeding (Berenson *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, long-term use of HC to manage cycle disorders does not address the underlying issues affecting women and girls' physiology. There is a paucity of longitudinal research on the long-term health effects of HC. For example, a 1996 study investigating HC methods on bone density found those utilising depot medroxyprogesterone acetate (Depo-Provera/ injection) had decreased bone density after 2-years usage, compared to improvements seen by OCP and implant users, and a control group (Cromer *et al.*, 1996). The use of HC is subject to individual health considerations and personal preference and highlights the need for individualised care for symptom management with careful consideration.

Whilst contraceptive purposes remain the primary reason for HC, the ability to utilise HC as a method to manage and/or manipulate bleeding windows has been perceived as a worthwhile

endeavour for its use amongst athletes (Bennell, White and Crossley, 1999; Schaumberg *et al.*, 2018; Adam *et al.*, 2022). Two studies within Australian sports found the ability to regulate cycles alone accounted for 38% and 53% of HC use from athletes, respectively (Clarke *et al.*, 2021; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). This included the ability to skip their period due to convenience (22%) and to reduce the impact upon sporting events (19%) (Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Furthermore, 36% of athletes reported using HC to mitigate pain (Clarke *et al.*, 2021), the most commonly identified menstrual symptom. Research within sportswomen suggests those utilising HC experience significantly fewer symptoms than non-HC users (Martin *et al.*, 2018; Heyward *et al.*, 2022). However, negative side effects from HC methods is often mentioned by athletes as a reason they stopped taking them (Clarke *et al.*, 2021; McNamara, Harris and Minahan, 2022). Mood was cited as a key side effect by 43% of those who reported side effects as a result of HC use within Australian sportswomen (Armour *et al.*, 2020a). The inclusion of adolescent athletes within studies reporting HC prevalence is limited. Taim and colleagues found that 2% Singaporean adolescent athletes utilised OCP, with the low rate proposed to be due to the cultural context in which data was collected (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Further supporting evidence including adolescent athletes would be valuable to ensure future support is targeted appropriately.

2.6 Societal Perspectives of the Menstrual Cycle

The historical views of menstruation have been shaped by cultural, societal and religious influences. Menstruation has long been seen a sign of sexual maturation and thus reproductive potential. Historic cultures have varied interpretations of what menstruation represents; whilst some understood it as sacred, and a gift, others believed it to be unclean, destructive, and a punishment (Johnston-Robledo and Chrisler, 2020). There remains ambiguity over the original negative interpretation of menstruation. Many religions view menstruation as an ‘impurity’, one which can often separate women from men and places of worship dependent upon their menstrual state (Summers, 2017). Furthermore, biblical code considered the ‘impurity’ to be contagious and unclean (Mazokopakis and Samonis, 2018). This isolation continues into modern history when, due to their MC, it was often considered that women should be deemed unfit for higher education due to the time spent in menses, and physical activity was considered dangerous to menstrual health (Vertinsky, 1987; Newton, 2016b).

2.6.1 Historical Menstrual Stigmas

Historically, the introduction of menses into a young girl's life, through menarche, was considered a critical transition into womanhood, and thus childbearing. So much so, stigmatisation exists if menarche comes later in adolescence for some and are therefore physically less developed (Olson *et al.*, 2022). At this young stage, it is often taught to hide menstruation, both physically through the use of menstrual management products, but even in discussion within a home environment (Roberts *et al.*, 2002; van Lonkhuijzen, Garcia and Wagemakers, 2023). The taboo is often established at this point in adolescence, with girls taught that discussing menstruation is socially unacceptable (McHugh, 2020). Furthermore, the first menses can often occur without girls having previously received the education of what would be expected, and thus invokes a stress response due to the lack of understanding of what is happening to their body and serves to further reinforce negative connotations of the act of menstruation (Betsu *et al.*, 2023; van Lonkhuijzen, Garcia and Wagemakers, 2023). Within the U.K., a 2018 PLAN UK report highlighted that 14% of adolescent girls did not know what was happening when they initially started their period (Youth Sports Trust, 2018). For those who do know about menarche prior to its onset, it is proposed that girls now hit puberty with the preconceived notion that menstruation is negative, due to the taboos infiltrated throughout their peers, media and education (McKeever, 1984). This is true to date, as even when 'breaking barriers' around discussion is often referenced as a positive in promoting the weakening of menstrual stigmas, the conversation often shared between women remains negative (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). Often women only highlight negative symptoms, and conversation can often promote the discourse that women's bodies are imperfect and weakened (Lee and Sasser-Coen, 1996). Furthermore, even when connection and sharing stories may be positive in increasing the visibility of menstruation as a topic, the so called "menstrual moaning" may reinforce shame rather than promote empowerment as it fails to recognise the socio-cultural impact upon menstrual stigmas (McHugh, 2020).

2.6.2 Manifestation of Menstrual Stigmas

Menstrual stigma can often be demonstrated by the behaviours found commonly within society. With menstruation often treated as a private, or secret, matter, women and girls often conceal any reference to their own menstruation. This can be through the discrete use of menstrual products or

avoidance of discussion on the topic (Moffat and Pickering, 2019; Johnston-Robledo and Chrisler, 2020). Furthermore, society often does not facilitate appropriate support to allow women and girls to manage their menstruation. Moffat and Pickering (2019) refer to this as a double burden, in which women feel the need to conceal menstruation, yet the ability to do so is limited by the infrastructure to support this and contribute to the “social invisibility” of menstruation. This infrastructure may include appropriate changing facilities, menstrual product availability and costs, and increased visibility of support routes, either medical or non-medical. For example, until recently in many countries, the so called “tampon-tax” allowed consumption levies on menstrual products to be taxed at the same rate as other “non-essential” products, when many would instead view it as a necessity. A number of global menstrual activism movements (Howarth and Edge, 2015; USA Today, 2022) occurred prior to the removal of such levies in countries such as Australia (*BBC News*, 2018), Germany (Gallagher, 2019) and finally the U.K. in 2021 (GOV.UK, 2021). Scotland also became the first country in 2020 to promote the free availability of products within public facilities, including schools, to reduce the period poverty which is known to exist within even the more-developed countries (Scottish Government, 2021). This act was implemented following a successful trial period, in which almost 90% of schoolpupils who responded to the evaluation reported that they were less worried to have their period in school due to the products available (Social Research, 2022).

An example of societal taboos promoting secrecy or distain can often be found in the media’s portrayal of menstruation. Mass media, including television, radio, print, and digital platforms, play a significant role in shaping public perceptions of menstruation. Historically, advertisements have been heavily censored in their visual content and language utilised. For instance, the word “period” was only first said in a Tampax television advertisement in 1985 (*BBC News*, 2022). The emphasis on discretion references the secrecy associated with bleeding, stressing the need for women to avoid the embarrassment of bleeding through clothing, or alerting anyone to the state of menstruation (Przybylo and Fahs, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2023). This contributed to feelings of fear and shame experienced by women and girls. Additionally, the use of euphemisms (e.g. “time of the month”) and the portrayal of menstrual blood as blue liquid instead of red perpetuates the idea that menstruation is something to be hidden or sanitized, referencing the historical narrative of menstrual ‘hygiene’ (Johnston-Robledo and Chrisler, 2020). Media

portrayal of menstruating individuals often focuses on negative aspects, such as mood swings or inconvenience, rather than promoting the sign that regular menstruation can be a sign of health (McHugh, 2020; Piran, 2020). Furthermore, a societal shift in gendered roles contributes to campaigns promoting women in leadership capacities not being limited by their menstruation (Fahs and Collins, 2024). The consideration of active women was also a focus, with messaging and imagery suggesting bleeding shouldn't impede athletic performance. For example, a 2009 advertisement utilised the tagline "A champion like Serena Williams doesn't let Mother Nature's Monthly Gift interrupt her game", with the tennis star dressed in white (Procter and Gamble, 2009). Despite the progression in discussion, the avoidance of language and visuals related to bleeding remains evident. A longitudinal thematic analysis studying menstrual product advertisements from the past 100-years found that the messages promoted by campaigns have not significantly changed through time, highlighting the stigma that remains engrained within society and will be inherited by the younger generation (Fahs and Collins, 2024). Media representation and public discourse are powerful tools for shaping menstrual health literacy and challenging societal norms and taboos around menstruation. While traditional mass media has often reinforced negative stereotypes and secrecy, recent trends in advertising, television, and online platforms are moving towards more open and positive representations of menstruation. In recent years, social media is thought to contribute to an open platform to promote discussion, peer support, and advocate for menstrual equity and highlight the importance of menstrual health (Bobel and Fahs, 2020). A 2015 post to social media site Instagram sparked controversy when artist Rupri Kaur posted pictures including a menstrual stain, and the company removed the post due to rule violations (Cafolla, 2015). Kaur utilised this to initiate a public discourse to promote the normative frame society utilised to remove visibility and invoke shame upon women for a natural biological phenomenon (McHugh, 2020). However, this is not always representative of society; content analysis through over 2000 "tweets" (now 'X') in 2010 portrayed menstruation with anger, frustration, and disdain (Thornton, 2013). One key theme, 'anger and frustration' was overwhelmingly from males (86%), with tweets voicing complaint regarding embarrassment, deprivation from sex, and at times expressing misogyny and violence. Thus, there remains substantial work to weaken the stigma associated to menstruation and ensure women can receive support in a safe environment.

2.6.3 Modern Day Menstrual Stigmas

Menstrual stigma is known to alter methods of communication and behaviours within the general and sporting population. The use of euphemisms to avoid direct conversation is employed widely between both men and women as a result of menstruation being thought to require concealment (Newton, 2016a). Overall, conversation is thought to be limited due to the awkwardness felt, again due to the taboos reinforced throughout history and modern day. This is also true and visible within sport. Barriers are often recognised by active exercisers regarding their management of their MC within physical activity. Changes to clothing to ensuring leakage would be less likely were reported by active exercisers, as was the positioning in the gym to avoid potential visibility of leaking, and change of exercise selection to avoid movements where leakage may be more likely (Kolić *et al.*, 2023, 2024). The overwhelming shame of menstruation being visible highlights the engrained menstrual “etiquette” found and reinforced regularly (Moffat and Pickering, 2019), and can lead to exclusions of women due to discomfort. Furthermore, within elite sport, athletes recognise these barriers exist in limiting the discussion they have within sport, and subsequently the support they may receive to manage their cycle and symptoms alongside their training and performance. Both elite senior and adolescent athletes frequently report feeling awkward or embarrassed to discuss their menstrual experiences with their coach, and furthermore, perceive their coach will feel uncomfortable if they do initiate this conversation (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Therefore, communication barriers are known to exist as a result of menstrual stigmas and have been found to infiltrate sport.

Bobel and Fahs (2020) stress within their recent work that as menstrual activism as a social movement is indeed progressing, it potentially fails to address the endemic issues of the menstrual stigma, leaving work still to be done in addressing the problem itself, to leave this topic as a historical discussion piece. McAllister and colleagues further attest to this through their argument that despite literature pushing the narrative of developing discussion, global health policies cease to reflect this (McAllister *et al.*, 2025). Moreover, it is often considered a problem of hygiene, and fails to account for the health disparities (World Health Organisation, 2023) and menstrual justice, encapsulating topics such as discrimination, economic disadvantages, exclusions, and indignities (Amery *et al.*, 2023). This so-called ‘menstrual justice’ highlights the expansive approach that must be taken to truly consider the cost of menstruation within a global context (Johnson, 2019),

with law and social change required to ensure menstrual activism is effective. Thus, when considering policy changes within sport, understanding those affected is critical. Historically, sport has included rules irrespective of gender, failing to account for the menstrual-specific factors females may experience. In recent years, there has been some relaxation to policies. For example, Wimbledon allowing dark undershorts in 2022 (Guardian Sport, 2022), numerous football teams stepping away from white shorts (*BBC Sport, 2023; BBC Sport, 2022*), and rugby accounting for menstrual product changes in their “blood-stoppages” (England Rugby, n.d.). Athletes themselves have noted that they perceive the narrative is changing to a more positive culture within sport (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). Whilst these are positive advancements in the consideration of female athletes, this does not remove the impact of menstruation upon performance and may not encapsulate the full root of the issue experienced. Moreover, the advancements in policy and support relies on women being vocal about their experiences, which can be difficult to overcome the societal silence to do so. Without addressing the stigma which upholds the shame from women, and thus silence, women will remain unable to access the support they may require, within both general society and within sport.

2.7 Menstrual Health Education

Personal health literacy (HL) is an umbrella term that summarises the *“degree to which individuals have the ability to find, understand, and use information and services to inform health-related decisions and actions for themselves and others”* (Bobel and Fahs, 2020). The 2030 Healthy People consensus, a framework of health objectives set by the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, highlights not only the correlation between poor HL and poor health outcomes, including higher morbidity rates, but also health disparities, increased healthcare costs, and lower-quality care (Santana *et al.*, 2021). Personal HL is markedly subject to societal, cultural, and organisational contextual factors dictating the accessibility to, and appropriateness of services to improve literacy, and thus, health outcomes (Braveman and Gottlieb, 2014). Whilst women have often been seen to possess greater HL levels than men, a report from the U.S. Department of Health (2004) noted 12% of women still had below “basic” levels. Furthermore, recent research has confirmed that further barriers are observed to obstruct the service of women’s health needs within current models of health services, including the inclusion of women’s health-specific research

(Department of Health and Social Care, 2022). Therefore, the limited HL of women, combined with the lack of recognition of female-specific support often prevents girls from being aware of, or accessing, the appropriate services they may need require. One key aspect of female-specific support is that which seeks to improve menstrual health and hygiene (MHH), with menstrual health literacy (MHL) alluding to the ability to apply knowledge and seek support to manage MC or associated factors. A key determinant of MHL is socio-economic status, contributing to not only the ability to attend school in some countries to receive education on the topic, but then also access to the physical resources (period products) to manage bleeding (Rossouw and Ross, 2021). Moreover, the subsequent stigmatisation of seeking help further limits individuals' awareness of their access routes to gynaecological education or support from a medical standpoint. Furthermore, with limited research focusing on MHL within sport on athletes or those who support them, this topic requires further consideration.

HL is often characterised in three ways to detail the different avenues HL can be acquired or utilised; functional, interactive and critical, with HL often considered to progress in this order respectively. This forms the Health Outcome Model originally outlined by Nutbeam (2000) and forms the basis for numerous HL scales and assessments (Chinn and McCarthy, 2013; Abel *et al.*, 2015; Roux *et al.*, 2019). Possessing functional literacy is considered as having proficiencies in basic information/ everyday practices, due to the ability to seek out information and understand it explicitly. Interactive, or communication literacy requires social skills to apply basic knowledge to changing or differing circumstances (i.e. sport) and convey this effectively. This may include engaging with healthcare providers (Roux *et al.*, 2021). Lastly, critical literacy is outlined as the advanced literacy skills to critically analyse and appraise information. Models have since expanded this tri-step approach to reflect the evolution of healthcare, with critical health literacy especially detailed further to consider the cultural literacy (i.e. recognition of beliefs, practices, and behaviours), and civic literacy (knowledge of social processes and cohesion) influences (Zarcadoolas, Pleasant and Greer, 2005). The majority of evidence assessing HL focuses on the interactive and critical HL markers (Guzys *et al.*, 2015), with a critical review of HL assessment highlighting the need for appropriate frameworks for such assessment.

2.7.1 Menstrual Health Literacy Assessment

Whilst experiences of menstruation and subsequent impacts upon daily health and wellbeing is well documented (Santer, Warner and Wyke, 2005; Santer, Wyke and Warner, 2008; Schoep *et al.*, 2019a), there is a lack of consensus regarding functional MHH literacy levels in women and girls due to the inconsistencies within measurement of outcomes. Systematic reviews on the topic have consistently highlighted the limited number of studies, and the lack of high-quality validated evidence within the research to date (Sumpter and Torondel, 2013; Phillips-Howard *et al.*, 2016; Hennegan *et al.*, 2020). There is a lack of standardised tools for assessing literacy; however, this is also due to calls to not only focus on biological knowledge, but to consider the broader social, emotional and cultural influences. Therefore, whilst tools such as the Menstrual Health Questionnaire (MHQ) cover the basic biology, it focuses on participants understanding key concepts related to menstrual health and does not reflect participant attitudes or perceptions regarding menstruation. The Menstrual Attitudes Questionnaire (MAQ) is a psychometric tool designed to assess individuals' attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions regarding menstruation. Developed initially by Brooks-Gunn and Ruble (1980), the MAQ has been widely used in research to explore how attitudes toward menstruation vary across different populations, cultural contexts, and age groups. The MAQ were found to be particularly useful in regions where cultural beliefs may be pertinent to limiting visibility on the topic (Bramwell, Biswas and Anderson, 2002) yet there are still criticisms within the potential negative framing of menstruation and the lack of universal language on some topics (Chrisler *et al.*, 1994; Marván & Trujillo, 2009, Marván *et al.*, 2006). A large volume of the research available has been found to focus on low-middle income countries (LMICs), with hygiene practices often the focus of literature. These tools typically include structured, closed-ended questions that ask respondents about their menstrual hygiene behaviours, access to sanitary products, facilities for changing and washing, disposal practices, and experiences with menstrual discomfort or stigma. For example, the Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) Questionnaire developed by UNICEF includes questions about the types of menstrual products used, the frequency of changing these products, and access to water and sanitation facilities (UNICEF, 2019). Therefore, there remains a gap in the literature for a validated MHL questionnaire suitable for universal purposes and targeted to both the education of MHH, but to assess understanding and attitudes within modern day society.

2.7.2 Menstrual Health Literacy of Women and Girls

With poor MHL known to impact health outcomes, understanding the current landscape of MHL within society and sport is crucial to target knowledge gaps with appropriate support. As mentioned, MHL is remarkably influenced by key contextual and environmental factors, with research often focused on LMICs and focused upon MHH. However, literature within high-income countries (HICs) is limited (Holmes *et al.*, 2021). Schools have often been recognised as a vital place to target MHH literacy, yet the inclusion in frameworks is mixed throughout the world dependent on cultures, policies and practical ability to deliver the education (Sommer *et al.*, 2016, 2021). Armour identified reduced academic performances and absenteeism as a result of difficulties related to the MC (Armour *et al.*, 2019a), highlighting the importance of education for a multitude of reasons within an adolescent's development. It has been remarked that girls are underprepared for the onset of puberty and subsequent menses; a scoping review focused on LMICs stated that girls had inadequate knowledge on menstruation, and often their first period was their first exposure to the topic (Coast, Lattof and Strong, 2019). The focus of this research surrounding this topic has focused on LMICs, where the cultural influences dictate the support available; for example, period product availability or access to changing facilities (Kuhlmann, Henry and Wall, 2017). Upon use of the MAQ questionnaire (Brooks-Gunn and Ruble, 1980), a study with Chinese school girls ($n = 1573$, $\text{age} = 13.14 \pm 0.98$) found 77% perceived their knowledge to be 'inadequate' or 'completely inadequate'.

Education on the MC and HC is known to be limited within the UK, both in schools and within the general population due to a multitude of factors. Brown *et al.* (2022a) found that 37% of teachers ($n=789$) in the United Kingdom stated that menstrual health education was not provided in their school, and in instances it was, the content focused on the biology of the MC, with only 14% discussing lived experiences and symptom self-management strategies. Furthermore, there is little guidance for course content, or mentorship on how to lead these discussions, often left to teachers within the school (Brown *et al.*, 2022a). However, it is known that education can have a positive impact upon markers of knowledge within young women. A meta-analysis of 11 studies found all 11 saw significant improvements of menstrual knowledge of adolescents following education, with an average effect size of 3.44 (Evans *et al.*, 2022a). The focuses of education programmes were found to differ in the topics addressed, with critical health

literacy least often addressed (Roux *et al.*, 2021). Critically, the education which is performed is often solely targeted and inclusive of females. This separation leaves men lacking the adequate knowledge to progress from previous stereotypes and taboos. Women have reiterated their own perception of a lack of knowledge of men, often referencing men potentially being more embarrassed in discussion of menstrual experiences, such as leaking, than them (Prince and Annison, 2025). Any knowledge learnt is typically through experiences with partners (Prince and Annison, 2025), or sometimes mothers (Allen, Caestle and Goldberg, 2011), and thus dependent on their menstrual characteristics. A lack of knowledge was found to be potential reason for teasing girls about periods within adolescent boys within a study in Northern Tanzania, where 20% of boys reported they believed periods to be “unnatural” (Benshaul-Tolonen *et al.*, 2020). Whilst the majority (72%) recognised that girls typically get their period every month, 49% answered questions correctly regarding menses length. Total knowledge was not found to be significantly different between boys and girls. Moreover, the boy’s knowledge was not found to be correlated with reported teasing to girls or negative attitudes, but those who reported restrictions on menstruation (i.e. no discussion) were more likely to engage in such behaviours. Moreover, the study reported that 63% of boys had received information within school curricula, which may explain the knowledge scores, yet did not seem to overcome the societal discourse on attitudes towards menstruation. This highlights a key example of how stigmas remain and circle within society, as even upon receiving education regarding the biology, without communication, they potentially do not understand the lived experiences and daily complications women and girls suffer from.

A recent systematic review collated results from MHE interventions to understand the role of education format and content on improving knowledge and MHM skills (Evans *et al.*, 2022b). Education which involved interaction, such as a lecture with proceeding question and answer, had the highest effect sizes upon knowledge improvements, whilst pamphlets or books had the lowest. Qualitative findings also highlighted that interventions which used peer education and group workshop style sessions were as effective as those delivered by medical staff. Importantly, MHE was found to be highly effective in normalising menstruation, increasing confidence, and improvements in understanding management strategies, such as asking for pain relief (Evans *et al.*, 2022b). There are, however, some limitations to these findings, namely the lack of evidence

from HICs (1/24 studies included), and thus potentially not relevant for considering the baseline knowledge, resources, and learning environments upon a global level and considering the context of this thesis.

2.7.3 Athlete Menstrual Health Literacy

Within sport, there is emerging research to measure the MHL of athletes and coaches. Firstly, Larsen and colleagues (Larsen *et al.*, 2020) believed knowledge of the MC and HC to be poor, with 36% of questions answered correctly (n = 189). HC-users were found to possess greater total knowledge as previously reported within the general population (Philipson, Wakefield and Kasparian, 2011) and sport (Anderson *et al.*, 2023), as were those competing in individual sports rather than team sports. Higher education level was also seen to be positively associated to greater knowledge within elite Australian athletes (Larsen *et al.*, 2020). Responses included the recognition of key ovarian hormones (both oestrogen and progesterone correctly identified by 16% of athletes), but also what may be considered more practical questions. For example, 18% of athletes correctly identified what amenorrhoea represented (Larsen *et al.*, 2020). Poor knowledge of menstrual disturbances or issues has previously been found, with work within UK football findings that 28% and 14% of elite and development players, respectively could identify the definition (Anderson *et al.*, 2023). With the known complications amenorrhoea can bring to performance, but also to health and wellbeing, improving athlete knowledge and understanding is critical. Overall, Andersen and colleagues found greater MHL within elite football players compared to development, potentially finding age and thus experiences may aid knowledge. Athletes themselves have frequently reported that comfort in communication improved with age (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Hyde and Zipp, 2023), and therefore may receive informal education from peers, friends, or other sources. Moreover, contextual factors such as culture and geographic location must be considered when assessing MHL. Work from (Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023) performed a questionnaire across two African football tournaments and found that 23% of players knew the average MC duration, compared to 31% of Australian athletes by Larsen *et al.* (2020). However, 54% of players were confident in providing advice to teammates, highlighting the misinformation peers may receive and further hinder MHL within sport. Generally, the idea that education within athletes is poor has been reflected and voiced by athletes themselves, with 26% of Swedish and Norwegian athletes (n = 278) from a variety of sports

perceived their knowledge to be poor or very poor (von Rosen *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, the acquiring MHL does not always support the progression of support; other barriers may still remain to limit the use of the newfound knowledge, such as comfort and communication (Höök *et al.*, 2021).

2.7.4 Coach Menstrual Health Literacy

Coaches inherently play a role in the growth and development of athletes, and often work closely from a young age, thus playing an influential role in the education of young women (Fasting and Pfister, 2000; Kuhlin, Barker-Ruchti and Stewart, 2020; Anderson-Butcher, Bates and Lo, 2024). However, athletes widely report they do not receive adequate support pertaining to their MC within their sporting environment, with common perceptions regarding their coach limiting this support (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Verhoef *et al.*, 2021). Firstly, athletes regularly cite the belief their coach would not have the required knowledge on menstrual health topics to engage in conversation, never mind provide support (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022). Research from von Rosen *et al.* (2022) found that 53% of athletes perceived their coaches' knowledge of female athlete health to be poor or very poor. The same question found that 5% regarded their male coaches' knowledge to be good or very good, compared to 30% with a female coach. Coaches have previously mirrored these claims by admitting they lack the knowledge regarding key topics of female athlete health (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). There is an appetite to do so by coaches already, with work from Clarke and colleagues (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021) performing workshops with male coaches to allow them to vocalise what they would like to know regarding the MC and support to athletes.

MHL of coaches is found to be limited within the literature. Research within the U.S. regularly highlights the limited knowledge of coaches within collegiate, or high school sports, on the female athlete triad. Work from Pantano found that 43% of collegiate (Pantano, 2006), and 14% of high school (Pantano, 2017) coaches could correctly identify three key components of the triad, with neither study finding gender to be significantly influential. Furthermore, amenorrhoea was considered to be a normal consequence of exercise by 24% and 38% of collegiate and high school coaches, respectively. The normalised environment towards menstrual disorders may

culminate in coaches and athletes not identifying the urgency of negative symptoms or bleeding changes, and therefore not prioritise seeking support. Within football, assessment of MHL found coaches with prior education on female health topics scored better in assessed knowledge (Anderson *et al.*, 2023). Total knowledge scores amongst football coaches were found to be 48% on average, with significantly greater correct responses for questions regarding MC (63%) compared to HC (36%). Whilst coaches failed to achieve half of the available correct answers, 89% correctly identified MC duration and 47% correctly answered the timepoint within the MC of ovulation. However, there was little understanding on key concepts related to HC use, such as the consequences of replacing placebo or inactive OCPs with active OCPs (26% correctly guessing that menstruation does not occur), and only 5% accurately reported the correct effectiveness of OCP at preventing pregnancy (Anderson *et al.*, 2023). To the author's knowledge, this is the sole study to date assessing MHL within football. Generally, it can be concluded that coaches require further education to develop their knowledge and subsequent availability to support athletes. Furthermore, there is little research to highlight whether education is effective at improving knowledge of coaches. Clarke and colleagues (Clarke *et al.*, 2024) recently performed 'short-course' education within coaches of mixed sporting involvements (n = 93). This was conducted as an 8-week online course, composed of a 4 week teaching block, focused on key concepts related to female athlete physiology and support, followed by a 4-week self-guided education block focus on improving interactive literacy. Content knowledge was found to significantly improve following the 8-week period although it was not sustained at a 6-month follow-up timepoint. However, perceived knowledge and confidence of coaches increased post-education, and remained above pre-education levels at the follow up check-in. Furthermore, 80% of participants stated they believed the course altered the way they work with female athletes moving forward. Therefore, there are direct positives to supporting coaches improve their knowledge, highlighted by coaches themselves. However, that study failed to include the exact measurements utilised to capture and assess knowledge, creating difficulties in replicating such work in other contexts. Recent research is advocating for transparent and collaborative approaches to developing MHL within sport (McGawley *et al.*, 2023), with athletes at the heart of all research.

2.7.5 Menstrual Health Literacy Assessment In Sport

It has been evidenced throughout this chapter that MHL is low within athletes and their support networks in sport. With the MC a key indicator of female athlete health, the ability to utilise knowledge to translate into support strategies is therefore limited. This may mean key signs of menstrual dysfunction are missed, and crucial help is not accessed. Furthermore, low MHL leads to environments where menstrual health is not discussed and further reinforces the taboos promoting silence and awkwardness. It is important to note, as recognised by McGawley in a recent narrative review, the majority of evidence highlighting MHL in sport has focused on functional MHL, which may not be a true indicator of understanding, engagement and application of knowledge (McGawley *et al.*, 2023). The review outlines the need for greater evidence outlining the impact of the MC upon health and performance markers, and visibility of discussion to improve functional MHL. Furthermore, this would hopefully aid confidence and thus improve communication strategies, thus improving interactive MHL. To do so, education must be comprehensive and promote numerous learning techniques and styles to engage learners. The use of focus groups between athletes and coaches following a period of education was proposed by Höök *et al.* (2021). This then must be evaluated appropriately to understand the true effectiveness of the programme. However, the assessments to improve interactive and critical HL are not well understood, again due to the lack of validation of MHL questionnaires within sport.

2.8 Menstrual Health Support

2.8.1 Menstrual Health Support to Women and Girls

The topic of menstruation remains discrete within wider society due to the culture of silence and embarrassment. Current efforts to support menstrual health within the general population are increasingly focused upon structural changes to promote greater visibility on menstrual health topics, but also on greater education and access to medical support. There has been growing recognition of menstrual health as a crucial aspect of public health, leading to policy initiatives highlighting the need for greater funding and support to improving. This is due to recent reports highlighting that within the U.K. women receive poorer healthcare than men, recognised by the government, again due to the smaller representation within clinical trials and potential societal influences discussed (Winchester, 2021). Healthcare providers provide menstrual care, such as HC

and pain management but also for the diagnosis, management and treatment of menstrual disorders, however the severity of such cases is overlooked, with long waiting times and times to diagnosis leaving women dissatisfied with the service they receive (Department of Health and Social Care, 2022). This is also true within adolescents, with 14% of a cohort of 706 Hispanic adolescents visiting a physician, and 50% visiting their school nurse regarding menstrual symptoms, with 77% of the latter finding their visit did not provide any relief (Banikarim, Chacko and Kelder, 2000). A women's health strategy in England has enforced mandatory teaching and assessment on women's health topics for medical students from 2024 (Department of Health and Social Care, 2022). Thus, changes at structural level are aiming to improve support available and accessible to women and girls. The report also included a public survey, with women highlighting support is required within the workplace to allow them to manage their cycle effectively. With impacts also seen on productivity and time loss from work due to menstrual symptom impacts (Schoep *et al.*, 2019a), a call for flexible working arrangements was made (Department of Health and Social Care, 2022). However, there is little evidence to date to highlight how this has affected workplace policies, or initiatives.

Other structural support include that of education, period product availability and facilities, impacted by socio-cultural restrictions discussed within this thesis (Chapters 2.5 - 2.7). A perceived social support from women and girls from family, friends, colleagues, and healthcare professionals has been found to influence an individuals' experiences and perceptions of the impact of their MC. Mothers are often the primary source of information and guidance about menstruation for young girls (Wijesiri and Suresh, 2013; Sommer *et al.*, 2021). Research suggests that positive communication and support from parents can improve menstrual health practices and reduce anxiety related to menstruation. For instance, a study in Nigeria found that girls who received support and information from their mothers were more likely to use sanitary pads and practice good menstrual hygiene (Aniebue, Aniebue and Nwankwo, 2009). Conversely, if mothers hold misconceptions or adhere to restrictive practices due to cultural beliefs, these are likely to be passed on to the next generation (Sommer *et al.*, 2016). Mothers who have accurate knowledge and a positive attitude towards menstruation can empower their daughters with better menstrual health literacy and confidence (Aniebue *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, the emotional support offered was deemed valuable by adolescents (Lee, 2008; Allyn *et al.*, 2020). Mothers who express such

emotional support were considered to help ease feeling of shame and embarrassment around bleeding (Lee and Sasser-Coen, 1996; Lee, 2008). This support is not always available for every girl, and even those with supportive mothers may still express negative attitudes towards their early pubertal years (Lee, 2008; Rubinsky, Gunning and Cooke-Jackson, 2020). Furthermore, the personal support given to women and girls highly depends on contextual factors of their personal circumstances. There is little evidence, however, focusing on the mechanisms of support from family and/or friends. Personal self-help includes use of books, internet and social media to improve their knowledge and thus potential support strategies. Online information was found to be useful for those who deemed it a less embarrassing space to explore the topic, and allowed them to view other experiences and compare their own to understand if their experience was ‘normal’ (Clark and Southerton, 2024). This also allowed young women to fill in the gaps of knowledge they had initially gained from family, friends or school environments, but potentially with a more practical lens towards management. This newfound ‘femtech’ includes mobile applications which often provide suggestions to women around their nutrition, productivity, and describe how they may feel in each menstrual stage, and how they can improve such symptoms. This has been critiqued throughout academia, due to the lack of supporting objective evidence of therapies suggested, and the individual nature of experiences (Elliot-Sale *et al.*, 2020; McNulty *et al.*, 2020; Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the use of technology such as social media may expose women to the negative discourse often highly visible on such platforms, as discussed in Chapter 2.6.2.

2.8.2 Menstrual Health Support to Athletes

With menstruation known to limit sporting participation (Youth Sports Trust, 2018; Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021), feelings of shame and the associated symptoms provide a barrier to women and girls’ staying active. For those who remain in sport and progress, menstruation often remains a confidential topic. Communication is deemed essential for the improvement of MHL, and athlete support (McGawley *et al.*, 2023). Within this context, the “support” often alluded to within the literature can take many forms. This may be the ability to listen and acknowledge the experiences of athletes, to guide them to appropriate resources when signposting or education is required or work closely with the athlete to guide their training around their symptomology (van den Berg and Doyle-Baker, 2025; Brown *et al.*, 2022a). As seen in Figure 2.3, this support can be influenced

by many aspects to be discussed throughout this thesis. Athletes continually report an unwillingness or reluctance to discuss their menstrual health, HC use, or experiences with their coach, however (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Höök *et al.*, 2021, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Laske, Konjer and Meier, 2024; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). For example, 76% of Australian athletes report that they did not discuss menstruation with their coach (Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Structural barriers enforce the notion that discussion is awkward and uncomfortable (Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Moreover, at club or organisational level, support is determined through practical strategies employed, or inter-personal relationships allowing conversation. Often, athletes perceive their coach lacks education, but also their sex impacts the likelihood of discussion (Höök *et al.*, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). Lastly, personal barriers such as limited knowledge have already been noted (Chapter 2.7), however athlete comfort in seeking help is determined through the structural and organisational support they receive, to be outlined below. This chapter will therefore explore these barriers in detail to fully understand the current support to athletes, and what further work is required to ensure athletes have the education, network, and organisational structure to support them in regard to their menstrual health and experiences.

Figure 2.3 Current influences to support for athletes regarding their menstrual health and experiences.

Currently, there remains little work within the literature detailing what “best practice” may look like at an organisational/ club level, due to the individual nature of symptomology and experiences (Julian and Sargent, 2020). The limited support available to athletes may result in them not identifying potential issues with their menstrual health, and then not being able to resolve such issues. Work utilising semi-structured interviews with Canadian athletes constructed three key themes to highlight where athletes’ priorities lie in regard to what they considered important regarding MC support within sport (van den Berg and Doyle-Baker, 2025). Firstly, the understanding of training and performance related factors was critical. This includes the potential use of phase-based training, or potential modifications to training based on cycles or symptoms. Next, the culture within sport was cited as a focus, with communication and having a multi-disciplinary team important to ensuring considered support. Lastly, the focus of health was identified as important, with codes such as body image, overtraining and body autonomy cited as valued points for consideration. The complexity of providing adequate and appropriate support is highlighted, especially when supporting evidence highlights the individual nature of support required (Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Read *et al.*, 2021). These internal and external considerations must be made to ensure athletes feel confident to ask for support initially and then ensure the support itself is relevant and appropriate.

2.8.2.1 Current Support Strategies in Sport

Within sport, clubs and/or organisations are increasingly attempting to improve their efforts to be pro-active in order to improve the support to players in managing their menstrual symptoms. Firstly, MC tracking is an initiative utilised throughout sport, whereby players input their bleeding and symptom characteristics into a mobile application which support staff can access. Within practice, this can be mixed in regard to the effectiveness and usefulness. Firstly, athletes may not be comfortable sharing information pertaining to their menstrual health or experiences (Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). Athlete autonomy and privacy remains a critical ethical consideration outlined by athletes and coaches when planning MC tracking protocols (Carmichael *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, McHaffie and colleagues (2022) interviewed players within the WSL, with players perceiving they were inputting data into tracking apps to share with club staff, with no action happening as a result, and viewed the exercise as not worthwhile. The resultant measures to utilise

the data vary, with football coaches in France saying they may lighten the intensity or load of training dependent on the severity of information inputted, or in some cases excuse players from training, whilst others stated that they would not adapt their practice irrespective of the data they receive (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). However, the practicalities of adapting training are often considered too difficult in team sports, for example in football and rugby where 20-30 players data is received daily (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Verrier, Knight and Brown, 2024). Work from Carmichael and colleagues involved coaches and female athletes performing a series of ratings on statements related to MC tracking feasibility (Carmichael *et al.*, 2024). Amongst the least feasible practices was that of “performance-related variables”. There currently remains no evidence to suggest implementing phase-based training is a helpful practice nor can be performed accurately due to the limited evidence linking MC phase to performance outcomes (McNulty *et al.*, 2020; Meignié *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, with the limited knowledge of the MC of coaches identified (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Anderson *et al.*, 2023), they may not be able to utilise the information correctly or appropriately, and again lessen the want from athletes to share this. Furthermore, concerns have been highlighted over the collection of data and athlete privacy, with potential discrimination, but also in regard to topics such as pregnancy (Casto, 2022). This is a poignant conversation in cultures where reproductive rights are under threat, and the presence of such data may in some cases be incriminating (Casto, 2022; Garamvolgyi, 2022). There are a number of guidelines available on how to utilise MC tracking programmes (Elliot-Sale *et al.*, 2020; Australian Institute of Sport, no date). The individual use includes potentially accounting for abnormal fluctuations in bleeding or cycle patterns, and may support the diagnosis of health conditions whereby the MC is affected, such as RED-S. However, this also relies on suitable multi-disciplinary collaboration by staff to ensure this is within scope of practice and appropriate actions can take place (Carmichael *et al.*, 2024). Tracking applications have an overwhelming positive aspect, that is facilitating conversations to expand on the data inputted and provide a platform to strengthen the visibility of female athlete health within sport (Carmichael *et al.*, 2024; Verrier, Knight and Brown, 2024). This discussion, however, is still subject to various influences constructed by inter-personal and external means.

2.8.2.2 Coach-Athlete Relationship

The communication between coach and athlete is a known factor to determine the support an athlete will receive in regard to their MC (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Nolan, Elliott-Sale and Egan, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). Across sport, the coach-athlete relationship is a fundamental necessity to developing an athlete both personally and professionally and contribute to success, determined via a number of ways. This relationship itself is seen to be multidimensional and nuanced (Jowett and Poczwardowski, 2007; Srinivasa Gopalan *et al.*, 2024), and often explained by the relationship model created by Jowett and Poczwardowski in 2007 (Figure 2.4), which integrated previous visualisations of the relationship. This model is tri-layered, with the foundations alluding to the antecedent variables of the coach and athlete such as the wider socio-cultural context, but also individual and relationship characteristics of coach and athlete (Figure 2.4). The second layer is bookended by communication, known to be critical to establishing and maintaining the relationship within sport. This communication can establish key components of the relationship which will determine its' success. This leads to outcome or consequent variables. The following paragraph will therefore explore the impact of each layer upon a key intrapersonal outcome, which whilst not outlined within the model can be proposed to be feelings of support and satisfaction of support. It can be translated to the support an athlete receives to be the end product of successful communication regarding athlete's experiences of their MC. With the social-

cultural context outlined previously, this will namely focus on key individual and relationship characteristics and components.

Figure
Model of

2.4
the coach-athlete relationship from Jowett and Poczwardowski (2007)

There is limited evidence in how the determined coach-athlete relationship relates to the MC. One study by Gopalan and colleagues performed a systematic review upon existing literature pertaining to athlete perspectives of the MC, and discovered key themes related to the relationship with their coach which created both barriers and facilitators to participation (Srinivasa Gopalan *et al.*, 2024). One key determinant was the characteristics identified of both coach and athlete, with gender and age influential considerations. Coach gender is consistently referenced within the literature as impacting discussion on the MC (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Verhoef *et al.*, 2021; McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Hyde and Zipp, 2023). A study of 140 elite cross-country skiers and biathletes

found that 44% of athletes reported previously discussing their MC with a female coach, as opposed to 22% of those with a male coach (Solli *et al.*, 2020). A similar study with Swedish and Norwegian athletes (n = 1086) found more contrasting results, with athletes reporting discussions with 55% and 4% of female and male coaches, respectively (von Rosen *et al.*, 2022). Gender has been found to impact the likelihood of discussion due to a number of perceptions from athletes. Firstly, the notion that male coaches will have less knowledge on the MC, and thus less likely to help them with their experiences (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Hyde and Zipp, 2023). This is perceived to be due to them not experiencing menstruation themselves and thus cannot relate to the experience shared by athletes (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Hyde and Zipp, 2023). Furthermore, adolescents have shared that they would be uncomfortable discussing the MC with a man, with 11% of schoolgirls surveyed by Plan International UK had been told not to talk about their period in front of their father (Youth Sports Trust, 2018). The gendered barriers are therefore engrained from a young age and may prevent them seeing men as a viable option for support in later life. However, in sport this can be problematic as it is considered that the majority of female athletes have a male coach (von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; FIFA, 2023). Sport, especially football, is often male-dominated, and shaped by patriarchal norms and often disregards female experiences (Schoch and Clark, 2024). This also creates the notion that female coaches are experts on the MC, despite the supporting evidence to suggest this is not the case and coach education, often regardless of gender, is limited (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Verhoef *et al.*, 2021; Anderson *et al.*, 2023; McGawley *et al.*, 2023; Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023). This also places those without a female coach at an immediate disadvantage as they may presume that they are then unable to receive appropriate support. However, there is some emerging evidence, especially by coaches, to suggest the nature of the relationship itself is a greater determinant of open conversation than coach gender (Hyde and Zipp, 2023).

In addition, age is an influential factor impacting the relationship between coach and athlete and thus discussion on personal matters such as MC experiences (Srinivasa Gopalan *et al.*, 2024). Athletes have shared that their comfort in communication has improved as they have matured, and with this are more likely to discuss their MC within a sporting environment (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Hyde and Zipp, 2023). This may be due to a greater perception of knowledge upon

increasing age (von Rosen *et al.*, 2022). Whilst this study provided mean data related to the age of athletes, this was subdivided by elite status and not broken into age categories to understand if adolescents were included within this dataset. Further impacting factors to the coach-athlete relationship are the inter-personal traits, such as closeness or trust (Jowett and Poczwardowski, 2007). This, as already mentioned, could be more critical than coach gender. The closeness between coach and athlete may depend on the period of time they have spent together, also determined by the status of the athlete's career. A lack of trust may result in behaviour changes, and athletes actively trying to hide menstruation so as not to be perceived as weak, or impact team selection (Read *et al.*, 2021; Adam *et al.*, 2022). Coaches too have recognised that this fear from athletes creates a barrier to discussion (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022), even if it may not be the case. This reiterates the need for a safe environment to facilitate open communication, and clear understanding of what support should look like for each athlete (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). This has also been recognised as importantly being pro-active, with the coach and/or support staff initiating conversations not just upon menstruation or severe symptoms, but from early on in their relationship to ensure athletes feel supported in their personal life, not just a reaction to their menstrual state (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). Moreover, the ability to provide reassurance that open conversation is encouraged and acceptable was deemed valuable by adolescent athletes (Taim *et al.*, 2023b), however they wanted this conversation to be in set boundaries to maintain comfort in this communication.

2.8.2.3 Support Strategies from a Coaches' Perspective

Athletes have therefore recognised the relationship they possess with their coach, and indeed the perceived limited knowledge they possess, to be a key barrier to them discussing their menstrual health experiences and further developing this relationship to gain the support they may require, especially in the instances they have menstrual health dysfunctions. To the authors knowledge, nine studies to date have included coaches within studies focusing on perceptions, experiences and support regarding menstrual health (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Marais, Morris-Eyton and Janse van Rensburg, 2022; McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Hyde and Zipp, 2023; Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023; Brown and Knight, 2022), and a further four within the female athlete triad (Pantano, 2006, 2017; Kroshus *et al.*, 2014; Hamer, Desbrow and Irwin, 2023). Three of these studies were performed solely in

football (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023). The support coaches perceive they give to athletes is mixed amongst all studies. From a cohort of 31 swimming coaches, 18 coaches noted being willing to adjust training if their athlete is menstruating, or experiencing menstrual symptoms, whilst 22 stated that their expectations of the athlete would change if they knew she was menstruating or suffering with associated symptoms (Marais, Morris-Eyton and Janse van Rensburg, 2022). Another study within swimming found just over half of the coaches had only discussed the MC with an athlete as they had approached them (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). This study also reported that the potential for coaches to discuss or be proactive was found to be intertwined with poor performance and deemed to be a reactive approach. Work within football also found that coaches felt like, despite knowing players perceived their cycle was influencing their performance, there was little they could do about it (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022). Support techniques also involves referring to female coaches and/or menstrual health apps (Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). Coaches consistently failed to understand how they could support athletes in team sports in regard to managing their load, due to the high volume of players and thus cycles to manage (Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). This highlights the focus on feeling like action needs to be made, whilst players have reported even an acknowledgement may be beneficial to them (Srinivasa Gopalan *et al.*, 2024). Semi-structured interviews of female coaches and sport scientists provided further information to evidence varying types of support (Brown and Knight, 2022). Examples included practical strategies such as adjustments to training, but also emotional support and reassurance, or in providing products to athletes. However, there has been found to be a disconnect within staffing structures as to who's responsibility dealing with athletes truly was, or agreement on how the club should manage such instances (Höök *et al.*, 2021; McHaffie *et al.*, 2022); having a designated staff member to discuss such matters with may show athletes to a clear support route, however, as discussed, this depends on the relationship they have with this person. This approach has been utilised within the WSL, with a designated “menstrual health support” to be designated at every club under new league guidelines (Women's Football Association, 2024). There remains no mandate within youth leagues.

The perceived and assessed limited MHL of coaches has already been discussed within this thesis and discussed as a barrier to athletes approaching them for support, and their ability to

engage in this process. However, Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther (2023) highlighted a number of interpersonal barriers from a coach's perspective which limited the communication and support to athletes. This includes false assumptions made about the athlete, such as they did not think they needed to discuss their MC since they did not approach them, yet the athletes reported that they did not want to bother their coach, or their coach may not understand them. This highlights the awkwardness around approaching discussion, due to the silence of the topic within wider society. Further interpersonal barriers were highlighted from cross-country ski coaches (Höök *et al.*, 2021), with the need to respect athletes' privacy once again referencing the perceived taboo throughout society and infiltrated into sport. Coaches did, however, cite not being sure of how to approach conversations, what would be appropriate or helpful (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). Improving coach confidence in communication, through education, may improve their ability to provide support to athletes. However, with little evidence documenting the methods of coach education, this remains difficult to understand.

Coaches have recognised their MHL is limited, however frequently report wanting to improve their knowledge and understanding to ensure they can support athletes (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Hyde and Zipp, 2023; Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023; Brown and Knight, 2022). However, there fails to be menstrual health education provided within coach education curriculums within swimming (Hyde and Zipp, 2023) and football (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). A study within football cited a lack of support from top-level management, with lack of resources and limited training available to upskill coaches on important aspects regarding female athlete health (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). Swim coaches wanted education of symptoms and side effects specific to the sport, and how this advice could be implemented in training (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). This sport-specific approach was recognised in the work of Clarke and colleagues (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021), who utilised a concept mapping approach with male coaches to identify what they required in regard to further education on the topic. Training management and physical performance were deemed the priority topics for knowledge, due to the practical use they would pose. The largest cluster, however, was that of communication. This included optimal strategies to promote communication and engage athletes in discussion. With the individual preference for communication however, this potentially requires athletes and coaches initially discussing what

support may be appropriate in the realms of what the athletes wants and feels comfortable with. Additionally, some athletes may never feel comfortable discussing this topic with a male staff member, or any staff member we may add, and thus must be considered when designing coach education frameworks (Clarke *et al.*, 2024).

2.9 Contextual Considerations of Thesis

2.9.1 Language Utilised Throughout

Within this thesis, the term ‘female’ and ‘women’ are utilised to describe both sex characteristics and gender, respectively. However, this author recognises the terminology throughout is based on previous work within the field, with the use of gendered words to describe individuals who menstruate. Within sport, this can pose further complexities and often a vessel for division (Roberts, Smalley and Ahrendt, 2021; Heather, 2022). This thesis recognises that gender and sex are not intertwined, and in fact are not binary, however does utilise the terminology regarding ‘women’ or ‘girl’ when indeed referencing persons who menstruate, due to the presence of ovarian hormones. This allows the inclusion of the societal perspectives which often reference historical narratives and shape menstrual stigmas, and experiences upon those who menstruate. However, this study does not account for the further complications and societal impacts upon menstruators who identify as transgender, non-binary or other gender minorities (Babbar *et al.*, 2023). Whilst “progress” in improving visibility of the topic, and thus removing barriers has been discussed within this literature review, this has primarily been researched within cis-gendered contexts. Limited data extends to trans, non-binary or non-conforming genders. Menstruation-induced dysphoria has been found to be exacerbated by a lack of supportive social spaces, safety concerns around bathrooms and a lack of general education, amongst other factors (Martin and Narushima, 2024).

With Chapter 3 of this thesis focusing on collecting player data, no individual identified as something other than “women or “girl” (with such information reported by club player data prior to data collection), and thus this topic was not discussed. The author, however, recognises the need for universal language to improve the landscape of menstrual health, hygiene and support for all those affected.

2.9.2 Researcher Positionality

This PhD was the product of a partnership between the university and applied sporting organisation. Therefore, the lead researcher had a joint role of being an applied practitioner, whilst performing data collection within the same environment. It is important to acknowledge the embedded nature of this role, and the potential implications this held during the collection, analysis and conclusions made throughout this thesis. This position granted a unique opportunity in engaging participants and afforded informal interactions on the work, observational insights, a depth of trust that may not have been achievable otherwise, and a deep understanding of the context at hand. This therefore also brought challenges in maintaining boundaries, remaining critical and avoiding assumptions. Maintaining reflexive practices was important throughout to understand and acknowledge the influence on the research process, and relationships developed as a result (Sveinson *et al.*, 2025). There are a number of processes outlined throughout this thesis to highlight the efforts to ensure rigor and validity of data. Moreover, the nature of the PhD also contributed to the need to collect meaningful, practical results which can be utilised by the club, and therefore guided the nature of studies performed, data collected, and theories utilised.

2.9.3 Theoretical Underpinning of Work

This thesis utilises a number of approaches to collect, analyse and discuss data, dependent on the aims of the study. As referenced throughout, each approach includes extensive consideration of the primary aims of the work, whilst also acknowledging the context in which such aims were conceived. The parameters of the doctoral studentship provided distinct research setting and framework, shaped not only by institutional factors but also by the researchers involvement within the environment. This interplay forms a foundational aspect of the work performed.

This PhD is grounded in social constructivism, recognising that the foundations of the work are actively constructed through the experiences and interactions of those whom this topic concerns (Creswell, 2012; Gergen, 2015; Deznin and Lincoln, 2017). From this perspective, reality is not objective, but rather fluid, shaped by context (Kelly, Dowling and Millar, 2018). This chapter has already discussed the individual nature of menstruation, and whilst menstrual health is rooted in biological process (Chapter 2.2), it is deeply influenced by social attitudes, stigma, and institutional practices (Chapters 2.3 – 2.8). Furthermore, sport, more specifically football

provides a further complexity, as the historical lack of visibility and support for women and girls (Chapter 2.7) provides further context to this topic, which social constructivism allows us to interrogate and understand deeply how experiences are understood and shaped.

Moreover, social constructivism encourages critical reflection of the researcher's role within the process of knowledge production. Importantly, as the author is situated both as a female who menstruates, but also within the football environment, this interaction with the data is a vital consideration. The notion of an 'insider' status often affords a researcher a greater level of access and trust from participants, which, given the potentially sensitive information disclosed, could be viewed positively (Kanuha, 2000; Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). This position is also viewed to incur potential challenges, such as bias or assumptions (Adler and Adler, 1994). However, to ensure the validity of the work was not compromised several considerations were taken to ensure a critical and reflexive gaze was kept throughout this work, detailed within the research chapters (e.g. member checking, reflexive analysis processes, design-thinking models) (Berger, 2015). Therefore, adopting a dialectical approach of sitting in 'the space between' steps away from the dichotomy placed upon researchers. Instead, it invites a 'dwelling space' in accepting that, as a researcher, due to the extensive engagement within academic literature, solely occupying an 'insider' or 'outsider' position may not be possible (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). Acknowledging and critically engaging in the nature of this status was of ethical importance, but also methodologically critical to ensure the PhD was transparent and meaningful. Overall, the aim of the work was to provide useful and practical findings to contribute to the field, due to the recognition that support was much needed.

The strategies behind data collection do differ within this thesis due to the different research questions and thus structures being explored. For example, Chapter 4 focuses on the social structures of coaches within the youth football environment (critical realism), whilst Chapter 5 utilised a more collaborative, meaning-making model to elicit desired integrated discussion (social constructivism). However, when considering the research piece as a whole, and its' intended aims and outcomes, the philosophical perspectives ensure a well-considered and rounded approach to understanding the current landscape of menstrual health and support within Scottish women and girls' football.

With this theoretical underpinning in mind, this thesis adopts a mixed methods design, with both quantitative (Chapters 3 and 6) and qualitative (Chapters 3,4,5 and 6) data collection and analysis methods utilised, including questionnaires and interviews, as examples. This followed a pragmatic approach to consider the aims of the PhD, and the environment in which the work was situated (Kelly, Dowling and Millar, 2018; Kelly and Cordeiro, 2020). The topic of menstrual health and support is multifaceted, and requires consideration from a physiological, psychological, social and organisational standpoint. These influences cannot be measured through a single lens, and thus required the ability to collect broad findings whilst still gaining a deep understanding of the context at hand. The integration of findings across methods aims to provide a richer, holistic account of the topic at hand, allowing research to fit the aims being both academically robust, but also practically meaningful for the audience. When considering the nature of the PhD, having quantitative data was required for the empirical contribution desired by stakeholders, whilst the qualitative approaches provided a novel perspective on the challenges, and wider considerations, especially in a topic where discussion is often limited. Therefore, by adopting a mixed methods approach, this PhD sought to achieve a scholarly contribution to the field, whilst providing practical insights for use within the sport.

2.10 Aims and Objectives of Thesis

This literature review has highlighted a large body of self-reported research within female athletes to show an overwhelming impact of the MC on various aspects of health, wellbeing and performance. However, notable gaps remain within the existing literature regarding youth athletes, and the support athletes receive in regard to their menstrual health and performance impacts. This thesis therefore primarily aimed to understand the current landscape of MC experiences and perceptions within football from both players and coaches, and to develop and assess the effectiveness of targeted menstrual health education (MHE) resources in improving the knowledge and support from football coaches. This was therefore performed through four distinct studies within this thesis presented in Chapters 3 to 6 of this thesis. Initial work explored the current experiences and perceptions from an adolescent perspective and examine how they may differ to those of adults (Chapter 3). Furthermore, there is a lack of support available for women both within

the general population and within sport in regard to their menstrual health. This lack of support may be considered to limit women and girls' ability to share their menstrual experiences or access the necessary resources. Chapter 4 therefore focused on understanding the lived experience of coaches' and communication within a coach-athlete capacity. To date, the reported methods of improving education of football coaches has been overlooked, with few studies reporting this education nor documenting the process of developing appropriate education strategies. Thus, Chapters 5 and 6 firstly documented the process of developing education resources within sport and then assessed the effectiveness of this within football coaches regarding knowledge, perceived knowledge, and comfort in communication. Overall, this thesis strives to contribute to the understanding of menstrual health and support within sport by addressing existing gaps within the literature. Thus, the practical implications of this thesis include contributing to the improved support of female footballers within Scotland and further afield. The titles and aims of each study contributing to this thesis are highlighted below:

Chapter 3; Study 1.

Title: Perceptions and Experiences of the Menstrual Cycle amongst Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players.

Aim: To investigate the adolescent and adult elite football players experiences and perceptions of the MC and the perceived impact on performance, and secondly to understand communication practices and perceived support to adolescent and adult elite players.

Chapter 4; Study 2.

Title: Coaches' Ability to Support Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players Throughout their Menstrual Cycle .

Aims: To investigate youth and elite adult football coaches' awareness and perceptions of the MC relative to football performance; and to explore the lived experience of football coaches and the influence this has on MC knowledge and communication between coach and athlete.

Chapter 5; Study 3.

Title: Utilising a Design-Thinking Approach to Develop a Menstrual Health Literacy Programme for Coaches of Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players.

Aim: To develop a sport-specific menstrual health literacy intervention following a DT approach targeted to coaches of elite and adolescent football players.

Chapter 6; Study 4.

Title: Evaluating the Effectiveness of a Pilot Menstrual Health Education Intervention in Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Coaches.

Aims: To evaluate the effectiveness of a novel pilot performance focused MHE intervention in improving MHL knowledge in football coaches. Secondly, to understand the perceived effectiveness of the MHE from football coaches in regard to their comfort in communication and supportive practices to players.

3. Chapter 3; Study 1

Perceptions and Experiences of the Menstrual Cycle amongst Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players.

A version of this chapter has been published in the following journal article:

Donnelly, J., Valentin, S., White, A., Easton, C., & Forrest (née Whyte), L. J. (2025). Perceptions and Experiences of the amongst Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players. *Science and Medicine in Football* pp1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2025.2476485>

A version of this chapter has been presented at the following conferences:

Donnelly, J., Macrae, E., Valentin, S., White, A., Easton, C., & Forrest (née Whyte), L. J. (2024). Soccer players awareness, experiences and perceptions of the and athletic performance. Poster presentation at: Women in Sport Congress; 6th – 9th March; Sydney, Australia

Donnelly, J., Macrae, E., Valentin, S., White, A., Easton, C., & Forrest (née Whyte), L. J. (2024). Female elite and adolescent soccer players experiences and perceptions of the and athletic performance. Poster presentation at; European Congress of Science and Soccer; 2nd – 5th July; Glasgow, Scotland.

3.1 Introduction

With the rise in visibility, popularity and professionalism of women's football in recent years (FIFA, 2022; Welford, 2015; Williams, 2015), player development pathways (youth teams with direct links/ association to elite first teams to facilitate progression) are crucial to identify, develop and produce senior athletes that can successfully compete domestically and internationally (North *et al.*, 2014). However, only 6% of sport and exercise medicine research is conducted solely on female participants. Thus, much work is required to understand factors affecting female athletes, and more specifically, female football players (Cowley *et al.*, 2021). Although previous research does not show that exercise performance is objectively impacted by menstrual phase (McNulty *et al.*, 2020; Meignié *et al.*, 2021), sportswomen often self-report that MC related symptoms perceptually negatively affect their performance (Martin *et al.*, 2018; Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Solli *et al.*, 2020; Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Heyward *et al.*, 2022; Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.*, 2024; Oester *et al.*, 2024; Armour *et al.*, 2020a; Carmichael *et al.*, 2021b). Thus far, there has been little focus on the landscape of MC health within the adolescent population, especially within football.

In the early post-menarcheal years, MCs can be extended in length, with irregular MCs common due to the immature hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis (Mansfield and Emans, 1984). Up to 97% of adolescents report painful periods (dysmenorrhoea), which, along with other symptoms such as fatigue and headaches, can negatively affect school engagement, performance and attendance (Houston *et al.*, 2006; Steiner *et al.*, 2011). There has been little work, however, to understand the experiences and impact of the MC on adolescent sporting performance (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024; Keil, Adam and Neely, 2024; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Although no football players were included, Taim *et al.* (2023b) highlighted that 43% of naturally menstruating (NM) Singaporean adolescent athletes perceived their performance to be “worse” during their period and led to modified training (20%) or competition (15%). Recent work within Australian youth and senior football players reported 40% perceived training or performance to be disrupted by their MC; 89% found it to be “while menstruating” (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024). Therefore, the MC is known to sometimes cause complications within daily life and sport for adolescents, but this requires further understanding within a football context.

The perpetual notion that the MC is a “taboo topic” means that athletes and coaches may not be comfortable communicating about menstrual-related topics (Larsen *et al.*, 2020; Höök *et al.*, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Anderson *et al.*, 2023; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Whilst most studies in this area have been conducted in adults or senior athletes, Taim and colleagues reported 17% of youth athletes had spoken to their coach regarding their MC, citing gender and awkwardness, amongst other factors as barriers to communication (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). However, positive changes to the culture and discussion were noted by seven adolescent athletes from a variety of sports, with changes to clothing requirements and menstrual product policies noted as allowing the topic of menstruation to be more normalised, yet support from coaches still felt limited (Keil, Adam and Neely, 2024). Thus, there remains a lack of understanding of communication practices and available support to adolescent football players. Through understanding adolescent players’ experiences within the unique environment of football, we will be able to provide football-specific support systems for adolescents. Therefore, the aims of this study are:

1. To investigate the adolescent and adult elite football players’ experiences and perceptions of the MC and the perceived impact on performance.
2. To understand communication practices and perceived support to adolescent and adult elite players.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Participant Information

Adult elite and adolescent female football players were recruited through purposive and convenience sampling from clubs in the Scottish Women’s Premier League and English Championship. This included the associated youth academies, ranging from Under 14s teams to First Team level. A minimum reading age of 13 years was established to take part in this study due to the mandated scientific understanding required for questioning and response depth as defined by the National Centre for Education Statistics (NAEP, 2017), whilst also the starting age for National Performance pathways from the National Governing Body.

Following ethical approval by the School of Health and Life Science Ethics Committee (2021-17219-14436) at the University of the West of Scotland, written informed consent was attained from participants. For those under the age of 16, consent from parents/ legal guardians was given.

3.2.2 Data Collection

Participants completed an online questionnaire through QuestionPro (Appendix A), which was adapted from Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.* (2024). Questions were provided within three sections: 1) MC characteristics, including historical and current MC status, 2) MC symptom frequency and severity, 3) symptom management strategies, and impact on training and/or football games and 4) communication and support available to them, including how they may access information (if relevant). Participants who had not yet reached menarche completed section 1 and were then directed to section 5) pre-menarcheal perceptions of the MC, and its positive/negative impact on lifestyle, health, and performance. Question formatting included both quantitative (e.g., Likert-scale style questions and singular/ multiple choice) and open-text qualitative questions. Due to the perceived sensitive nature of the topic, some questions signposted to relevant services e.g., General Practitioner if the participant is over 16 years old and experiencing amenorrhoea.

Pilot data was collected from 12 participants and the feedback prompted minor amendments in question wording to improve clarity. For the main study, a total of 212 responses were recorded, with 116 responses removed due to insufficient completed sections (i.e. incompleteness of MC symptoms, impact and communication). Data from 96 participants were therefore analysed, including 31 elite adult professional (age 24.6 ± 5.1 years) and 65 adolescent (age 15.0 ± 1.1 years) football players (of which 8 were pre-menarcheal). Participants were from three clubs in the SWPL ($n = 87$) and one within the English Championship ($n = 9$). The questionnaire took on average 37 ± 12 min (range = 28 – 61 min) minutes to complete.

3.2.3 Analysis

Data was exported from QuestionPro, and statistical analysis was performed within Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corporation) and Jamovi (version 2.3.21.0). Where appropriate, data checks for normality and homogeneity of variance were performed to check assumptions for analysis were

met. Independent t-tests were utilised for continuous data, with Cohen's d reported to determine effect size. A chi-square test of association analysis was utilised to test for associations between age categories (adults aged 18+ years and adolescents aged 13 - 17 years). Significance was set at $p < 0.05$. When expected counts were less than 5 and, where appropriate to the question, two routes were taken: 1) the category with the lowest counts were merged with the nearest category, and the test for association was re-tested until expected counts were met, or 2) descriptive statistics and/or proportion frequencies were used to report data.

Open-text responses were analysed using frequency analysis to accommodate for the short nature of responses, displayed in descending order of frequency/ appearance within text (Mayring, 2015). The question "How do you think your MC impacts your performance?" was analysed via conceptual content analysis (Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020), interpreted implicitly to infer key concepts summarising like-minded codes and to allow for quantification (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005; Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020). For the purpose of reporting qualitative data, quotes within text have been coded with NM = naturally menstruating, PM = pre-menarcheal, AD = adolescent, A = adult (e.g., NMA10 = Naturally menstruating adult, participant 10).

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Personal MC Characteristics

Personal information denoting individual MC characteristics are outlined in Table 3.1. Average cycle lengths were not found to be significantly different, yet bleeding lengths were, on average one day longer in the adolescent cohort compared to the adult cohort.

Table 3.1 Self-reported MC characteristics of adolescent and adult football players.

	<i>Adolescents</i>	<i>Adults</i>	<i>Analysis</i>
Mean (and range) age at menarche (years)	12.7 ± 1.1 (10 - 15)	13.5 ± 1.3 (11 - 16)	t = -3.04, df = 94 p = 0.003, Cohens D = -0.664
Mean (and range) cycle length (days)	30.8 ± 10.8 (12 - 90)	29.3 ± 5.4 (10 - 38)	t = 0.658, df = 80, p = 0.512, Cohens D = 0.156
Mean (and range) bleeding length (days)	5.6 ± 1.3 (3 - 14)	4.8 ± 1.3 (3 - 9)	t = 2.502, df = 92, p = 0.014 Cohens D = 0.554

A total of 32.8% (n = 20) adolescents and 53.5% (n = 15) adults described their bleeding as ‘Heavy’ or ‘Very Heavy’. Self-reported secondary amenorrhoea was historically or currently experienced by 16.9% (n = 11) and 16.1% (n = 5) of NM adolescents and adults, respectively (Table 3.2). Of those currently experiencing amenorrhoea, 66.7% (n = 4) of adults perceived that they ‘knew’ the reasons for this, with all participants citing elements included within the RED-S criteria (Mountjoy *et al.*, 2023) such as “*Stress, weight-loss, change of training*” (NMA18).

Table 3.2 Self-reported menstrual bleeding characteristics of adolescent and adult football players

	Adolescents (%)	Adults (%)	Analysis
<i>Does the time between one period and your next period change each time?</i>			
Yes	30.8	22.6	$\chi^2 = 1.640$, df = 2, p = 0.44, n = 96
Somewhat	58.5	58.1	
No	10.8	19.4	
<i>Have you ever experienced missing a period for a duration of 90 days in a row or more?</i>			
Yes	16.9	16.1	$\chi^2 = 0.009$, df = 1, p = 0.922, n = 96
No	83.1	83.9	
<i>Of those who selected 'Yes'; Are you currently experiencing amenorrhoea?</i>			
Yes	18.2	40.0	$\chi^2 = 0.873$, df = 1, p = 0.350, n = 16
No	81.8	60.0	

Figure 3.1 Symptom frequency for NM A) adolescent and B) adult football players

3.3.2 Symptom Frequency and Severity

Figure 3.1 shows the frequency of MC symptoms in both adolescents and adults. Of all NM participants, 90.1% (86.9%; n = 53 adolescents and 93.3%; n = 28 adults) reported experiencing symptoms related to their MC. No significant association was found between NM age categories and overall symptom prevalence ($\chi^2 = 1.32$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.518$, $n = 91$).

The most frequent symptoms experienced on a monthly basis by adolescents were abdominal pain/cramps, tiredness or fatigue and feeling irritable or angry (Figure 3.1, Appendix B). When considering symptom severity, abdominal pain/cramps (37.0%; n = 17), tiredness/fatigue (37.0%; n = 17) and feeling irritable/angry (28.3%; n = 13) were seen as ‘Severe’ or ‘Very Severe’ (Figure 3.2, Appendix C). One participant added ‘*muscle aches*’ to additional symptoms experienced. The most frequently experienced symptoms by adults (i.e. experienced every month) were abdominal pain/cramps, tiredness or fatigue and bloating (Figure 3.1). Moreover, abdominal pain/cramps (57.1%; n = 16), feeling sad or teary (35.7%; n = 10), and breast tenderness (25.0%; n = 7) were ranked most commonly as ‘Severe’ or ‘Very Severe’ (Figure 3.2, Appendix C). One participant selected ‘Other’ to add additional symptoms experienced, citing “*uterine pain*”.

Figure 3.2 Symptom severity for NM A) adolescent and B) adult football players

3.3.3 Symptom Management and Perceived Impact of the MC

Both adolescents (51.8%, n = 26) and adults (58.6%, n = 17) tracked their MC symptoms either ‘always’ or ‘sometimes’. ($\chi^2 = 0.446$, df = 2, p = 0.800, n = 83). Both NM adolescents and adults reported managing their MC symptoms with medication (60.9% and 77.7%; $\chi^2 = 2.56$, df = 2, p = 0.278, n = 73) and non-medication (87.0% and 92.9%; $\chi^2 = 0.639$, df = 2, p = 0.726, n = 73), and these were not significantly associated by age category. Content analysis highlighted that ibuprofen (34.8%, n = 16 adolescents; 40.7%, n = 11 adults) and paracetamol (41.3%, n = 19 adolescents; 40.7%, n = 11 adults) were the most popular medicative means. Hot water bottle use was the preferred non-medication symptom management method amongst both cohorts (69.6%, n = 32 adolescents; 77.8%, n = 21 adults) (Appendix D).

Eighty five percent (n = 62) of NM participants (78.3%, n = 36 adolescents and 96.3%, n = 26 adults) believed their MC impacted their performance, therefore a significant association between age category and response was identified ($\chi^2 = 4.32$, df = 1, p = 0.038, n = 73). Content analysis identified three key concepts from open-text responses to highlight reasons for this impact; “*Physical symptoms*”, “*Psychological symptoms*” and “*Reduced Energy*” were all found to be influential to football performance by adolescents and adults (Appendix E). Firstly, players referenced the physical repercussions of their MC as directly influencing their ability to reach the required training or match demands. For example, adults noted they felt they experienced “*Slower reaction times and heavy legs*” (NMA28), or they “*I sometimes feel as though I can’t focus on what I’m trying to (do) in the game, as my cramps/pain is instead on my mind, so (I) can’t perform as well*” (NMA44). Additionally, ‘Energy’ was seen to be a concept identified by players as being impacted by the MC: “*I feel tired more often and a reluctance to move...*” (NMAD60). Both adolescents (20.4%, n = 11) and adults (24.1%, n = 7) report to avoid, reduce, or change their sporting habits during their cycle ($\chi^2 = 1.9$, df = 2, p = 0.387, n = 83).

3.3.4 Support Available and Support Preferences

Table 3.3 Adolescent and adult football players MC-related communication and support.

Question	Adolescents		Adults		Analysis
	N	%	N	%	
Where would you go to find information related to the MC? Please select all that apply:					
Internet	22	42.3	24	80.0	Exp value<5
Books	0	0.0	0	0.0	
Journal Articles	0	0.0	2	6.6	
Social Media	15	28.8	6	20.0	
Health Professional	5	9.6	8	26.7	
Friends and Family	42	80.8	14	46.7	
Period-tracking Apps	18	34.6	13	43.3	
Other	0	0.0	0	0.0	
Have you spoken to a fellow player regarding your MC?					
Yes	19	36.5	24	82.8	$\chi^2 = 16.000$, df = 1, p <0.001, n = 81
No	33	63.5	5	17.2	
Have you spoken to a doctor or health professional regarding your MC?					
Yes	4	7.7	12	41.4	$\chi^2 = 14.300$, df = 2, p = <0.001, n = 81
No	45	86.5	17	58.6	
I do not experience symptoms	3	5.8	0	0.0	
Have you ever experienced situations in which you found it challenging to communicate or were not able to communicate to others that you were menstruating?					
Yes	9	17.3	0	0.0	$\chi^2 = 7.840$, df = 2, p = 0.020, n = 81
Sometimes	14	26.9	5	17.2	
No	29	54.7	24	82.8	
Do you believe the gender of your coach influences comfort in communication?					
Yes	33	63.5	10	34.5	$\chi^2 = 6.390$, df = 2, p = 0.041, n = 81
Somewhat	10	19.2	11	37.9	
No	9	17.3	8	27.6	

<i>How happy are you with the current resources, help or support available to you in regard to your MC?</i>					
<i>Extremely happy and satisfied</i>	2	3.8	3	10.3	
<i>Very happy and satisfied</i>	7	13.5	7	24.1	
<i>Somewhat happy and satisfied</i>	21	40.4	9	31.0	
<i>Neither happy nor unhappy</i>	20	38.5	8	27.6	Exp values <5
<i>Somewhat unhappy and unsatisfied</i>	1	1.9	2	6.9	
<i>Very unhappy and unsatisfied</i>	1	1.9	0	0.0	
<i>Extremely unhappy and unsatisfied</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0	

Communication related to their MC differed between the age categories of NM participants (Table 3.3). There was a significant association between age and communicating with fellow players and health professionals (Table 3.3). Adolescents would typically approach friends and family (67.2%, n = 41) or fellow players (23.0%, n = 14) to discuss any MC-related issues, and 16.4% (n = 10) answered “No-one”, whilst adults highlighted fellow players (56.7%, n = 17), sports doctors (53.3%, n = 16) and friends and family (50.0%, n = 15) (Appendix F).

Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between age and experiencing difficulties in communicating regarding the MC (Table 3.3). The influence of gender of the coach was also found to be significantly associated by age category (Table 3.3). Frequency analysis identified a perceived lack of knowledge or ability to relate from their coaches were key responses from adolescents and adults (Appendix G). Adults commonly recognised key traits of a coach to be of greater importance than gender: *“I think it [gender] could be a factor, but I think [it] mainly would depend on how approachable I feel they are as a person and how comfortable I would be speaking to them about any issue.”* (NMA10). No positive aspects of having a male coach were identified upon responses from adolescents, with players citing male coaches being less likely to understand or do not have enough knowledge to engage in discussions *“As a male may feel awkward because they are less knowledgeable”* (NMAD20). Participants’ also cited awkwardness as a key determinant related to the gender of coach impacting discussion:

“If the coach is a man who can take the issue without embarrassment, then I would feel as comfortable as speaking to them as to a woman who I would assume is more comfortable talking about the issue.” (NMA10).

3.3.5 Pre-menarcheal Perceptions

Eight pre-menarcheal participants were also captured within the dataset. Almost 90% (n = 7) of respondents perceived there would be negative aspects to having a period. Answers often referenced the symptoms involved, or inconvenience of bleeding. One participant stated, *“I never hear anything positive about having [periods]”* (PM06). When asked if they perceived the MC would help sporting performance, 87.50% (n = 7) disagreed. One referenced the positives of maturing on their physical performance; *“Body develops a bit more”* (PM01). Reasons for disagreeing included the potential to be distracted due to menstrual products, or pain (n = 5): *“I think I will feel uncomfortable and if I’m sore it might have a negative effect on my performance”* (PM07).

3.4 Discussion

This study investigated adolescent and adult female football players’ experiences and perceptions of their own MC and communication practices. This research adds to the limited findings currently available to identify experiences and perceptions of the MC in general sport (Taim *et al.*, 2023b) and, more specifically, football (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024), but the first to outline findings against an adult population. Critically, this research also provides a novelty in its exploration of communication practices and support within academy and senior football. While symptom frequency and severity were comparable between adults and adolescents, the adults perceived that their MC had a greater impact on sporting performance than the adolescents. Moreover, communication was largely varied, with adolescents less likely to communicate about their MC within both personal and sporting environments. This research, therefore, demonstrates that there is a clear need to understand MC-related communication barriers within female youth performance environments and develop support mechanisms for athletes, coaches and their support team.

When evaluating MC characteristics between age groups in this study, the adolescent players had significantly longer bleeding duration than the adults, yet no differences were found between cycle lengths. Whilst it has been previously reported that cycle lengths are longer during the early post-menarcheal years, the mean age of adolescents (15.0 ± 1.1 years) meant they were, on average, 2-3 years post-menarche (with menarche occurring at a mean age of 12.7 ± 1.1 years). By this time, 60-80% of MCs are 21-34 days long as per adult typical values (World Health Organisation, 1986; Hickey and Balen, 2003). Nevertheless, 89.3% ($n = 58$) adolescents stated that the timings between their periods change. Irregular cycle lengths can be expected for three years post-menarche (American Academy of Pediatrics *et al.*, 2006; Hillard, 2008), with reported lengths ranging up to 90 days and historical or current secondary amenorrhoea self-reported by 16.9% adolescents. The potential for menstrual disorders (known or unknown) within this population is therefore a worthwhile consideration. Historical or current secondary amenorrhoea was documented by 16.9% and 16.1% of adolescents and adults, respectively, which is within the range (0 – 61.5%) found by Taim *et al.* (2023a) in their systematic review of 24 studies (1705 female athlete participants with secondary amenorrhoea). Amenorrhoea has previously not been well identified, and then recognised as a potential issue by players, parents and coaches of adolescent and adult football players (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022, Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Amenorrhoea within athletes is a key indicator of Relative Energy Deficiency in Sport (RED-S), and outcomes such as reproductive issues, poorer immune health, and greater injury risk can all impact athletes short and long-term health and performance (Mountjoy *et al.*, 2023).

The age category of NM players was not found to influence the overall symptom prevalence. Abdominal pain/cramps prevalence was found to be comparable to, or greater than, research within adult and adolescent athlete populations (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; McNulty *et al.*, 2023; Taim *et al.*, 2023a; Taim *et al.*, 2023b; G. Brown *et al.*, 2024; Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.*, 2024). There was a significant association between age category and the perception of performance being impacted by the MC ($\chi^2 = 4.32$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.038$, $n = 73$), 78.3% adolescents and 96.3% adults). This may be due to adults having had MCs for a longer time, leading to a greater likelihood of being impacted, and a stronger connection between these experiences and sporting outcomes. Additionally, adults may be more likely to discuss and share these perceptions with others. This study also found a higher proportion of athletes reporting MC-related

performance impacts than previously highlighted by previous survey data responses in adults (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2016; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Armour *et al.*, 2020a), and adolescents (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). This may be due to increased awareness from mainstream media, particularly in football, where issues faced by female players have been highlighted (The Athletic, 2020; The Independent, 2023), including the movement to remove white shorts from the game (The Guardian, 2023). Whilst some athletes have perceived positive impacts of their MC on performance outcomes (Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Armour *et al.*, 2020a), content analysis in this study supports the findings that the majority of athletes have a negative perception of the performance implications of ovarian hormonal fluctuations (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Taim *et al.*, 2023b).

Content analysis in this study sheds further light on the reasons why MC-related issues are perceived to impact performance. Physical and psychological symptoms were key factors, and are commonly reported in the literature and by professional athletes (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Players also identified ‘*reduced energy*’ as a key outcome of their MC which consequently impaired their exercise performance. This too was highlighted in the recent work by G. Brown et al. (2024) with 87% senior and youth athletes citing this as disrupting performance. The high-intensity intermittent nature of football relies on repeated sprinting bouts (Scott, Haigh and Lovell, 2020; Mäkinen *et al.*, 2023), and with players perceiving difficulties due to “*tiredness*”, “*fatigue*” and “*taking longer to recover*”, these football-specific demands may pose an added complexity to maintaining optimal match performance. To date, there is limited research which explores the impact of menstrual phase on football-specific performance. While Julian et al. (2017) highlighted that very high-intensity running distances were greater during the luteal phase compared to the follicular phase in elite football players, a greater volume of high-quality evidence is required to support these findings and for a general consensus to be made (McNulty *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, self-reported responses from English Women’s Super League players found that just over half (n = 8/15) perceived increased recovery times and fatigue following performances during menses (Read *et al.*, 2021). The ability to match performance outcomes with athlete perceptions is currently difficult due to the divide in research outcomes, with the inclusion of adolescent athletes yet to be considered within this dynamic.

Adult players were found to be more likely to turn to teammates and medical professionals for support than adolescents. The ability to share experiences and be more comfortable in discussions may provide comfort to those seeking support. In general, adolescents experienced greater difficulties communicating about these topics, noted previously by Hyde and Zipp (2023). Adolescents were also reliant on friends and family to support them with their MC experiences (Table 3.3). Whilst this has been reflected in the general population (Santer, Wyke and Warner, 2008), Findlay and colleagues (2020) found elite rugby players were more likely to communicate with health professionals than non-experts in the field, perhaps due to the in-built support system within some sport organisations which facilitates greater contact time to build relationships, improving comfort in communication. However, PLAN UK noted 27% of girls aged 14 - 21 years had not sought medical help for their MC as they felt too embarrassed (Youth Sports Trust, 2018). This further highlights the often-stigmatised nature of the topic which propagates embarrassment and shame over menstrual bleeding and hinders communication within sporting environments and society (Olson *et al.*, 2022; Youth Sport Trust, 2022). In the present study, adolescent and adult athletes were found to seek support from the internet, social media, and period tracking apps; potentially due to the ease of access and privacy of accessing information. However, gaining advice on health-related matters through these mediums can result in conflicting and, at, times, erroneous information (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Having designated sport-specific resources that are clearly signposted to athletes would ensure they receive the correct information in a digestible format tailored to age and stage of development. With 28.8% of adolescent athletes utilising social media to receive information, ensuring these resources fit the medium they may be accessed is also crucial. McGawley *et al.* (2023) suggest these resources should be “functional, interactive and critical”, ensuring the information is not only reliable and practical, but engaging and relevant to the individual and their experiences.

Athletes perceived a lack of support was available to them to support their MC experiences, with the gender of the coach seen as a limitation to communication, which mirrors previous research in rugby (Findlay *et al.*, 2020), swimming (Hyde and Zipp, 2023), football (Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023), and cross-country skiing (Höök *et al.*, 2021). The current study found that adolescents and adults considered that their coach’s knowledge of the MC was lacking and

considered them to offer limited support for related issues. Qualitative responses from adolescents did not cite any positive aspects of having a male coach regarding communication on the topic, and a significant relationship was found between age and the perception of the gender of coach impacting comfort in communication. There may be several reasons behind this; the full-time nature of the adult elite athletes mean they spent considerably more time with their coach than younger players and therefore may be more willing to share personal details due to the increased time spent developing their coach-athlete relationship. In addition, adolescents in recent work in this field identified gender to be a constraint, but also the relationship itself with the coach, with key aspects such as trust and closeness being critical to discussing sensitive topics (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Overall, the lack of comfort in discussion from adolescents was found to be evident, with 16.4% stating they would usually speak to ‘No-one’ regarding their MC, highlighting communication barriers are still very much in place which may prevent them from receiving support within daily life or sport. While coaches from various sports (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023), including football (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)) have previously acknowledged that they have inadequate understanding of the MC, they are generally willing to learn in order to improve the openness of discussion. Improving education throughout the sporting environment is crucial to ensure players, coaches and support staff receive sport-specific support they require, but also do so in a comfortable and safe space (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). In doing so, it should help develop a culture of open discussion where defined support processes are established.

3.5 Limitations and Future Work

There are several limitations to this research. The population utilised limits the ability to transfer findings to other sports, countries or environments. This study used a self-reported questionnaire which means recall bias may influence results (Althubaiti, 2016). For example, the adult population may have greater difficulty recalling age of menarche. Furthermore, frequency and severity of symptoms is subjective and menstrual dysfunctions such as amenorrhoea were not confirmed with medical diagnoses.

Future studies should consider the efficacy and designing of menstrual health education across the football sporting pathway. McGawley *et al.* (2023) highlight the need to assess these education interventions for effectiveness to ensure “knowledge” is improving and resources are suitable. Whilst schools also have a vital role in aiding discussion and targeting improved knowledge for adolescents, pupils have reported education is currently limited in the U.K. (N. Brown *et al.*, 2024a) and teachers do not always have the knowledge or confidence to deliver the content (Brown *et al.*, 2022a). Thus, ensuring there are sport-specific fit-for-purpose educational resources is key to equip female football players with the appropriate knowledge and ability to communicate and advocate for themselves and others.

3.6 Conclusions

This study has shown that both adolescent and adult football players often perceive sporting performance to be impacted by their MC, with athlete’s experiencing difficulties in communicating these experiences from an early age and thus limiting the access to support they may require. This highlights the need to consider targeted sports and age-specific education and support to ensure athletes not only have the tools to manage any MC-related issues but are also in a comfortable environment where open conversations about these topics are normalised, or access routes to support services are well-recognised.

4. Chapter 4; Study 2

Coaches' Ability to Support Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players Throughout their Menstrual Cycle.

A version of this chapter has been published in the following journal article:

Donnelly, J., Macrae, E., Valentin, S., White, A., Easton, C., & Forrest (née Whyte), L. J. (2024). Coaches' ability to support elite and adolescent soccer players throughout their menstrual cycle. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 19(5), 1905-1915. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17479541241255280>

A version of this chapter has been presented at the following conferences:

Donnelly, J., Macrae, E., Valentin, S., White, A., Easton, C., & **Forrest (née Whyte), L. J.** (2023). Coaches' ability to support elite and adolescent soccer players throughout their menstrual cycle . Poster presented at: Women in Sport and Exercise Academic Network; 21st – 23rd June; Liverpool, England.

Donnelly, J., Macrae, E., Valentin, S., White, A., Easton, C., & **Forrest (née Whyte), L. J.** (2023). Supporting coaches to support players. Oral presentation at; European – Women in Sport (eWINS); 11th December; Staffordshire, England.

4.1 Introduction

The rise in professionalism and popularity of women's football in the past decade has contributed to improved commercial revenue, investment, and surrounding infrastructure (FIFA, 2022). Whilst commitment to supporting the women's game is progressing, there remains a significant under-representation of females within sport and exercise research which is contributing to a lack of understanding of the female-specific factors underpinning health and performance (Costello, Bieuzen and Bleakley, 2014; Cowley *et al.*, 2021, 2023). The underlying cause of this under-representation is multi-factorial. Contextual factors such as lower female participation at all levels of female football (FIFA, 2023) may play a role in conducting research in this area (Cowley *et al.*, 2021, 2023). In addition, hormonal variation across the menstrual cycle (MC) has been deemed to result in methodological challenges due to the within- and-between-player variability (Emmonds, Heyward and Jones, 2019; Cowley *et al.*, 2021). The MC is a key consideration, with hormonal fluctuations potentially impacting various bio-psycho-social processes (Dawson and Reilly, 2009; Carmichael *et al.*, 2021a). While the objective performance data aiming to assess the impacts of the MC remains inconsistent (McNulty *et al.*, 2020), the perceived impact is widely recognised amongst athletes and in the associated literature (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; McNulty *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; Read *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Within the female athletic population, 74-100% report MC related symptoms and despite acknowledgement of some positive experiences across the MC (Armour *et al.*, 2020a) the common experiences tend to be negative. Athletes report an average of 11 symptoms, including stomach pain, migraines, vomiting and lethargy, with the total number of symptoms associated with an increased risk of outcomes such as missing training or competition (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021). Whilst it is difficult to draw firm conclusions between menstrual phase and exercise outcomes (McNulty *et al.*, 2020), more than 50% of women report menstrual symptoms negatively affect their perceived sporting performance (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Within football, players have expressed that menstruation can negatively affect power, fatigue, reaction times, and speed (Read *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, a greater sensitivity to criticism during menstruation, a reduction in mental sharpness, attentional focus and confidence have all been noted by players (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Read *et al.*, 2021; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022). In addition, with

heavy menstrual bleeding (HMB) reported by 3-42% of athletes (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2016; Vannuccini *et al.*, 2020; Taim *et al.*, 2023a), the fear of flooding has been described as a distraction to performance, perpetuated by structural barriers such as kit and lack of appropriate facilities within sporting environments (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021).

Whilst the perceived impact the MC can have on performance is widely recognised by athletes and within the literature, the support provided to manage symptoms and associated outcomes within a sporting environment is less understood. Athletes often report difficulties communicating their MC experiences to their coaches and support staff (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Gender has been cited as an impacting factor with Solli *et al.* (2020) citing that 44% of athletes communicated MC information to a female coach compared with only 22% to a male coach. Although reasons for this may be multi-factorial, female athletes have stated that female coaches can empathise with them due to their own lived-experiences and have more knowledge and understanding (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021). Given only 26% of coaches across all football leagues are women (FIFA, 2022), many players may feel that they cannot share pertinent information that may impact their performance (Smith, 2023). Furthermore, female football players have highlighted sharing MC information to support staff for monitoring purposes, yet never discussing it further, describing collecting the information as “being for the sake of it” (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022). With potentially sensitive information being disclosed, athletes need to feel their voice is heard and actioned where required.

Within football, player pathways are critical to identify talent and develop players to reach the demands of the sport, but whilst research at this elite level is growing, the support and evidence within adolescents remains limited. Physiologically, hormonal variations throughout the pubertal years result in irregular cycles being more common due to the immature hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis (American Academy of Pediatrics *et al.*, 2006; Carlson and Shaw, 2019). Adolescents are also known to report dysmenorrhoea (period pain), HMB and other bleeding disorders (De Sanctis *et al.*, 2015; Zia *et al.*, 2020; Marques, Madeira and Gama, 2022). The MC is known to limit sporting participation in adolescents, with 37% of 12-18 year olds viewing their period as a barrier (Youth Sports Trust, 2018). Earlier work within this thesis, however, found that the age of

the athlete (adolescent vs adult) held no significant relationship to overall symptom prevalence (Chapter 3; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025). However, age was significantly associated to the perceived impact of the MC on sporting performance, yet little understanding of the reasons why this may be the case. Age has been found to limit MC-related communication, with Hyde and Zipp (2023) reporting that adult swimmers increased comfort in communication as they got older. This thesis highlighted the lack of perceived support within sport, with 13.1% of adolescents citing that they would feel comfortable approaching their coach to discuss their MC, compared to 23.3% of adult players (Appendix F; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025). Factors such as gender have been noted by athletes to impact this comfort in communication (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). Despite recent studies exploring coach and practitioner experiences of the MC impacting sporting performance, the focus has been on the elite adult athletic population (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Brown and Knight, 2022). There remains a lack of understanding of current support provided within youth football through a coaches lens.

Therefore, the study aims were:

- 1) To investigate elite adult and adolescent football coaches' awareness and perceptions of the MC relative to football performance.
- 2) To explore the lived experience of football coaches and the influence this has on MC knowledge and communication between coach and athlete.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Participant Information

Thirteen football coaches ($m = 9, f = 4$; age 33 ± 9 years) were recruited through purposive and convenience sampling. All participants were, at a minimum, either undergoing or had previously achieved a UEFA C License coaching qualification. Participants had between 2-16 years in coaching women or girls' football, and all were within one club in the Scottish Women's Premier League, working with Under 12s to First Team (elite senior professional) level (youth team coaches = 10, senior team coaches $n = 3$).

This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Science Ethics Committee, University of the West of Scotland (Approval Code 2022-17220-14803) on 13/01/2022. All participants were provided with information pertaining to the study and informed consent was attained. To protect confidentiality, numbers were used to reference participants throughout the study (e.g. P1 = Participant 1).

4.2.2 Data Collection

Data was collected through semi-structured interviews, either face-to-face or online via Microsoft Teams (Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Corporation). The interview questions were derived from relevant literature (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown and Knight, 2022) and followed four broad categories: 1) participant background, including coaching experience and academic underpinning; 2) awareness and understanding of the MC and hormonal contraception (HC); 3) experiences of the MC and HC from inside and outwith their sporting environment, including communication on these topics; and 4) perceived education requirements. The interview guide (Appendix H) ensured that the fundamental questions relating to the study aims were covered, however the semi-structured nature of the interviews allowed for follow-up questions. Prompting questions were used to explore further thoughts, feelings and experiences based on earlier answers (Rubin and Rubin, 2011; Kallio *et al.*, 2016; DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019). The interviews lasted on average 39 ± 11 (28 - 61) minutes and recorded via Microsoft Teams. Recordings were transcribed verbatim, resulting in 98,588 words for data analysis.

4.2.3 Analysis

This research was methodologically underpinned by a critical realist ontology and an interpretivist epistemology. Critical realism assumes the thought that a real world exists independent of our construction (Edwards, O'Mahoney and Vincent, 2014; Deznin and Lincoln, 2017; Fletcher, 2017). An epistemology of interpretivism, therefore, addresses the subjectivity of the researcher and participants, yet maintaining the aim of producing valid, practical outcomes (Kelly, Dowling and Millar, 2018; Ryan, 2018).

Reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) was performed on interview data (Braun and Clarke, 2019) using NVivo (NVivo 12.7.0; NVivo 12, Qualitative Solutions and Research International, Victoria, Australia). Open coding was inductive and latent. The process of RTA broadly followed the steps of thematic analysis denoted by Braun and Clarke (2006), with slight modifications to allow for the researcher's working method. This was performed as follows: 1) data familiarisation and writing familiarisation notes; 2) data coding; 3) collating like-minded codes under the context of questioning; 4) generating initial themes from coded and collated data; 5) developing and reviewing themes (and revising initial coding where relevant); 6) refining, defining, and naming themes; 7) reflecting on work with a fellow researcher; and 8) writing the report. The reflexive nature of the analytic method allowed for flexibility and iteration in this approach, with RTA allowing the lived experiences of participants to be accounted for, plus understanding of the researcher's role in both the academic field and practical environment (Berger, 2015). This resulted in the researcher applying meaning to the data due to previous research within the field, despite entering the process with no coding framework or pre-conceptions regarding the final themes generated from collected data (Nowell *et al.*, 2017).

4.2.4 Research Quality and Rigour

Two pilot interviews were performed (Turner, 2010), with a researcher and a coach/researcher and feedback attained to ensure no leading questions were asked and that the level of questioning allowed for a detailed and accurate portrayal of the participant's feelings and experiences. In addition, following the interviews with the football coaches, a 'critical friend' (the sixth author) aided the first author to reflect on their analysis throughout the data analysis process by reviewing interview transcripts, examined the categorisation of data and themes, and provided feedback on the wording and categorisation of themes in line with the study aims (Smith and Sparkes, 2006).

4.3 Results and Discussion

Following RTA, 232 meaning units were generated, leading to 10 sub-themes to support 3 key themes: environment and culture, coach-athlete dynamic, and coach support (Table 4.1 and Appendix I).

Table 4.1 Breakdown of key themes following coach interviews, with sub-themes and higher order codes.

Theme	Sub-theme	Higher Order Meaning Units
Environment and Culture (i.e., how is player support influenced?)	Society	Taboo limits visibility
		Historically hidden (“it’s just how it is”)
	Club and/or Sporting Environment	Would feel awkward starting conversation
		Believes players wouldn’t initiate a conversation
Coach-Athlete Dynamic (i.e., how do coaches support players?)	Relationship Affects Support	Gender implications/ Females better in communication
		Time spent with player impacts comfort in communication
		Age of athlete affects communication
	Coach Interpersonal Skills	Coach recognises being trustworthy as important
		Coach values person over performance
	Coach Experience	Coach can recognise player struggling on pitch
		Experience of players participation impacted
		Limited experience in supporting players
	Coach Support (i.e., how do we support coaches?)	Need for Education
Recognises lack of knowledge		
Recognise they may be an integral support structure for players		
Lack of knowledge due to personal experiences		
Willingness to Learn		Coach wants players to start a conversation
		Coach wants to be able to support players
Comfort in Communication		Knowledge affects communication
		Coaches don’t know how to communicate
Education Methods		Education should be practical
		Led by players experiences

4.2.1 Environment and Culture

Participants often referenced the environment and culture, both within and outwith sport, as influencing communication with athletes, their ability to develop their knowledge of the MC, or ability to support players. Broadly, this was divided into two key issues: the taboo nature within wider society limiting the visibility of the topic; and the club environment, where the topic is hidden on an everyday basis.

4.2.1.1 Society

The hidden and stigmatised nature of the MC throughout society was thought to perpetuate embarrassment and shame from participants. One youth coach was able to provide an example of the associated taboo presenting itself in society, with period products being covered with discrete wrappers and being hidden within stores, signifying menstrual concealment and secrecy.

“Growing up (.) I wouldn’t have felt comfortable kinda speaking about periods, or I would look away, I wouldn’t know what to do. [...] I actually worked in a shop that sold products of feminine hygiene, and that section, [...] was located at the very back of the store, like in a corner, so even the taboo of like it’s out the way, it’s hidden, it’s not at the very front of the store [...] maybe it’s not what people in general want to see in a sense of society..” (P1, Male)

The branding and placement of menstrual products has played a significant role in feeding the menstrual stigma and associated taboos. Teenage magazines have been found to promote secrecy, fear and uncertainty through advertisements (Merskin, 1999), and mainstream media traditionally used blue liquid to represent menstrual blood implying that it should not be shown (Merskin, 1999; Røstvik, 2018). One coach alludes to this, expressing that they *“wouldn’t like to know the gory stuff [...] that’s a private thing”* (P2, Male). With a natural process hidden, it perpetuates the idea of menstrual bleeding being dirty and unclean, and still continues to be a very prominent perception in many communities and cultures (Roberts *et al.*, 2002; McHugh, 2020).

The hidden nature of the MC was often suggested, with euphemisms replacing words such as “” or “period”: “*time of the month*” (P1, Male; P6, Male; P12, Male); “*their time*” (P6, Male, P11, Female; P13, Male); or “*all that stuff*” (P7, Male; P8, Male; P10, Male) were all referenced multiple times by both youth and senior coaches, showcasing the hidden nature and the discomfort in discussing the MC. Whilst these comments were stated primarily by male coaches in this study, findings from others have highlighted that females use euphemisms (Newton, 2016a; Moffat and Pickering, 2019). Participants also often referenced the historical nature of the MC-related taboo, with “*the way it’s always been*” (P1, Male), “*just the way it is*” (P6, Male) and that it is “*just a society thing*” (P5, Male) all highlighting coaches reasoning on the limited discussion and a potential unwillingness to change or challenge this. Several participants, however, felt the narrative shifting, with a perception from coaches that discussion has progressed positively. Participants cited this as differing from their own adolescence, and the increased willingness to vocalise topics once deemed inappropriate: “*I think kids in the last maybe 15 years, that generation are so more open, [...] You know, so you can see it changing*” (P1, Male). This has also been seen in society, with the Period Products Act becoming law in Scotland in 2021, requiring free menstrual products in public venues. Therefore, while the stigma and associated taboo are well recognised by coaches as potentially influencing their communication in general, there are signs that this is improving to normalise conversations on the MC.

4.3.1.2 Club and/or Sporting Environment

Another influential aspect of the environment which coaches suggested limited their ability to support players was the structural barrier of the football club, or sporting environment in general, with the taboo surrounding the MC influencing many coaches. Many referenced the obstacle of communicating with players regarding the MC: “*I’d maybe feel a wee bit awkward [...], we’ve obviously had loads of conversations about football, about life, and that but not that specifically [...] if you had that conversation then it maybe just opens up and breaks down that barrier.*” (P4, Male). The perceived awkward nature of menstruation is corroborated in previous work focusing on athletes (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021), and coaches alike (Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Brown and Knight, 2022). Furthermore, “breaking the barrier” was often referenced, with initial conversations thought to normalise future discussion in the hope of improving the club environment. One demonstration of the menstrual

taboos limiting discussion in a sporting context is the belief shared by several youth and senior coaches that the MC is a private matter: “*Some girls might think that’s private or myself would think it’s kinda private for girls. I don’t know. I would be wrong to say it’s not to be talked about, ‘cause it probably has to be talked about, especially in sport*” (P6, Male). Privacy is commonly attributed to the lack of discussion by coaches, with many fearful of encroaching on athletes’ personal lives (Höök *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, whilst acknowledging the progression society is making, there is also recognition that the club environment is still lagging in tackling these challenges. Within sport, menstruation can act as a barrier to participation, with well referenced socio-cultural and personal constraints limiting involvement in physical activities, such as embarrassment or shame over asking for menstrual products (Prince and Annison, 2023). This, coupled with the reinforced idea that bleeding should be hidden, sends a message to young girls to fear leaking, potentially resulting in girls limiting daily activities such as sports participation (Youth Sports Trust, 2018). Mainstream media has greatly improved coverage of women’s sport in recent years, and thus vocalised the challenges athletes face (Womens Sport Trust, 2022). One example is the movement to remove white shorts in sport, cited by athletes as invoking fear of leaking and distracting to performance (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Adam *et al.*, 2022). Coaches within Scottish swimming believe the stigma and associated taboo behind not discussing the MC is “getting better” (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). Ensuring coaches understand the impact the associated taboo due to concealment has on restricting the support available to athletes hopefully encourages future involvement in open discussion.

4.3.2 Coach-Athlete Dynamic

The interactions between coaches and their athletes were seen to impact the coaches’ perceived ability to support players. The coach-athlete relationship, their interpersonal skills and experience were all important to communication, comfort, and overall support (Table 4.1).

4.3.2.1 Relationship Affects Support

Participants often identified that their relationship with players impacted discussion about the MC. These relationships were influenced by several factors, including the gender of the coach, time spent with the athlete, and the age of the athlete.

Gender was seen as a key factor impacting communication, with 11 participants sharing the opinion that players are more likely to disclose information to a female coach. Female coaches were suggested to be able to relate more due to personal experience, with less awkwardness, and greater comfort. One youth coach provided further explanation: *“they’ve experienced that so they can relate and empathise and offer probably a better solution and some support [...]. Like, girls feel a bit more awkward talking to the male staff.”* (P5, Female). Gender as a barrier has been cited in previous research, as rugby players noted comparable feelings and referenced the abundance of male staff in their environment, limiting the communication (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Höök *et al.*, 2021). Previous work within this thesis (Chapter 3; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025) has also found that the age of an athlete (adult vs adolescent) is significantly associated to the perception that the gender of their coach influences their comfort in communication (82.7% adolescents vs 72.4% adults, $p < 0.5$). This study reiterates this idea, with the ability of female coaches to relate seen as advantageous to improving awareness of male colleagues:

“a female member of staff is also going to give you more awareness of the situation as it’s something that I don’t go through [...] I think players could give miscommunication because they don’t want to show what’s wrong from [with] them and it would then affect them, whereas a [female] member of staff is going to give you the information that you need” (P1, Male).

Whilst gender was seen as important, several participants stipulated that it is the relationship with players itself that played a more critical role in communication. Participants mentioned familiarity with the player created a successful working relationship to ensure players felt safe to share information. One youth coach stated: *“I don’t think it’s [gender of coach] had any impact. I understand why it could, ehh, but I think we’ve built that relationship with the girls. And that they can trust us and that we are there for them [...] as a team I think we should be quite proud of that.”* (P10, Male). This was also found when interviewing swimmers, who thought that initially, gender may limit discussion, but familiarity with the coach improved this (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). The familiarity between coach and athlete is thought to be impacted by the time spent together, and the age of athletes, with one coach noting: *“at first team where it would just be said in front of you as a larger group. And maybe that’s just that embarrassment factor isn’t as*

prevalent there because [...] they're adults and they feel a bit more comfortable about the staff that they work with because they see them 4-5 times a week" (P1, Male). This is in agreement with previous literature stating full time athletes are more likely to discuss personal matters due to the relationship they have had time to develop (Foulds *et al.*, 2019). Coaches alluded to the embarrassment experienced by younger athletes due to their lack of understanding of what may be happening to them around menses, or menarche:

"I think the younger ones from [club] they maybe felt a wee bit embarrassed about it. And obviously if it was just new to them. And then by the time they get to [under] sixteens or [under] eighteens [teams], it's just like it's become normal to them and like they don't necessarily feel as if they need to [talk about their MC]." (P13, Male)

Given 14% of schoolgirls feeling that they did not know what was happening when they started bleeding (Youth Sports Trust, 2018), and a lack of MC education with only 63% of teachers in the U.K. reporting that their school delivered MC education (Brown *et al.*, 2022a), adolescent girls don't have the knowledge they need. Moreover, this thesis highlighted a significant relationship of the age of an athlete to perceived difficulties in communicating menstrual experiences (45.3% of adolescents vs 17.2% of adult athletes), highlighting the potential need for additional consideration of athlete age when developing support strategies (Chapter 3; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025). This highlights a key gap in adolescent MC education and support in both school and sporting environments.

4.3.2.2 Coach Interpersonal Skills

Participants found the communication and likelihood of players feeling comfortable relies on interpersonal skills displayed by their coach. Having a mutual trust and respect embodies the closeness at the heart of a successful relationship (Jowett, Kanakoglou and Passmore, 2012). Coaches also identified that maintaining this trust aids future communication, equally as important as initial discussions.

"Let's just say if another member of staff, that could be turned into a joke[...] You know, "Player X is not having a great night, they're on their period", and then that could have a

detrimental effect on that player because they've entrusted me telling me that information. [...] I don't want that could then be misconstrued in a way that puts me in a position where they wouldn't come to me again with anything". (P1, Male)

Whilst referencing the privacy and secrecy often felt around bleeding, a number of youth coaches also suggest that disclosing such personal information is valued and must be protected. Whilst progression of open discussion is key to ensure players feel comfortable and confident in communication, understanding the current limitations and the need for individual support and a safe space is recognised. Previous literature has shown that players similarly value trust in a coach, improving comfort in communication as they feel safe in disclosing personal information (Höök *et al.*, 2021).

Coaches from both youth and senior teams identified their behaviours should be person-centred, as opposed to performance related. Three participants suggested the potential lack of communication on the MC to be due to players perceiving it would impact team selection: *"I think too much the time we are seen, seen as coaches, as the selectors more than anything else. [...] I care more about them as a person as I do as a footballer"* (P10, Male). One participant also reported that the importance of game planning and outcomes does not interfere with this duty of care. It is worthwhile to note, however, that this was from a youth coach, and therefore may not be directly applicable to the elite setting which has higher stakes, financial repercussions, and increased pressure to achieve specific results. Evidence from elite rugby players (Findlay *et al.*, 2020) and swimming (Hyde and Zipp, 2023) shows athletes fear that discussing the MC will impact selection. Even for athletes who scored their closeness with their coach at the highest possible rank, discussing topics related to the MC still "feels private" (Höök *et al.*, 2021). Ensuring players feel supported within performance, but also emotionally, aids comfort in communication.

4.3.2.3 Coach Experience

Participants could often identify menstrual symptoms which could impact player's performance, yet fewer coaches could detail experiences of witnessing these events. For those that could, a variety of descriptors were often used, all of which could affect athletes negatively. Symptoms such as a lack of energy or speed were commonly discussed by both youth and senior coaches,

potentially due to the visual differences' coaches could identify. For example, one senior coach highlighted their experience with a player in their team: "*one of the things I've noticed is a lack of energy or a sudden dramatic [...] fall in the level they are normally comparative with the rest of their team or themselves and that can suddenly just within minutes fall off the end of a cliff, and you know you're not gonna get any more out of the athlete*" (P1, Male). Feeling lethargic, or fatiguing quickly, has been recognised by athletes themselves, with monitoring within Australian football highlighting perceived fatigue to be significantly greater during the luteal phase of the cycle (Carmichael *et al.*, 2021b). However, 87% of elite English football players reported greater fatigue during menstruation, highlighting the individual nature of symptomology experienced and difficulties drawing a universal consensus (Read *et al.*, 2021). Age has also been found to be an impacting factor, as age of the athlete, despite not being significantly associated to symptom prevalence, was significantly impactful upon athlete perception of the MC impacting performance (Chapter 3; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025). It could be theorised that a greater proportion of adult athletes hold this perception, and therefore may be easier to recognise on pitch. Whilst the understanding of how menstrual symptoms impact football was limited within coaches, common consequences of menstruation such as leaking were identified with over half of coaches recalling at least one experience of players bleeding onto light-coloured shorts and consequently leaving the field: "*It actually happened in the [club] game, one of the [club] girls 'cause they were wearing white and she just ran off the pitch, and could be embarrassing for her*" (P4, Male). Recently, some elite teams have removed white shorts to avoid this stressor, but there has yet to be a focus on the youth environment. With the potential for menstrual disorders to be more common within adolescents (Zia and Rajpurkar, 2016; Zia *et al.*, 2020) alongside the unexpected nature of bleeding through the immature ovulatory years, leaking could be a key issue. This requires further exploration from a young person's perspective.

Both senior and youth coaches reported mixed experiences when detailing their current support to players. Whilst the majority (8/13) stated they have never communicated with players on their MC, coaches expressed the value of being approachable to improve the likelihood of communication, and thus support: "*they might not be confident talking to me about it, so just making sure that I am open and create a kind of safe space if they want to come to me about it*" (P5, Female). Therefore, the coach recognised the role they have in ensuring players feel like they

could bring personal information to their coach and believe it would be handled supportively and compassionately. With women more likely to highlight symptoms they are managing within comfortable environments, the coach's ability to create a "safe space" may be pertinent in opening dialogue with athletes (Slade, Haywood and King, 2009).

4.3.3 Coach Support

A lack of open conversation on the MC was recognised to be a contributing factor limiting current support for players. Coaches suggested this could be due to their own limited understanding of the MC itself. Therefore, their support was often experiential rather than evidence-based, with future education cited as necessary for driving future conversation and support. Identifying a need for education for support, having a willingness to learn, and identifying methods for further support on the topic were all seen to be crucial in driving the support available for players.

4.3.3.1 Need for Education

The limited understanding of coaches was identified by questions relating to the biological mechanisms underpinning the cycle. No participant was able to detail hormones involved, and one cited the phases "*luteal and follicular*" (P9, Female). Knowledge barriers have been recognised widely within sporting literature as limiting communication between coach and athletes (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Brown and Knight, 2022). There was also a lack of recognition of key issues relating to the MC, such as secondary amenorrhoea: "*I don't know. There's that. I didn't know that happened*" (P4, Male) and "*No, no idea why that's the case*" (P8, Male). With amenorrhoea potentially resulting in both short- and long-term health complications (Shufelt, Torbati and Dutra, 2017), it is critical coaches understand the severity and vital signs surrounding menstrual health. McHaffie *et al.* (2022) also found parents, coaches and adult players were unaware of the factors leading to secondary amenorrhoea, with the 'convenience' of missing a period regularly commented upon positively, highlighting the potential limited support available.

This lack of understanding of the MC was recognised by both youth and senior coaches themselves, who were aware their knowledge was not sufficient to support players or understand their needs or experiences: "*I don't know enough to be working with women, I definitely don't*

know enough” (P4, Male). This was often reasoned to be due to the lack of formalised education on the topic. Whilst several coaches believed it may have been addressed in school; this was either a considerable time ago or only included females. Gender was thought to play a role, with coaches perceiving males to know less about the MC due to a lack of experience: *“[the embarrassment] partly comes from the fact that boys don’t get taught anything about periods”* (P9, Female). The demographics of the club set-up highlight the issues which may arise if this belief was to be true: *“I don’t know how many guys are coaching in the Academy. [...] There must be about two female coaches or something and the rest are all male. So how many people have an understanding?”* (P11, Male). Having a reliance on female staff and thus not taking ownership of furthering understanding leaves limited MC- related support for players and assumes all female coaches will be able to provide adequate help to players. However, one female coach also felt like they lacked knowledge, partly due to her personal experience with the MC: *“[I] wouldn’t say I would be knowledgeable on it [...] if it was something that did really affect me, I would probably have found out more about it in terms of stages of the cycle and how I was feeling, but generally I’m neither up nor down”* (P3, Female). Therefore, there cannot be a reliance on female coaches to lead conversations with athletes as their own experiences and understanding can vary considerably.

Similarly, male coaches highlighted their personal lives to have influenced their knowledge on the topic: *“my wife [...] every month she was essentially out of action. She was in bed for essentially 24 hours [...] I had never seen anyone who’d been affected in, in that way., [...] And it was just, I was in shock at that [...] like I just didn’t know”*. (P10, Male). Therefore, coaches’ knowledge was influenced by their environment and experiences which varied dependent on personal circumstances. There was also an awareness that the players’ environment may not provide them the support they may need, referencing the need for coaches to have the toolkit to deal with such instances: *“you’re not just there to coach kids, you’re there to learn them and be part of their life. So, if it’s that or anything in life that they needed, they feel comfortable speaking to you or myself or any kind of coach or teachers rather than speak to their mum or their dad, I don’t know.”* (P6, Male). Parents were identified as a contributing role in the support to adolescent athletes in previous research, with youth swim coaches reporting parents need education on the topic, as their lack of understanding could ‘undermine’ athlete education (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). With only 25% of adult female athletes feeling like they had sufficient knowledge on the MC (von

Rosen *et al.*, 2022), it is critical that education not only targets players themselves at an early age, but also their wider support structure.

4.3.3.2 *Willingness to Learn*

Whilst knowledge was cited as a limiting factor to communication, there was evidence to highlight coaches desire to improve this, and thus improve the support available to players: *“I would love for the girls to, to be able to come and say to me and um, you know, “I’ve just been in the toilet and that, I’ve started my period”, [...] and I can deal with it, I can, confidentially, okay, let’s go and deal with it.”* (P11, Male). The sense of achievement surrounding players disclosing information regarding their cycle was often commented upon, highlighting the current difficulties in doing so, and the understanding of the work it takes to foster an environment where players feel comfortable.

For those coaches who want to improve their knowledge on the topic to feel better equipped to support players, there were identified barriers. One coach cited the abundance of contradicting information on the internet, with no clear guidance available to gain an understanding of the impact the MC has on players:

“I had a wee look just to see what the effects are [...] was definitely contradicting ‘cause one was saying that when women were on their period [...] they burned more carbohydrates so they could perform at a higher level. And then there was another one saying that there would be lethargic, and I was like wait. What? What one is it? I was kind of confused”. (P8, Male)

This was echoed in the work of Höök *et al.* (2021) where coaches of adult athletes found the individuality of MC between athletes hard to navigate and implementing research into practice a difficult task. Strategies to improve coach education are becoming more common, with sporting organisations creating guidelines or information hubs for coaches to access (Power to Play, 2021; England Rugby, n.d.; NetballHer, n.d.), however, none have targeted those coaching at youth level, where further barriers have been identified. Having sport and age-specific education would likely be helpful to coaches to understand the experiences athletes may have within football, and the role the academy environment plays.

Both youth and senior coaches reported a willingness to learn more about the MC and be a focal part of the support structure, with one providing an example of when this hasn't been the case: *“the sport scientist came back and said [the player] was just getting really bad cramps and came of the pitch [...] she didn't know how to tell us. And that for me is an issue”*. (P12, Male). Coaches are therefore understanding of the reasons why they need to have better knowledge and utilise this knowledge to create an environment at club-level where players understand they have support available to them. In environments where conversation is limited, it is worthwhile to consider support structures which may help to bridge the gap until coach understanding is sufficient. For example, Findlay *et al.* (2020) highlighted the use of medical or support staff as a point of contact for athletes, as some may find it difficult speaking to their coach. At the youth level, this support mechanism may be more challenging due to limited numbers of staff, however reiterating to players that there is support available from whoever they feel comfortable with may be useful. Regardless of the support mechanisms in place, it is also worthwhile to consider that for some, they may consider it a sensitive subject and never feel comfortable discussing their MC, and this should be treated with equal respect and understanding.

4.3.3.3 Comfort in Communication

Communication has been detailed as important to improve comfort. Work within adult female athletes has shown coaches cited that having more conversations with their athletes to understand their experiences would benefit their knowledge and support (Höök *et al.*, 2021). With youth athletes however, the comfort in doing so may vary. Within interviews, youth coaches seemed unsure of what would be appropriate discussion with younger players: *“they maybe don't know the right thing to say to somebody else's daughter, you know, without thinking, panicking, have I said the right thing? You know, have I overstepped the mark?”* (P11, Female). The confusion around the navigation of discussion was common between coaches, with many stating the potential issues of guiding conversations on a potentially sensitive topic for some. Male coaches have previously identified they would like to know *“When and how should we communicate with athletes”*, emphasising the uncertainty felt around the communication with adult athletes at the elite level about the MC, let alone youth athletes (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021). Providing education resources that include guidelines on methods and content of communication may

improve the confidence of coaches to initiate conversations where required and create an environment where players recognise coaches that are well-informed and can direct them to resources or medical personnel if required. Finally, the manner of which communication occurs with younger athletes may need to be considered with the role of parents and athletes themselves.

4.3.3.4 Education Methods

Finally, coaches were able to provide coach education suggestions, or preferences. All 13 interviewees stated that the sporting National Governing Body should provide more education on the MC within coaching license badges. Understanding how to manage conversations with players was suggested to be a key focus for content. The preference was to ensure practical guidelines relevant to the sporting environment were created, to enhance discussion on the topic, rather than scientific literature where it would be easier to disengage: *“we have a very clear protocol for what happens if someone gets concussion. But we don't have a clear protocol of what happens if someone comes up to you and says, you know, I have an issue with period cramps”* (P10, Male). Nevertheless, whilst having clear protocols would ensure coaches feel well equipped to deal in conversations, the varying circumstances of individual players would continue to challenge the creation of blanket guidance (Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021).

Having the knowledge to work in women and girls sport is critical to ensure optimal support of athletes. Many coaches highlighted the need to have gender-specific coach education focusing on women and girl's health considerations for those most likely to be working in this area: *“I would say a course on it, that would be mandatory [...]. I think it gives everybody the level playing field to be able to make sure that anyone that comes into the Academy to top to bottom is being looked after the best way they can”* (P12, Male). Ensuring player wellbeing as a priority was again referenced, with a number of sporting organisations already covering such information. UK Coaching have created a 'Duty of Care' Learning Hub (UK Coaching, n.d.), with resources targeting basic knowledge on the cycle as visual aids. The method of education delivery was also discussed by coaches. Having a digestible format with quick pointers, and critically, signposting to direct players to further support was a suggestion from coaches to ensure they feel equipped to deal with conversations when they arise. Lastly, having players involved in the

education would allow coaches to see real examples and understand the impacts the MC can have on performance: “*what the players feel, how does it affect them, everything about it. Em, do they like you talking about it? You know, cause that’s the only way we are going to learn about it, is if they tell us*” (P8, Male). There are mixed results from athletes in whether they wish to talk to their coach regarding their MC, or would rather go elsewhere, such as GP or club doctor (Findlay *et al.*, 2020). However, ensuring coaches understand this individuality, and therefore know how to communicate to form an awareness of those individuals who may require targeted support is critical.

4.4 Conclusions

This study provides original evidence on the factors influencing current MC- related support coaches provide to Scottish elite and adolescent football players. Through investigating the awareness, perceptions and experience of the MC within football coaches, several factors must be considered. The environment was perceived to limit knowledge and communication of coaches due to the awkwardness perpetuated within society which was reflected at club level. Several aspects impacting the coach-athlete interactions limited conversations, but factors such as time spent with players and trust aided comfort in communication. Lastly, coaches identified they required more support to enhance their knowledge and in turn communication on the topic. Future education is needed, with a focus on the practical aspects of how players are affected by their cycle, and how they can break the communication barrier.

4.5 Limitations

Limitations for the present study, and the ability to extend findings to a wider population, should be noted. Recruiting coaches from only one club limits the ability to draw conclusions to other clubs, countries, cultures, or sports. Furthermore, having three coaches from the First Team, significantly less than the youth level, impacted the ability to compare findings between cohorts. Future work may consider larger sample sizes to understand these differences (if any). Performing a singular interview with each participant on a topic many view as sensitive may have restricted the volume and depth of information received due to comfort with the researcher, despite the researcher attending multiple training sessions to familiarise with the participants (Kvale and

Brinkmann, 2009). Having hybrid collection resulted in two interviews being performed online, however evidence has suggested online interviews are reliable and valid to capture data required (Kulasegaram *et al.*, 2022).

4.6 Practical Applications

Firstly, improving MC education will allow for a greater awareness of the MC, and in turn greater comfort in communication for both coaches and players. This education should be embedded, and effectiveness evaluated within the formal coach education structure, and is imperative for those working with female football players, including youth teams. In addition, with the understanding that the coach-athlete relationship is key to comfort in communication, coaches need to ensure time is taken to nurture relationships which allow players to feel comfortable discussing personal matters. With the individual nature of the MC, each athlete will experience symptoms and performance implications differently, and therefore understanding each individual is important. This can be done via approaches such as MC tracking. However, coaches and players need to understand that if teams use MC tracking, team selection is not dependent upon or influenced by reporting their MC and related symptoms. Thus it is important clubs consider the purpose of tracking and the resources available to manage resultant outcomes, such as screening for menstrual dysfunctions or irregularities (Okholm Kryger *et al.*, 2022). However, Brown and Knight (2022) reference that due to the surrounding stigma, athletes may not seek support, therefore coaches' must be pro-active and recognise when signposting, and engaging in discussion is relevant. This involves spending time with the athlete and developing a relationship which involves care for their health and wellbeing as a priority. It is also important, when considering individual athlete preferences, that some may never wish to discuss their MC and this needs to be respected by coaches and support staff.

Clubs and support staff should also recognise that environmental factors are worth considering improving overall support. Many coaches in this study had awareness around issues such as light-coloured sports kit and had experienced players leaking during training or competition. Equally, players and athletes often report light coloured training and competition kit to be a distraction during their period due to a fear of leaking (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Adam *et al.*,

2022). Thus, ensuring appropriate facilities and kit within both the elite and academy environment is important. Furthermore, having visual signposting with MC information and support mechanisms (including key referral contacts) would aid in developing a more period positive and supportive environment.

5. Chapter 5; Study 3

Utilising a Design-Thinking Approach to Develop a Menstrual Health Literacy Programme for Coaches of Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Players

5.1 Introduction

Ovulatory menstrual health literacy (MHL) has recently been defined as “*the discipline of applying ovulatory menstrual cycle knowledge and skills to monitor personal health and manage fertility with due cognisance of life stage and/or stressors; and secondly, confident engagement and active involvement with healthcare providers to maintain and/or restore good health*” (Roux, H. J. Chih, *et al.*, 2023). The provision of menstrual health education (MHE) within the UK is not fully understood, with as low as 22% of Scottish secondary schools receiving MHE reported by teachers (Brown *et al.*, 2022a), whilst 90% of young women in England recall receiving education related to menstrual health matters in some capacity (Taylor and Greig, 2024). For those that did receive MHE, many felt this lacked detail (Wigmore-Sykes, Ferris and Singh, 2021) and did not include the practical content to manage menstruation (N. Brown *et al.*, 2024; Taylor and Greig, 2024). Furthermore, gynaecological conditions was the top picked subject for inclusion within a proposed Women’s Health Strategy within the U.K. Government, with only 17% of respondents feeling they had enough access to information on menstrual wellbeing (Department of Health and Social Care, 2022). Moreover, work within adolescent females identified that knowledge of ovulation and menstruation was low (Roux, Chih, *et al.*, 2024). Mothers are consistently highlighted as a trusted source of information (Roux *et al.*, 2024; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)), yet previous work from Roux and colleagues highlighted that mothers themselves recognised a personal lack of knowledge on menstrual health topics (Roux, Burns, *et al.*, 2023). With young females reliant on potentially incorrect or insufficient information or guidance, there is a potential gap in support for them to manage their own menstrual health and experiences. Therefore, the limited menstrual health literacy of women coupled with limited recognition of female-specific support leaves the potential for women and girls to be unable to access appropriate services if needed.

Within sport, menstrual health is an increasingly popular focus, with research highlighting that many athletes perceive their menstrual cycle (MC) to negatively impact their performance, as a result of symptoms experienced (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; McNulty *et al.*, 2023; G. Brown *et al.*, 2024; Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.*, 2024; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). This too has recently been found in adolescent athletes, with 78% of youth football players perceiving their MC to impact their performance (Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). This, coupled with the pain, discomfort, and

difficulties in concealing bleeding contribute to decreased attendance in training, and increased drop-out rates due to discomfort, embarrassment, or a lack of guidance on managing symptoms within a performance environment (Solli *et al.*, 2020; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Adam *et al.*, 2022). Many athletes feel unable to share their menstrual experiences due to concerns their coach may not have the knowledge, or be comfortable in this communication (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). Coaches play a pivotal role in fostering athlete development and wellbeing (Foulds *et al.*, 2019), yet research has highlighted their knowledge on female health topics is limited (Anderson *et al.*, 2023; McGawley *et al.*, 2023). Many have identified this to be due to the ever-present societal and cultural restrictions placing taboos on such conversations, limiting visibility and therefore understanding of the challenges women, and athletes, can face as a result of their MC (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023; Hyde and Zipp, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Many coaches may view menstruation as a “private” matter, with little recognition that it may influence their training performance (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). However, coaches have recognised their knowledge is too limited considering the crucial role they can play in the support of athletes, with many calling for integrated education programmes within sport (Armour *et al.*, 2023, Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)).

With the known lack of evidence linking objective measures of sporting performance to MC phase (McNulty *et al.*, 2020), it is critical to consider lived experiences of athletes whilst creating functional and educational resources to ensure athletes can receive appropriate support when required (McGawley *et al.*, 2023). Research focused on adolescent school-girls in Australia where a multi-phase approach was utilised to develop a MHL intervention programme, including a Delphi panel to allow for a refined questionnaire and intervention plan following consensus (Roux *et al.*, 2019). Focus groups with target audiences (i.e. adolescent girls) ensured the intervention encompassed the issues identified. The sport-specific nature of education, and the focus on ensuring athletes understand the support routes available to them has been highlighted by coaches and academics (McGawley *et al.*, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4); Brown and Knight, 2022), yet fails to be addressed within research. There is, however, emerging evidence of the efficacy of menstrual health education programmes within sport (Clarke *et al.*, 2024; Donnelly

et al., unpublished (Chapter 6)), yet there remains no work documenting the approaches utilised to achieve this outcome.

Participatory design is broadly a collaborative approach to designing products or services to consider the end-stage user, ensuring specificity and consideration of needs and values (Vaughn and Jacquez, 2020). The aim is to encourage diverse perspectives and active engagement to feel invested in the outcome (Thienen *et al.*, 2011). Design thinking (DT) is a methodology under the umbrella of participatory design, focused on creating innovative and carefully considered solutions for often complex challenges (McLaughlin *et al.*, 2019; Hoolohan and Browne, 2020). This process typically engages key stakeholders throughout pre-defined stages to ensure a focused design route and outcome, or end-product, based on feedback. This empathetic, human focused approach has more commonly been used in science and engineering practice (Thienen *et al.*, 2011; Hoolohan and Browne, 2020; Herrick, Yu and Montilus, 2023; van Velzen *et al.*, 2024), however has recently been utilised in medical and health research to consider community needs when behaviour change or health promoting actions are required (McLaughlin *et al.*, 2019; Lake *et al.*, 2022; van Velzen *et al.*, 2024). Whilst there can be many variations utilised, this DT is often defined as a five-stage approach: Empathise, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test, with each stage having a distinct purpose to allow the users' needs to be revisited and remain at the centre of the model (McLaughlin *et al.*, 2019). However, the process has evolved throughout time and over industries to be adaptable to suit the context of the problem identified. For example, recent pedagogy research opted for 'Discover' over Empathise, and 'Mock-Up' instead of Ideate, to suit the activities performed and rapid nature of the design intervention employed (Hatt, Davidson and Carrion-Weiss, 2023).

DT processes typically start with an 'Empathise' stage, whereby the author conducts a needs analysis of the current landscape of the topic, specifically the current problems identified, and ensuring a deep understanding of the end stage users and their needs (Herrick, Yu and Montilus, 2023). Utilising an evidence-based support is critical to prioritise needs within participatory design processes; this means active engagement within the literature and practical environment is crucial (Herrick, Yu and Montillos, 2023). This can also involve engaging with end-stage users, or those within the space who have a deep understanding and can share

experiences to shape the DT process, through means such as workshops, empathy maps, interviews or literature reviews (Pande and Bharathi, 2020; Hatt, Davidson and Carrion-Weiss, 2023; van Velzen *et al.*, 2024). This culmination of information helps to ‘define’ the problem(s) identified, to ensure a focused approach to tackle the issues identified and create actionable measures to reflect upon. This should also ensure the desired outcome and impact of the process is easily identifiable (Pande and Bharathi, 2020). The process to then find solutions to this problem begins in the ‘Ideate’ phase, whereby a process of brainstorming, or drafting ideas allows progress towards the end goal. This stage often engages in collaborative efforts in some capacity, whether through co-creation or other means (Herrick, Yu and Montilus, 2023; van Velzen *et al.*, 2024). This may go through several rounds until an initial ‘prototype’ is reached. This prototype is a tangible outcome of the ideas generated and allow for a sense of understanding around how an end product may work, its adaptations required or to gain a better understanding of the problem statement (Thienen *et al.*, 2011; Pande and Bharathi, 2020). Upon all feedback, refinement, and drafting means, a final ‘Test’ phase may be conducted as a final measure of creating a solution.

Therefore, this study aims to develop a sport-specific menstrual health literacy intervention following a DT approach targeted to coaches of elite and adolescent football players.

5.2 Methods

This study adopted a qualitative approach to data collection and analysis. Full ethical approval was gained prior to the commencement of this study by the School of Health and Life Science Ethics Committee (2023-21204-16874) at the University of the West of Scotland, with written informed consent gained from all participants involved in any capacity. There were three key data collection phases (outlined below). Participants, referred to as ‘stakeholders’ throughout this process, were identified through purposive and snowball sampling (n = 11; male = 4, female = 7, age = 36 ± 9 years) due to their involvement within aspects of the women and girls’ game and. This includes the following: 1 Head of Women and Girls Football, 1 Head of Girls Academy, 1 National Governing Body Coach Educator, 2 Current Football Coaches, 3 Football Players, 1 General Practitioner/ Football Club Doctor, 1 Head of Performance, 1 University Lecturer/ Active

Contributor to the MC Research Field. Participants were randomly assigned identification numbers P1-P11, anonymised throughout the results of the study.

5.2.1 Theoretical Framework

A social constructivist ontology highlights the idea that whilst reality is socially constructed, this is shaped through the interactions and experiences of those involved in the process (Kelly, Dowling and Millar, 2018). Through a pedagogical context, this means the learning aspect is active and contextual through dialogue and shaped by participants (in this context stakeholders) prior knowledge and experiences (Pande and Bharathi, 2020). This is crucial within DT as the author relied on stakeholders utilising their knowledge and experiences to drive key ideation stages. Furthermore, having a pragmatic epistemology allows the focus of the application of this learning to addressing practical challenges and utilising this as a reflective practice (Kelly, Dowling and Millar, 2018; Kelly and Cordeiro, 2020). This approach allowed the author to consider how the learning experiences translated these theoretical stances into practical strategies (Hatt, Davidson and Carrion-Weiss, 2023). This author believes DT itself functions as a pedagogical approach, due to its ability to support and facilitate iterative learning and collaboration, crucial within key steps of the DT process. The alignment of these three elements shares complementary fundamentals to drive a collaborative, practical approach. Within learning environments, common themes of a constructivist teaching approach include the use of informal conversation and true engagement with the learners (Dangel, Guyton and McIntyre, 2004).

5.2.2 Data Collection and Analysis Methodologies

Figure 5.1 Design thinking approach depicting each stage of the authors process, whilst detailing each data collection method. This includes the (1) needs analysis of literature, (2) player interviews, (3) initial stakeholder engagement, (4) design of resources, (5) attain stakeholder feedback, (6) pilot education, and finally (7) user feedback

The DT approach performed in this study followed the process outlined in Figure 5.1. Seven key data collection processes occurred to create an author specific DT framework (Figure 5.1; Table 5.1). This includes both qualitative and quantitative collection and analysis methods, outlined in full in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1 Outline of all stages utilised throughout the design-thinking model, in reference to data collected and analysis performed

Data Collection Method	Data Analysis Method	Design-Thinking Stage
(1) Needs Analysis	n/a	<i>Empathise</i>
(2) Player Interviews	Hybrid Deductive-Inductive Thematic Analysis	
(3) Initial Stakeholder Engagement	Content (Frequency) Analysis	<i>Define</i>
(4) Resource Creation	n/a	<i>Ideate</i>
(5) Stakeholder Feedback	Matrix Analysis	
(6) Pilot Education	Quantitative analysis	<i>Prototype</i>
(7) User Feedback	Content (Frequency) Analysis	<i>Iteration (and Reflection)</i>

The initial ‘Empathise’ stage utilised a needs analysis of the literature (1) and player interviews (2) to identify what the user needs may be. This was then posed to stakeholders (3) to ‘Define’ an actionable problem, with resources then created (4) based on initial analysis and the ‘Ideation’ of findings thus far. These resources were then sent to stakeholders to attain feedback (5) before a pilot education intervention ran (6) to ‘Prototype’ the work performed. This involved a post-education evaluation to attain user feedback (7). This therefore merged the ‘Test’ phase often utilised in engineering and/or design processes (Hatt, Davidson and Carrion-Weiss, 2023; Herrick, Yu and Montilus, 2023) and instead adopted the idea that the education intervention will always remain as a prototype due to the need to constantly re-evaluate content, format and delivery based on the client, emerging evidence, and user feedback. This therefore allows the ‘Iteration’ of information and thus the cyclical approach considered. This process closely followed the visual framework developed by Pande and Bharathi (2020), whereby a mapping of constructivist learning tenets are married into key stages of the process to highlight the interlinked nature of theory and application.

(1) 5.2.2.1 Needs analysis of Literature

The needs analysis involved two separate components to descriptively summarise the needs of the end stage users, in this case football coaches. Firstly, a reflection of the author’s own contribution to the literature, forming the basis of the creation of this study. Next, a general overview of previous work within the field, with a focus on football coaches and/or support staff. That includes

the work performed within this thesis to date (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 3), 2025 (Chapter 4)), with Chapter 2 also informing this section in detail.

(2) 5.2.2.2 *Player Interviews*

Player interviews were conducted as a face-to-face semi-structured group interview, with three participants identified through purposive sampling. Interview questions were derived from relevant literature (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)) and followed two broad categories: personal MC and/or hormonal contraceptive (HC) experiences from inside and outwith their sporting environment, including early memories, current challenges and management strategies, and secondly, their preferences for support, and desire for coach education. The interview guide (Appendix J) ensured fundamental questions were asked, however there was flexibility in follow-up questions due to the semi-structured nature of the data collection (Kallio *et al.*, 2016; DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019). The interview lasted 38 minutes, and was recorded via Microsoft Teams (Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Corporation), and uploaded to a secure university cloud system. The recording was transcribed verbatim, with analysis performed in Microsoft Word (Microsoft Word, Microsoft Corporation), underpinned by the theoretical framework described in Chapter 4. A hybrid approach to thematic analysis was performed within this study (Fereday, 2006). Firstly, a ‘top-down’, deductive analysis was performed, in which the researcher utilised prior knowledge and identified findings throughout the literature (1), and with knowledge of the context required, in a systematic and structured manner. This resulted in two key themes to be identified and mapped the approach: “Considerations for support” and “Preference for support”. This guided groupings of data based on where they best fit, regardless of questions posed. From this point, inductive analysis led the creation of subthemes based on emergent data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This hybrid method was adapted from previous work within coach education (Clarke *et al.*, 2024) and described as a method to demonstrate rigor within qualitative analysis (Fereday, 2006).

(3) 5.2.2.3 *Initial Stakeholder Engagement*

Upon identification of stakeholders, a series of questions were posed to define the problem and the potential considerations to providing a solution (2). Responses were collated and fed back to stakeholders to allow further opportunity to add any additional thoughts at this stage. Stakeholders

were sent open-ended questions relating to the content, format, and delivery of menstrual education via email (Appendix K). Due to the format of responses, conceptual content (frequency) analysis was deployed to summarise responses through grouping into like-minded codes through implicit interpretation, and quantifying numerically, in order of frequency (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005; Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020). This was performed throughout the full complete dataset, irrespective of order of question asked. A total of seven responses were analysed within the dataset, with three participant's information removed following insufficient completion of the survey.

(4) 5.2.2.4 Resource Creation

Education Resources were created within online graphic-design tool Canva (Canva) and downloaded and saved within a university secure cloud system (OneDrive, Microsoft Corporation). Videos from Player interviews (1) were embedded within the resources to provide examples at relevant time points (i.e. younger years experiences). Resources gained initial feedback from LF to ensure content was appropriate to send to stakeholders to gain feedback.

(5) 5.2.2.5 Stakeholder Feedback

Data was collected through two means: either via a structured interview, either face-to-face or online via Microsoft Teams (Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Corporation), following an interview script (Appendix L), or as a written response through e-mail, with the same questions asked electronically. The interview questions were derived by the lead researcher to ensure feedback was relevant and in line with the problem statements defined earlier. Interviews lasted 33 ± 13 minutes and recorded transcribed verbatim and added to the dataset. A total of eight stakeholders took part in this data collection process (interviews = 5, written = 3). The dataset was then summarised into key recommendations under each resource, alongside comments regarding format and design of the resources as a collective. This follows recommendations under branches of participatory design, such as the use of community engagement practices (Joosten *et al.*, 2015), in which a one-time feedback process was outlined similarly to the work performed in this study. After amending resource content and format following stakeholder feedback, a final review from the lead supervisor (LF) was performed prior to the education intervention process to ensure all content was relevant and each learning outcome was attained.

(6) 5.2.2.6 Pilot Education

A series of education workshops were performed with eight coaches within women and girls' football, with pre-post questionnaires utilised to measure knowledge, understanding, comfort in communication and supportive practices. Each session lasted approximately 45 minutes to deliver, including five minutes to account for each discussion prompt included to promote informal learning opportunities. These were delivered in-person, 7 days apart for a period of 4 weeks. One additional catch-up session was available on another day if required. To assess the effectiveness of this intervention, quantitative analysis was utilised in a number of ways, detailed in Chapter 6 of this thesis.

(7) 5.2.2.7 User Feedback

Participants completing the pilot education (Chapter 5.2.2.6) completed a post-intervention feedback questionnaire, comprised of open-text responses to gain an honest evaluation of, regardless of any potential changes in assessed knowledge, their perception of the effectiveness of the education, and considerations in future iterations of the activity. Conceptual content (frequency) analysis was utilised to interpret and thus group responses and quantify numerically, in frequency order (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005; Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020). This was performed throughout the full complete dataset, irrespective of order of question asked. A total of eight responses were analysed within the dataset, with further available on the methodology, participant information and analysis within Chapter 6.2.

5.3 Results

(1) 5.3.1 Needs Analysis

The nature of the author's position within sport and academia ensures they are thoroughly involved in the active engagement of research within the field. Furthermore, the author has already contributed to this area of research through two pieces of work highlighting the current status of menstrual health experiences and support within football (Chapter 3, Chapter 4). This has included the use of a questionnaire to understanding the perception of 96 adolescent and elite athletes regarding the support they receive within sport, and their comfort in communication on their menstrual experiences (Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). Furthermore, this author has previously

interviewed coaches within adolescent and elite football so is acutely aware of current coaches perceptions towards the MC, but also their want for further education and preference of the format of this (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)).

When considering the wider research available to the researcher to understand key problems and/or gaps in regard to MC knowledge, understanding or support to athletes, the literature review within this thesis presents a detailed exploration of key findings to date (Chapter 2). However, some additional considerations can be extrapolated due to their relevance to the education work targeted within this study. Firstly, the content of any potential future education has often been referenced within the literature by both coaches and athletes. This often includes the idea of a ‘sport-specific approach’, due to the notion that involvement within football may influence experiences and perceptions of the MC. This has been highlighted as being crucial for inclusion by coaches themselves (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)) to ensure they have the toolkit to tackle any issues which may arise within a performance environment. Players highlighted the need for a general education covering the basic knowledge regarding the MC and HC, highlighted previously as being limited by players (Solli *et al.*, 2020; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023, 2023) and coaches (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4); Brown and Knight, 2022). However, this is regularly followed with the current limitations within sport being that of limited discussion to share this knowledge due to awkwardness from both coaches and players, potentially due to coach gender, perceived lack of knowledge or societal pressures of menstruation being a topic of secrecy (Kroshus *et al.*, 2014; Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Höök *et al.*, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Finally, the need for education has been recognised as a key driver towards an open, normalised environment within sport, aiding athletes being able to access key resources or share experiences with those who play a role in their development in sport (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; McGawley *et al.*, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4); Brown and Knight, 2022).

(2) 5.3.2 Player Interviews

Following data analysis, a further four sub-themes emerged under the two themes identified deductively, detailed within this section. Under ‘Considerations for Support’, the individual complexities of MC experiences were highlighted as being worthy of consideration when identifying required support practices. Secondly, the sub-theme of ‘Sport Influences Perceptions’ highlights the impact sporting involvement has had on perceptions of knowledge and what is ‘normal’ in regard to MC experiences and characteristics. Next, the second theme identified as ‘Preferences for Support’ allows players voices heard in the search for education content and delivery to target within this study. Two sub-themes were identified, the first being ‘Education...and Consideration’, highlighting the players perception that whilst coach education is a priority to improve support, an ability to convey this in a meaningful way is crucial. Lastly, the notion that the MC is ‘Okay to talk about’ was identified as a crucial point for inclusion to improve the culture around discussion within sport.

5.3.2.1 Theme 1: Considerations for Support

5.3.2.1.1 Sub Theme 1: Individual Complexities

Through detailing both younger experiences of menarche through to current MC characteristics and symptomology, three participants demonstrated varying perceived experiences and impacts to daily life and sporting performance. This ranged from negative, traumatic initial exposure to menstruation; *“And so I was really late [to menarche], and my mom actually took me to after-hours [when first bled]. I don't know why she didn't tell me to check, but because I had a really bad pain, we thought it was appendicitis”* (P8). On the opposite end, one player felt they did not relate to this due to very difference experience: *“Yeah, it didn't affect me one bit. I don't actually have any memories of it, me going to football and dreading going to football, doing PE at school”* (P6). Three players identified current symptoms they perceived to impact them regularly, such as heavy bleeding (P7), cramps (P6, P8), muscular soreness (P8) and sleep disturbances (P8). However, there was not a singular symptom that was identified by all three .

5.3.2.1.2 Sub Theme 2: Sport Influences Perceptions

Involvement within sport was found to influence the perception players had on the impact of their MC, due to the experiences they had in managing bleeding in a performance environment. Players referred to the occurrence of bleeding around match play as an inconvenience; *“I pray I don’t get [my period] on a matchday, especially cause I know I won’t have slept well and how bad my cramps can be in the first few days”* (P8). Furthermore, one player believed their MC was linked to their injury risk, due to previous incidences of injury falling in the pre-menstrual period: *“The week leading up to my period where I’m at my most like, Yeah, I’m susceptible to injury. So, for me, I think it’s just communicating to [medical staff], and then we manage my training load things like that, yeah, yeah, I don’t think I can push myself too much in that week.”* (P6). There was also an awareness that sport could also negatively impact general menstrual health, such as irregular bleeding due to overtraining, a key symptom recognised within Relative Energy Deficiency – Syndrome (or RED-S); *“I would skip a month sometimes for, I’m assuming, because I was so active, I was doing like three sports”* (P8).

5.3.2.2 Theme 2: Preference for Support

5.3.2.2.1 Sub Theme 1: Education... and Consideration

Every player recognised that education was important in them gaining support within a sporting environment in regard to their menstrual health; *“it starts with the general education around it, and kind of an awareness of the different stages, and maybe what that looks like for a female experiencing those emotions or symptoms”* (P6). Therefore, whilst having knowledge of the basic biology of menstrual health topics was deemed important, ensuring coaches understand how this may manifest in players in regard to symptoms experienced, or impacts had upon markers of health and wellbeing, was seen as a key inclusion topic to allow subsequent recognition and support to players. Furthermore, the recognition itself was deemed to be paramount to ensuring players feel safe and comfortable to approach their coach if ever they require support for their menstrual experiences.

“even just an acknowledgement or acknowledgement of, okay, that’s good to know, thank you. Not a reaction, yeah? Because sometimes a negative reaction could be like, hugely detrimental

and not helpful in the slightest... Even if they don't know what to do in that moment, that could do a lot for the kid coming up and just saying "okay"”. (P8)

Therefore, whilst the content of the education is important to make sure it is relevant to the athletes and improving the knowledge of coaches, ensuring coach education also includes how to engage athletes in conversation and create comfort in communication may help in the association of positive experiences relating to discussion.

5.3.2.2.2 Sub Theme 2: *“It's okay to talk about”*

Finally, the importance of creating an environment within the sporting organisation that conversations regarding menstrual health and experiences are welcomed, in the hopes of reducing the stigma and ensuring players receive the support they need, was recognised by players themselves; *“just making it an open thing that is something that we need to speak about, and it's okay to talk about... especially younger kids, just knowing that it's okay to speak about it” (P7)*. Therefore, setting these standards within younger teams was considered as especially important to ensure players grow up within an elite space where all aspects of their health and performance are considered.

(3) 5.3.3 Initial Stakeholder Engagement

Findings following frequency analysis are outlined in Table 5.2. Three key concepts identified throughout the frequency analysis were ‘Aims of Education’, ‘Content of Education’, and lastly ‘Format and Delivery of Education’.

Table 5.2 Findings following conceptual frequency analysis on initial stakeholder engagement regarding a) aims of education, b) content of education and c) format and delivery of the sessions.

a) Aims	Frequency (no.)
<i>Create an open culture and discussion</i>	7
<i>Improve coach knowledge</i>	5
<i>Improve coach communication</i>	3
<i>Improve comfort in coaches</i>	2
<i>Improve knowledge in players</i>	1

b) Content	Frequency (no.)
<i>Support methods/ practical solutions (including support services referral, allowing training load modifications)</i>	5
<i>Explanation of 'normal' MC</i>	4
<i>How to communicate with players</i>	4
<i>MC Management (period products)</i>	3
<i>Performance considerations</i>	3
<i>Injury risk</i>	3
<i>MC issues/ dysfunctions</i>	3
<i>Other physical impacts</i>	2
<i>What has worked in clubs previously/ previous research</i>	2
<i>How to identify players struggling due to MC</i>	2
<i>Psychological impacts</i>	2
<i>Wellbeing considerations</i>	2
<i>General female body</i>	2
<i>Impact of adolescent physiology</i>	2
<i>Understanding of 'best practice'</i>	2
<i>Debunking myths</i>	1
c) Format and Delivery	Frequency (no.)
<i>Clear, basic content</i>	5
<i>In-person</i>	4
<i>Small groups/ workshops</i>	4
<i>Athlete presence/ sharing experiences</i>	4
<i>Inclusion of NGB coach education curriculum</i>	3
<i>Facilitate open discussion</i>	3
<i>Online</i>	3
<i>Visual/ include infographics</i>	2

5.3.3.1 Aims of Education

Firstly, when considering the aims of the education, knowledge was prioritised to be targeted by resources (n = 5). However, participants often reflected on the need to deploy this in a way that ensured coaches were confident in sharing this new-found knowledge; *“The education programme should arm coaches with the appropriate level and amount of knowledge in order for them to better understand issues surrounding female athlete health. Thus, enabling and empowering them to appropriately support and guide athletes whilst optimising performance.”* (P5). Ensuring the players needs are at the heart of the education is crucial, with recognition that this may need a top-

down approach, and working to remove the stigma enforced within society and sport may help firstly improve comfort of coaches, in turn improving trust and allowing players to feel safe in sharing experiences; *“Remove the stigma for male coaches to speak and understand the female body and how to adapt best practice. For female players to become comfortable speaking to male staff about the menstrual cycle and vice versa.”* (P3). Creating an open culture to allow open discussion was cited by every participant within the dataset (n = 7).

5.3.3.2 Content of Education

When considering what content is worthwhile for being included within the education, the topic mentioned most frequently was the consideration of practical solutions within sport (n = 5), more-so than explanation of MC norms (n = 4) or performance impacts (n = 3) (Table 5.2). This was detailed in a number of ways. Firstly, having clear protocols around support practices within sport, and the ability to *“put players needs first, player welfare over team selection. Open door policy, willingness to get to know the player and their personality”* (P3). This often related to an ability to share knowledge or support, due to being comfortable in communication, which was considered could be a taught skill to *“help deal with these situations in sensitive and appropriate manner”* (P2). Content relating to player symptoms and experiences was often referred to in a sports setting; *“Explanation of some of the issues normal menstruation can cause - mood changes, pain, worries about leakage etc. Education about ways performance and injury risk can be affected by menstruation”* (P2). Other topics included having a general education on the female body (n = 2), consideration of the impact of adolescent physiology and how this may differ knowledge regarding the MC (n = 2), and finally, debunking myths regarding menstruation, or MC-related topics (n = 1).

5.3.3.3 Format and Delivery of Education

Ensuring content was presented and delivered in a way to maintain engagement was crucial. One participant stated *“...basic information to enhance discussion and create better cultures. It doesn't need to be long or confusing. It should include short statements and utilise imagery and examples of best practice.”* (P1). The idea of having a general education in a simplified language and format was prioritised by stakeholders (n = 5) (Table 5.2). This was also discussed as being delivered “in person” (n = 4) and in small group sizes (n = 4) to aid learning and engagement. One participant,

however, highlighted the flexible nature which may be required, and would ensure delivery was in-line with National Governing Body (NGB) standards around disseminating coach education.

“Included in all [NGB] and coach education programmes... There can also be additional courses online either E modules, or courses online via zoom, or practical courses at clubs etc. Players experience. Utilising current and former players to explain their challenges and positives they have had” (P3).

Finally, the inclusion of players to share experiences and encourage discussion was cited by stakeholders (n = 4). One participant noted this provided *“interactive learning”* (P5) through real-life examples of where coach support is useful.

Therefore, the amalgamation of work collected within the ‘Empathise’ stage, alongside stakeholder recommendations led the research group to define two ‘problems’ identified thus far:

- *Coaches of women and girls’ football did not have enough knowledge to support players in regard to their menstrual health experiences*
- *Coaches were not comfortable in communication and lacked the sport-specific understanding of support strategies*

(4) 5.3.4 Research Creation

An initial draft of resources was created by the researcher and can be found in Appendix M. Prior to dissemination to stakeholders, a review from LF was performed. Resources are outlined within Table 5.3 to show the intended focus of each education session, alongside intended learning outcomes.

Table 5.3 Education resource outline including lesson focus and learning outcomes.

Session 1: Menstrual Cycle: Basic Biology, Symptomology and Player Experiences	
<p>Focus:</p> <p>At this club we have identified that our players experience impacts to their performance as a result of their MC, and that coach knowledge limits support they receive. This therefore aims to tackle the ‘knowledge’ element to key characteristics regarding MC profiles and experiences to then understand what support may be required.</p>	<p>Learning Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identify the characteristics of a normal MC within adults and adolescents -Understand current club findings based on previous research in regard to player experiences and/or coach knowledge and support -Recognise keyways players may be impacted by their cycle (how symptoms may transpire) -Recognise the current research conclusions on the relationship of the MC to objective markers of performance
Session 2: Irregularities and Dysfunctions	
<p>Focus:</p> <p>There are known MC dysfunctions reported within the club, such as secondary amenorrhoea by 16.9% adolescents. Understanding how potential issues related to menstruation occur, and then how it impacts those that are facing irregularities and/or dysfunctions will allow greater recognition of how to support these athletes.</p>	<p>Learning Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Understand the rates and causes of menstrual irregularities and/or dysfunctions within athletes -Recognise the impact of menstrual irregularities and/or dysfunctions on performance -Identify ways to support those with menstrual irregularities and/ or dysfunctions (i.e. training load modification, communication practices)
Session 3: Management Strategies; and Hormonal Contraception	
<p>Focus:</p> <p>Both medicative and non-medicative methods were utilised by elite and adolescent athletes within the club. Previous coach knowledge regarding HC was found to be limited. Understanding how athletes manage their MC around their training and match play may help club direct support strategies to what is considered useful.</p>	<p>Learning Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Recognise the symptom and/or bleeding management methods utilised by players -Identify the variety of HC methods, and use of HC in athletes
Session 4: Opening Discussion and Player Support	
<p>Focus:</p> <p>The relationship between an athlete and their coach can be crucial to the athlete’s development</p>	<p>Learning Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Create club-specific protocols to flag potential menstrual irregularities (way of working)

<p>and progression within sport. Coaches have also identified they play a crucial role in the support of athletes yet feel awkward or would not know how to engage in communication regarding personal menstrual experiences. Identifying how, as a club, we want to drive support to players drives buy-in from coaches and players to ensure a positive culture around discussion and support.</p>	<p>-Develop communication cues to support athletes in regard to their MC/HC experiences</p>
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Firstly, basic information regarding the MC, including ‘norms’, characteristics and biological principles, was covered in detail alongside relevant research on player experiences of the MC, including symptomology and the impact of this upon daily wellbeing, training and performance. This included highlighting the findings of the thematic analysis following player interviews (2), but also previous work from this author on both elite and adolescent player experiences within football (Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)), and a thorough needs analysis of the literature (1; Chapter 2). Next, as identified by stakeholders (3) education included potential irregularities, issues or dysfunctions that may arise within those who menstruate (or not). This included ensuring time for discussion to establish clear protocols on escalating information if deemed relevant support required for players. Thirdly, education focused on the ‘practical’ aspects of managing a period within daily life and sport, and how this may cause difficulties within training or match play. This included brief discussion around HC use by players, such as the potential reasons for use, different methods of HC and potential impact. Lastly, the education concluded with a session focused on tackling the communication aspect of support to players, including players within the session to promote discussion, and workshop-style activities to create club-specific protocols to guide support.

(5) 5.3.5 Stakeholder Feedback

Following the presentation of draft resources to stakeholders, feedback was collated under the category of each session and outlined within Table 5.4. A final row summarised feedback from each session to ensure clear outcomes for further ideation.

Table 5.4 Matrix of stakeholder feedback following initial draft of education resources

	Session 1	Session 2	Session 3	Session 4	Design and Delivery
Positive Feedback	<p>-Normalised individual experiences.</p> <p>-Concise information put into clear terms (i.e. bleeding put into products as opposed to ‘mls’)</p> <p>-Adolescent differences worthwhile inclusion as not typically covered in education</p>	<p>-Clear link of dysfunctions to impacting football</p> <p>-Clear differentiation between symptoms and dysfunctions</p> <p>-Videos shows players highlighting ‘normalised’ dysfunctions within sport, and why that is problematic</p> <p>-Kept information brief when it could have been overwhelming</p>	<p>-Tracking information informative.</p> <p>-Having visual aids (period products) normalises visibility to improve comfort</p> <p>-Nice reminder of other stresses for adolescent athletes (i.e. school/ social stresses)</p>	<p>-Important to note ‘players might not ever want to share, and that is okay’.</p> <p>-Critical inclusion around referral, coaches do not want to feel overwhelmed.</p> <p>-Inclusion of players in-person helps share adolescent view and allow coaches to practice conversation</p>	<p>-Player videos informative. Having [player] videos in there good- role model.</p> <p>-Good use of recap at the start of each session to ensure recall</p> <p>-Covers every topic sufficiently, do not believe any aspect missed</p> <p>-Content pitched at correct level and flows well.</p>
Feedback Highlighting Potential Changes	<p>-Requires further simplification of MC phases</p> <p>-important to address more myths commonly</p>	<p>-Clear club protocol required to support/refer/signpost</p> <p>-Encourage coaches to track</p>	<p>-Requires further expansion on differing side effects with different HC.</p>	<p>-Content could include conversation starters</p> <p>-Activity could include designing</p>	<p>-Could have take-home infographics for each session to refer to.</p> <p>-Creation of more ‘formalised’</p>

	<p>spoken about in football. There is fear amongst players r.e. ACL injuries.</p> <p>-Biology section too brief, potential to include more anatomy</p>	<p>attendance, is this a way to help monitor absenteeism due to other reasons?</p>	<p>-Put 'management' into more football terms: i.e. if participation limited, could they be a floater in drills/ still be involved in some way?</p> <p>-Include coaches to present how they support players currently</p>	<p>club protocols around support routes</p> <p>-Focus on correct language/terminology to use</p> <p>-Highlight need for NGB to improve support to players and coaches</p>	<p>discussion (i.e. think-pair-share).</p> <p>-Too much recap each time gets repetitive, and coaches may disengage</p>
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Firstly, feedback regarding the level the information of scientific content around MC characteristics/norms was pitched at was mixed (Table 5.4). One participant considered the content to be at the correct level for the identified end-users but is scope for expansion when required:

“... deliver the basics. And if someone wants to question more, you the fact you've got the knowledge to give more is good. But if you give too much in it, they're just gonna switch off and it's gonna be scary and not too complicated, and they're not going to want to learn about it.”

(P7)

However, Participant 1 believed there to be scope to provide further explanation on some of the basic scientific principles; *“I just wondered whether it could be simplified. And [phases stated] like stage one, stage two, stage three, stage four”* (P1). The expansion of player experiences through video inclusion of the group interview was well-liked; *“So I thought it was really great discussion with the players as well. I thought it kinda normalize fluctuations and differences. I thought that was really, really good.”* (P3)

The second resource discussed MC issues or dysfunctions. Further clarity was requested around establishing clear protocols to ensure coaches can easily refer onwards, and understand the extent of their role in this:

“What's the club's process for that? ... You would say to the people speak to the parents of the player about going to the GP first or do they have access to a club doctor or is it safeguarding? Like you're not expecting them on the back of this to be like, Oh, I know exactly what you should do.” (P9)

The consideration of management strategies included within the third education session being in useful terminology, analogies and examples was highlighted as a positive *“that was quite good... basing it on pads and tampons. Because see, when people turn around and say, “Oh, you pass so many mls” ... how many people can measure that. But if someone says, I use about 3 or 6 pads I think that's much easier.”* (P9). The inclusion of HC detail was highlighted as a potential

area for expansion, with *“sometimes people that go on pills can have different side effects. So again, having to be aware that the hormones can behave differently as well.”* (P9). Furthermore, the inclusion of encouragement of tracking apps for players to ensure they are improving their own knowledge and understanding of their cycle/ symptoms was found to be a positive from a medical perspective; *““Some people don't realize they've missed their period for two or three months, and then suddenly they're down the line. So, for us, if they can produce a lot of them will come and show me their app and say, Oh, that's what my period is like. And it's really helpful for [doctors]”* (P9)

For the final resource regarding opening discussion, one participant suggested including coaches alongside players to share experiences relating to the MC:

“It might be potentially good to actually ask a couple of really good male or female coaches about how they've integrated and change the environment to be supportive for the work that you're doing. So, it's coming from coach to coach, and I think it'd be quite powerful to have a male in there.” (P2)

Finally, stakeholders fed back information regarding the overall structure of the resources, and design and/or delivery of the education intervention. One participant identified that at times information could be further divided in regard to shorter segments of discussion/ interaction, to create visuals in between to ensure the aims are always present. For example, shortening the player videos; *“an infographic of key summaries, and then a bit of discussion and then an infographic. Yeah. Just in case, for people listening to the discussion, if they don't pull out the key takeaways”* (P1). This therefore introduces the need to ensure this education promotes long-term engagement and support, not just a singular activity. This is especially true when conversations between coach and player may be limited, and therefore coaches must be prepared for every eventuality:

“it's it might not be a conversation that you'll be having every week, but you need to be able to have the conversation when it's needed, sort of thing, isn't it?” (P5)

Therefore, key feedback was attained regarding the content, format and delivery of initially proposed MHE resources. Feedback included positive aspects to the MHE including that of engagement, especially through the use of videos and discussion points to promote conversation, whilst potential areas to consider for further development was that of the level of material included in regard to some key aspects. Ensuring coaches are provided with clear take homes is critical to ensure their role in player support and development is not overwhelming, and they understand there is a structural support from the club to promote a safe space for coaches and players to develop their knowledge and improve comfort in communication to normalise the discussion around female athlete health.

(6) 5.3.6 Pilot Education

The resources were utilised to form an education intervention with football coaches within the women and girls' game. This included a pre-post questionnaire to assess changes to markers of knowledge, perceived knowledge, or comfort in communication and supportive practice. All findings and feedback from coaches can be found in Chapter 6 (Donnelly *et al.*, unpublished). The delivery of the education was performed in a format that primarily encouraged formal learning, due to the delivery of content focused on "knowledge", identified as a key problem in the 'Define' stage. However, opportunities for non-formal learning were included to enhance discussion, due to the key role of improving comfort in communication identified in our problem statements. This took two main approaches: open discussion-based questioning, organised in regard to the learning outcomes (Table 5.3) and guided by the lead researcher. Finally, the last education workshop, aiming to promote discussion and support strategies utilised a structured approach to promote communication (Appendix M). Format of education delivery is often discussed in regard to the longevity of knowledge retention, with a variety of teaching methods considered to be best-practice at engaging learners (Walker, Thomas and Driska, 2018).

(6) 5.3.6 Iteration (and Reflection)

Whilst DT is often considered to follow a linear process through the identified steps outlined above, the author has adopted a reflexive version to incorporate elements from other collaborative process to ensure a holistic approach to fulfil the needs of the end user (football coach). This involved the continuous review of the literature and supportive evidence which was published

during this process to ensure all work was up to date. For example, during the data collection process of this study one paper was published highlighting the effectiveness of a coach education programme in improving knowledge of menstrual health topics, allowing the author to reflect on both the content included and the success of this content in improving knowledge (Clarke *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, the use of coach feedback following the pilot intervention will continue to drive future education resources (Chapter 6, Donnelly *et al.*, unpublished). The content analysis utilised to gain user feedback is detailed in Chapter 6.3., with two key messages from participants when evaluation of the intervention was requested. This was the acquired knowledge, and the inter-personal skills gained and understood to be a critical aspect of athlete support.

5.4 Discussion

This study aimed to develop a sport-specific menstrual health literacy intervention following a DT approach targeted to coaches of elite and adolescent football players. This utilised a number of data collection and analysis methods across five key stages to document the collaborative, considered approach to create informative, actionable education resources focussed on the problems identified within this study. Firstly, thematic analysis of player interviews highlighted some fundamental points for inclusion and consideration within the design, content and delivery of coach education. This included the need for consideration of the individual nature of MC experiences and the impact sport has upon these. Highlighting the individual nature of menstrual characteristics, symptomology, and experiences which can also be influenced by age of the athlete has been corroborated as being necessary information to understand in previous research by adolescent athletes (Keil, Adam and Neely, 2024). This can create complexities in delivering education due to the inability to give blanket guidance, but may highlight to coaches the importance of having an open dialogue to allow each player to share their experiences and guide the support needed (McNulty *et al.*, 2020; Meignié *et al.*, 2021). However, it is important coaches are informed prior to this discussion to ensure myths and misconceptions are identified and highlighted to players. This includes the normalised behaviour regularly seen within sport on issues such as secondary amenorrhoea, or increased risk of injury, both cited within this study by players and found within the literature from players (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Hayward *et al.*, 2024) and coaches (Forsyth *et al.*, 2023). Whilst there is some evidence in infancy stages to suggest

injury risk may be elevated prior to ovulation (Martin *et al.*, 2021), there is further evidence required to confirm these findings and then inform future practice.

Frequency analysis highlighted a number of points from stakeholders for consideration towards coach education. Every stakeholder cited the need for an open, normalised culture, reported more frequently than improving coach knowledge of menstrual health topics. The role of society and sport in limiting discussion of menstrual-health related topics is well-noted in the research due to taboos limiting visibility of the topic, creating difficulties in improving knowledge and thus sharing information (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). The need for coaches to improve their knowledge has been identified both by players (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Solli *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022) and coaches (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; McGawley *et al.*, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4); Brown and Knight, 2022), and objectively by literacy assessments (Anderson *et al.*, 2023). A recent assessment of menstrual health literacy within elite English football saw a total knowledge score of 48% within coaches (Anderson *et al.*, 2023), highlighting there is still work to do in upskilling support staff on menstrual related topics. Athletes have reported that by their coach improving their knowledge, they believe conversation regarding the MC would become more open (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021).

Initial stakeholder feedback highlighted the need for the focus of education on practical support to players. This has been reiterated in a recent review within sport (McGawley *et al.*, 2023). This includes exactly how to communicate on sensitive topics. Previous work performed with coaches found they were unsure of what was appropriate to discuss, or what may offend players (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). The format of this discussion may aid this, with players sharing their preferences, alongside previous experiences. It is often mixed in responses from players in whether they may wish to discuss their menstrual experiences with their coach (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)), however players themselves have also noted this may be due to the perceived awkwardness of coaches, in that they believe they will be unable to support them (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). This was encouraged to be a top-down approach, with the NGB providing this education and therefore showing the importance and support they hold for

progressing the culture around discussing female athlete health (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Finally, the format of the education was discussed, with in-person, small group sessions being preferable. The inclusion of non-formal learning techniques are thought to improve engagement (Walker, Thomas and Driska, 2018) and long term retention of information.

Following the dissemination of draft resources to the stakeholders, adaptations to resource content included the need to ensure simplification of biology related information to maintain engagement. Moreover, critical inclusion of simple protocols for coaches to follow regarding identifying potential issues players are experiencing related to their menstrual health as vital to ensure coaches do not get overwhelmed with the role they may possess here. This also highlights the need for structural support from the club to engage and facilitate this process. This has often been found to be limited, with Donnelly *et al.* (2024; Chapter 4) performing semi-structured interviews with coaches and overwhelmingly, all eight coaches included had not received support from their NGB. Furthermore, if clear processes are not in place to guide support, players may perceive it to be pointless for them to actually share information due to the lack of action which takes place as a result. This has been seen previously within football, with MC tracking perceived to be a worthless exercise (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, the reinforcement of practical examples was recognised; with one participant highlighting the effectiveness of measuring blood loss as product changes per day. The use of this method of outlining bleeding through the number of period products is often contested within the literature, due to the variation amongst types and brands of products, or the individuals' constraints, or preferences (American Academy of Pediatrics *et al.*, 2006), yet valued in this approach, highlighting the difficult balance to strike in ensuring clear valid evidence which is engaging and retained.

The value of inter-personal skills was seen to be a valuable component of the pilot education by coaches, identified in their post-education feedback, alongside the knowledge acquired (Chapter 5.3.6). This is crucial when considering comfort in communication has often been identified as a barrier by athletes in achieving support from their coach (Höök *et al.*, 2021; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). This again highlights the crucial need for education to include the ability to practice communication through the engagement in learning. This may not always require a formalised structure, as a study assessing

different education formats found that interactive education had the highest effect sizes upon knowledge improvements, whilst pamphlets and books saw the lowest effect sizes (Evans *et al.*, 2022b). Furthermore, qualitative findings also highlighted that interventions which used peer education and group workshop style sessions were as effective as those delivered by medical staff, potentially due to the greater comfort in asking questions, and showing a starting lack of knowledge.

5.5 Limitations

There are a number of limitations to consider when evaluating this research. Firstly, due to the nature of data collection, this was targeted to one football club, limiting the ability to generalise findings and transfer to those in various clubs, cultures, or countries. The accelerated nature of this process due to time constraints meant only one round of feedback was attained from the stakeholders within the ‘ideate’ stage. Previous research has often lengthened this process, including methods such as co-creation to expand this phase to promote learning opportunities for those involved, i.e. stakeholders (Bovill, 2020; Hoolohan and Browne, 2020). However, due to the unique nature of this study that the end-user may have been different from those within the creation process, this process did not occur. Furthermore, one interview with the players and stakeholders meant thematic analysis was performed on one dataset, which may be considered limiting to the depth and richness of findings, especially in their ability to be generalised across larger populations. The methods of data collection also allowed for varying levels of detail (e.g. stakeholder feedback both written and verbally), and therefore richer insights may have been given to those through in-person collection and thus prioritised within the ‘Ideate’ stage.

5.5 Conclusions

This study followed DT practices to create and ideate a series of menstrual health education resources. Prior to the end product, the author conducted several data collection methods within key stages to identify key needs and inclusion content. The need for practical, discussion-based education allowed the format of resources to integrate formal and non-formal teaching styles, with examples throughout to ensure the aims and problem statements remained at the centre of the process. Ensuring the end user, in this case football coaches, was considered at every stage was

key to the production of appropriate, relevant resources which will continually be updated in accordance with feedback and updated research.

6. Chapter 6; Study 4

Evaluating the Effectiveness of a Pilot Menstrual Health Education Intervention in Elite Adult and Adolescent Football Coaches

6.1 Introduction

The menstrual cycle (MC) is a complex interplay of hormonal fluctuations resulting in various physical, physiological and emotional health considerations (Dawson and Reilly, 2009; Carmichael *et al.*, 2021a). Despite failing to be validated by high-quality objective evidence (McNulty *et al.*, 2020; Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021), self-reported information from sportswomen highlights that between 51-100% of athletes perceive their MC negatively affects their sporting performance (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Bruinvels *et al.*, 2021; Read *et al.*, 2021; Oester *et al.*, 2024). To date, research has primarily focused on the adult population. Few studies have included adolescents to understand their experiences of managing their MC within both daily lives and sporting environments; Taim and colleagues (2023) identified 67% of adolescents from a range of sports (age 15.4 ± 1.8 years) perceived their competitive performance was influenced by status of MC (Taim *et al.*, 2023b), whilst work in football has seen match or training performance altered by 40% in Australian players (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024), and 78% of Scottish players from Donnelly and colleagues (2025 (Chapter 3)). Therefore, with the known difficulties in menstrual experiences, ensuring athletes have support structures in their personal and sporting environments is crucial.

Menstrual health literacy (MHL) of athletes and their coaches has previously been regarded as low within the literature, potentially reducing the ability to recognise and support menstrual health issues (Larsen *et al.*, 2020; Anderson *et al.*, 2023; McGawley *et al.*, 2023). McHaffie *et al.* (2022) highlighted that key stakeholders (e.g. coaches, support staff, parents) within youth and elite support structures could not identify crucial aspects of female athlete health (i.e. consequences of irregular MCs) and regularly cited the environment as limiting conversation due to the culture and awkwardness present. Athlete's themselves note their perceived lack of knowledge of their coach to be a key reason behind not confiding in them regarding their menstrual experiences (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). There is, however, a desire to change this, with Donnelly *et al.* (2024 (Chapter 4)) demonstrating that all thirteen coaches interviewed within elite and adolescent football desired more information on the topic, and believed such information should be mandatory within the footballing National Governing Body coach

education content. This is supported by work within Australian sport, with male coaches wanting further information on MC management for their athletes, highlighting the practical nature of menstrual health education (MHE) desired to ensure athletes receive appropriate guidance (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021). Whilst a number of research publications in the field have made a call to action to improve MHL in athletes and coaches via education programmes (Höök *et al.*, 2021; McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; McGawley *et al.*, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)), to date, few studies have identified the efficacy of said interventions in improving knowledge of the MC, or in improving subsequent support for athletes' based on findings. Armour and colleagues (2020) found a web-based MHE resource improved recognition of menstrual health dysfunctions within adolescent girls in the general population, with 35% of participants perceiving the education corrected previous misguided notions around periods and MC (Armour *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, a school-based intervention involving a MHE programme in Australia found significant improvements in 75% of items related to functional ovulatory- MHL assessed (Roux *et al.*, 2023). There is, however, limited evidence to highlight education focused on those who play a role in supportive practices to women and girls. Recent work by Clarke and colleagues (Clarke *et al.*, 2024) found an online short course improved both perceived and measured knowledge of the MC in coaches working with female athletes of any level or sport. To the author's knowledge, this has yet to be performed within football. This leaves a gap in understanding of the usefulness of performing education on those who support female footballers within a performance environment.

Therefore, this study aims to:

1. Evaluate the effectiveness of a novel pilot performance focused MHE intervention in improving MHL knowledge in football coaches
2. Understand the perceived effectiveness of the MHE from football coaches in regard to their comfort in communication and supportive practices to players

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Participant Information

Eight football coaches (male $n = 7$, female $n = 1$, age = 34 ± 7 years) working with elite adult and adolescent players were recruited through purposive and convenience sampling from one club in

the Scottish Women's Premier League (SWPL). All participants had a UEFA C-License qualification, or above, and coached females at groups ranging from U12- 1st Team for a minimum of two years.

Following ethical approval by the School of Health and Life Science Ethical Committee (Approval 2023-21204-16874) at the University of the West of Scotland, informed consent was attained from participants. Participants had the right to withdraw at any time and were informed that all information would be kept confidential. To protect anonymity, participants were assigned codes to represent their information throughout the process (e.g. P1 = Participant 1).

6.2.2 Data Collection

This study adopted a longitudinal cohort intervention study design. Eight participants completed a paper- format questionnaire (Appendix N) prior to, and following, a 4- week education intervention.

6.2.2.1 MHE Resources

Education resources were produced through a DT approach with co-collaborators (Chapter 4) and adapted from questionnaires utilised by Forrest *et al.* (2024), Andersen *et al.* (2023), and Roux *et al.* (2023). In brief, the DT process included collaboration from key stakeholders within the women and girls game (1 Head of Women and Girls Football, 1 Head of Girls Academy, 1 National Governing Body Coach Educator, 2 Current Football Coaches, 3 Football Players, 1 General Practitioner/ Football Club Doctor, 1 Head of Performance, 1 University Lecturer/ Active Contributor to the MC Research Field) and utilised approaches from, and literacy gaps discussed in similar studies within the field to fill the identified gap of coaches having limited knowledge of the MC and subsequent topics, but also an inability to support players due to a lack of comfort in communication (Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Roux, H. J. Chih, *et al.*, 2023; Kiemle-Gabbay *et al.*, 2024).

Initial educational content suggestions were utilised to create appropriate resources and sent to collaborators to achieve feedback and allow adjustments/ changes where applicable. A final review was made by LF upon completion of resources prior to education sessions. Four

educational sessions were completed, with sessions ranging from 45-60 min every week, for four weeks. The initial creation of sessions was formed from principles of a social constructivist approach to the DT process shaping the model outlined in Chapter 4. This places particular emphasis on the interaction between teacher and learner, and the use of informal conversation and activities to facilitate a greater engagement and hopefully understanding of the topic in focus (Pande and Bharathi, 2020). Namely, this allows for iteration of sessions included the following:

Session 1: MC norms, underlying biology, and known experiences

Session 2: “Red Flags”: dysfunctions, support links

Session 3: Symptom management and hormonal contraception information

Session 4: Communication and support to Athletes

These sessions were focused on promoting discussion from coaches, both within sessions, but also within their coaching environment to other coaches or players. Learning objectives and session content are outlined in Table 4.2. Therefore, questions were often used throughout the education programme to promote knowledge recall, initiate conversation and ensure engagement throughout (Herbert and Lohrmann, 2011; Pande and Bharathi, 2020). This follows findings from previous work from this author ([Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 \(Chapter 4\)](#), [2025 \(Chapter 3\)](#)), but also from Clarke and colleagues (2021), where male coaches identified that education should be practical, and sports led.

6.2.2.2 Pre-Post Questionnaire

The questionnaire (Appendix N) was produced following identified aims of education content (Chapter 3), and adapted from current literature (Larsen *et al.*, 2020; Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023; Forrest *et al.*, unpublished). It was comprised of four sections (Table 6.1): Section 1: Self-ratings of knowledge and comfort; Section 2: short-answer MC knowledge-related responses (MC length, symptoms, management, sporting impacts); Section 3: Statement agreement of MC-related facts/myths/misconceptions, and Section 4: (post- education only) Evaluation of education, through short answer responses. Question formatting included both quantitative (e.g. Likert-Scale questions) and open text qualitative questions.

Table 6.1 Question Formatting for the Pre-Post Education Questionnaire assessing MC knowledge, perceived knowledge and comfort in communication, and post-education evaluation.

Question	Format of Questioning
Section 1	<i>Self-ratings of knowledge, and comfort of scenario-based examples</i>
1.1-1.4	7-item Likert Scale (No Knowledge-Very Poor-Poor-Average-Good-Very Good-Excellent)
2.1-2.7	7-item Likert Scale (Strongly Disagree-Disagree-Somewhat Disagree-Neither Agree nor Disagree-Somewhat Agree-Agree-Strongly Agree)
Section 2	<i>Knowledge responses (MC length, symptoms, management, sporting impacts)</i>
3.1-3.10	Open text responses
Section 3	<i>Statement Agreement of MC-related facts/myths/misconceptions</i>
4.1-4.7	6-item Likert Scale (Strongly Disagree-Disagree-Neither Agree nor Disagree-Agree-Strongly Agree-Unsure)
Section 4 (Post intervention only)	<i>Evaluation of education</i>
5.1-5.4	7-item Likert Scale (Strongly Disagree-Disagree-Somewhat Disagree-Neither Agree nor Disagree-Somewhat Agree-Agree-Strongly Agree)
5.5-5.8	Open text responses

6.2.3 Analysis

Data was inputted into Microsoft Excel (version 16.90 2024, Microsoft Corporation), and descriptive statistics summarised, such as key demographic information (e.g. age), displayed as Mean \pm SD. Data related to scores were presented as Median (Inter-Quartile Range). Further statistical tests were performed on RStudio (RStudio, R v2023.09.1+494). Likert-Scale data was converted into numerical order to allow for statistical analysis. Non-normal distribution was identified in all questions ($p < 0.001$). Wilcoxon signed-rank Tests were therefore utilised to assess differences pre-post, with effect sizes also reported and significant set at $p < 0.05$. This was performed on Jamovi (Jamovi, version 2.3.21.0). Whilst typically Wilcoxon Rank requires larger

sample sizes to confirm validity, power analysis identified Achieved Power of 0.907 (Question 1) and 0.822 (Question 2).

For short-answer qualitative responses, conceptual content (frequency) analysis was utilised for questions regarding menstrual products, symptoms/ other list data and listed in descending order of frequency (Mayring, 2015). This involved collating like-minded codes through implicit interpretation, and counting appearance within the data (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005; Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020). Short-answer post-education feedback also followed frequency analysis, with all responses coded semantically and quantified in order of frequency (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005; Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020). This was performed throughout the full complete dataset, irrespective of order of question asked. Final codes were then grouped inductively under key messages to summarise the quantitative findings.

Ten participants started this study, with two participants information removed following insufficient completion of the survey (i.e. no post-intervention responses). A total of eight participants (youth team coaches $n = 6$, senior team coaches $n = 2$) were included in the final analysis.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Perceived Knowledge Pre-Post Intervention

Perceived knowledge of participants found a statistically significant improvement to coaches “*knowledge of ways to reduce MC symptoms or feelings*” pre-to-post intervention from 3.5 to 5.0 ($p = 0.048$). The remaining questions, whilst seeing an average change in perceived knowledge rankings from 3.5 pre-education to 4.5 post education, was not found to overall be statistically significant (Figure 6.1; Table 6.2).

Figure 6.1 Boxplot highlighting pre-post participant responses regarding perceived knowledge of the MC. * denotes significance, set as $p < 0.05$.

Table 6.2 Pre- and Post-Menstrual Health Education Responses for Perceived Knowledge (Q1), Comfort in Communication (Q2), and Menstrual-Health Related Myths (Q3)

Question	Pre (Median (IQR))	Post (Median (IQR))	p-value	Effect size
1.1 Your knowledge of what the MC is?	4.5 (1.3)	5.0 (0.3)	0.134	0.808
1.2 Your knowledge of what a normal MC is?	4.0 (1.0)	5.5 (1.0)	0.056	1.070
1.3 Your knowledge of symptoms can be experienced during a MC?	4.5 (1.0)	6.0 (0.3)	0.089	1.030
1.4 Your knowledge of ways to reduce MC symptoms or feelings?	3.5 (1.3)	5.0 (1.3)	0.048	1.350
2.1 I feel comfortable discussing the MC if a player was to approach me	4.0 (2.3)	6.0 (1.0)	0.073	0.826
2.2 I feel comfortable starting a discussion with a player on their MC	3.0 (1.3)	5.5 (1.5)	0.057	1.230
2.3 I could identify if a player was struggling with symptoms associated with their MC	4.0 (1.3)	5.0 (0.3)	0.242	0.545
2.4 If a player was affected by their cycle during training or a match, I would feel confident in knowing how to support them	4.0 (1.3)	5.5 (1.0)	0.034	1.240
2.5 I would know the right people to direct a player to if they required further support regarding their MC	4.0 (2.5)	6.0 (0.0)	0.073	0.952
4.1 Regular periods are an indicator of good health	4.0 (0.3)	5.0 (0.3)	0.129	0.726
4.2 Experiences of the MC are very individual (e.g. symptoms will be different from one person to the next)	5.0 (0.3)	5.0 (0.0)	0.346	0.586
4.3 The MC has a negative impact on sporting performance ability in all females*	3.5 (4.5)	1.5 (1.0)	0.035	-1.530
4.4 It is normal for a female to lose their period if they are doing lots of exercise training*	4.0 (3.3)	3.5 (2.0)	0.461	-0.353
4.5 Exercising whilst having a period is not recommended for most girls or women*	2.0 (1.5)	1.5 (1.0)	0.174	-0.586
4.6 Players are more likely to be injured on their period than at any other point in their cycle*	3.5 (2.0)	2.0 (2.0)	0.055	-1.070
4.7 Light to moderate exercise can help symptoms related to periods	4.0 (0.8)	4.5 (1.0)	0.374	0.409
Question Scales: Q1.1 - 1.4, 1 = No Knowledge to 7= Excellent Q2.1 - 2.5, 1 = Strongly Disagree to 7 = Strongly Agree Q4.1 – 4.7, 1 = Strongly Disagree to 6 = Strongly Agree, 7 = Unsure *reverse answers desirable				

6.3.2 Assessed Knowledge Pre-Post Intervention

A 'Total Knowledge Score' was calculated from a total of 20 survey responses that related to participants knowledge of MC characteristics, norms, and practices, MC hygiene, management and sporting practices. Total Knowledge Score was also not significant pre-to-post on average, (pre 16.6 ± 2.1 (range 13 – 19); post 18.1 ± 1.7 (range 15 - 20, $p = 0.085$). Age of menarche both pre- and post-education reported a median of 12 years. Cycle length was correctly identified both pre- and post- education with median scores of 28. Post-intervention, every participant was able to correctly identify the age females should seek medical attention if yet to reach menarche (16 years) (Appendix N).

6.3.3 Comfort in Communication and Supportive Practices Pre-Post Intervention

Regarding comfort in communication and supportive practices, agreement with the statement “*If a player was affected by their cycle during training or a match, I would feel confident in knowing how to support them*” was found to have a significant increase from 4.0 to 5.5 ($p = 0.034$) (Table 6.2). The remaining questions within this section changed from 4.1 to 5.4, failing to be statistically significant (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.2 Boxplot highlighting pre-post responses regarding coaches perceived comfort in communication, and resultant supportive practices for MC experiences in football players. * denotes significance, set as $p < 0.05$.

6.3.4 Recognition of Myths and Misconceptions Pre-Post Intervention

Question 4 (Section 3) identified participants ability to recognise factually correct or incorrect statements regarding the MC in sport and its impact upon women and their sporting performances. The following statement “*The MC has a negative impact on sporting performance ability in all females*” resulted in a statistically significant reduction in agreement from 3.5 to 1.5 pre-to-post intervention ($p = 0.035$). No significant differences were found pre-post in other questions regarding myths or misconceptions of the MC or related matters (Table 6.2).

6.3.5 Post Intervention Coach Feedback

Post-education feedback was gathered to understand participant experiences of the education series through the frequency analysis of short text responses. Two key messages were produced to summarise the quantitative analysis; Interpersonal Skills and Acquired knowledge (Table 6.3).

Table 6.3 Breakdown of key messages created to summarise post-MHE feedback from football coaches

Key Messages and sub-messages	Frequency (no.)
<u>Inter-personal Skills</u>	14
<i>Normalise conversation</i>	5
<i>Help players feel comfortable in discussion</i>	2
<i>Be approachable</i>	1
<i>Be relatable</i>	1
<i>Refrain from Judgement</i>	1
<i>Body language</i>	1
<i>'Show' knowledge</i>	1
<i>Signpost</i>	1
<u>Acquired Knowledge</u>	12
<i>Recognition of MC impacts</i>	5
<i>Recognise MC symptoms</i>	3
<i>Individual experiences</i>	2
<i>Age-specific considerations</i>	1
<i>Impact of overtraining</i>	1

Firstly, the value of fostering interpersonal skills was identified by the ability to foster openness and inclusivity within discussion and overall environment within sport, through a number of codes highlighting the importance of MHE not only on the content, but in the recognition that for players to receive support, coaches must be able to deliver any knowledge acquired effectively:

“Create an open and honest environment where players feel comfortable to approach a conversation around a period. having more confidence handling these scenarios and having the education to signpost them in the correct direction” (P7)

The skills required in delivering any support was also recognised through one participant highlighting the ways in which will improve the comfort in communication from players; *“Normalize the conversation. Be approachable. Use the information in the correct way (body language)”* (P1). Finally, the importance of ensuring players understand they have the option of utilising their coach to listen or provide practical support is highlighted; *“Just simply informing the girls that we have been educated. Show awareness”* (P2).

Furthermore, the ‘Acquired knowledge’ of participants was identified as a key outcome of the MHE. This focused on the content of the education retained and indicated the practical sense of knowledge attained (Table 6.3). Three coaches identified that the need for individualisation of support due to athlete experiences was beneficial information: *“better awareness and understanding of individuals symptom and possible impact on performance”* (P3). A further two coaches cited specific aspects to the education, e.g. age of menarche, and impact of overtraining (i.e. RED-S); *“how overtraining can have a negative effect on their period and health”* (P3). Furthermore, practical applications were also recognised: *“...Encourage players to track their . Be more wary of symptoms to look out for and be aware of how this might impact the individual.”* (P7). Therefore, the two messages identified highlighted the take-home messages from coaches in regard to the content, delivery and translation of MHE to practical support within sport.

6.4 Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of a series of MC education sessions on football coaches' knowledge and understanding of the MC and its perceived impact on comfort in communication and supportive practices. Whilst previous research has shown coach knowledge regarding the MC is insufficient considering the vital role they play in player development (Anderson *et al.*, 2023; McGawley *et al.*, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)), this study is the first to perform a novel MHE intervention targeted to improving knowledge and supportive practices solely in football. Whilst several questions did not find significant improvements following a 4-part education series, significant improvements were found in a number of key areas regarding the practical support and understanding of athletes within football coaches. Qualitative responses post-intervention suggests this process was found to be valued by coaches and deemed

worthwhile for improving confidence in symptom management and support to players and has a worthwhile place within women and girls' football.

The assessed 'Total Knowledge Score' of coaches was not found to significantly improve following the MHE intervention, however, a worthwhile consideration is what could potentially be considered to be a high baseline knowledge of participants. This total score was higher than a recent previous MHL assessment within football coaches (63%; Anderson *et al.*, 2023), but with different literacy assessment utilised, it is hard to draw conclusions and calls for the need for a validated questionnaire within the field. Furthermore, pre-education, 75% (6/8) coaches within this study (based in Scotland) could correctly identify the average duration of a MC, compared to 89% in England (Anderson *et al.*, 2023), and 14% in Africa (Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023), highlighting the varied knowledge levels worldwide due to influential societal, educational, cultural, religious and contextual factors (Johnston-Robledo and Chrisler, 2020; McHugh, 2020). Post-intervention, 100% (8/8) of coaches in the current study correctly identified the age that an athlete should seek medical help if they have not started their period. Both primary and secondary amenorrhoea is known to be prevalent in female adult sports (Taim *et al.*, 2023a), and with health-repercussions including cardiovascular, bone-density and fertility complications (Shufelt, Torbati and Dutra, 2017), ensuring awareness of basic menstrual functions is crucial to long-term health and wellbeing. Amenorrhoea has previously not been well understood by stakeholders within sporting organisations and subsequently affects the support athletes receive (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022). Survey data within U.S collegiate coaches identified that 30% were able to list specific components of the female athlete triad (Pantano, 2006). One recent study, however, showed 63% of football staff were able to identify the definition of amenorrhoea (not defined by type intended) (Anderson *et al.*, 2023). Ensuring coaches can identify potential menstrual health related issues which may arise is key to being able to signpost athletes to medical support if required. This also helps to set key parameters around the scope of coaches within education; coaches are not medical professionals and should not relay specific medical advice. Instead, empowering athletes to improve their own knowledge and understanding creates a more open environment.

Prior to the MC education intervention, coaches self-reported perceived knowledge of MC, MC norms, symptoms, and management strategies as being between a median of 3.5 - 4.5

depending on the question. Following the intervention, all items within the questionnaire related to perceived knowledge were ranked as a median of 5 ('Good') or higher. Furthermore, the perceived "*knowledge of ways to reduce MC symptoms or feelings?*" was found to be significantly higher post-intervention. Published literature in this field has regularly cited that coaches feel they have limited knowledge on topics regarding female athlete health (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4); Hyde and Zipp, 2023; Bergstrom *et al.*, 2023). Work within Scottish swimming highlighted that coaches of adolescent and adult swimmers were not confident that the knowledge they possessed would enable them to give practical advice to their athletes (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). Coaches within a range of female sports found that their experiences may not have equipped them to be able to effectively support female athletes due to their own lived-experiences or HC use (Brown and Knight, 2022). This is supported by Donnelly *et al.* (2024; Chapter 4) as one coach identified that they did not work to improve their knowledge of the MC as they did not experience resultant symptoms. It has also been previously identified that lack of knowledge in turn directly impacts the support athletes receive (Brown and Knight, 2022). Moreover, athletes report perceiving that the knowledge of their coach will prevent them from being honest with their experiences regarding their MC (Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). The importance of education being practical, and specific to supporting individuals, rather than on basic MC characteristics and biology, has been cited regularly by coaches to ensure they have the toolkit for this support potentially despite a lack of knowledge on some key points (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Interestingly, this study highlighted perceived knowledge scores to significantly improve, despite the lack of objective based knowledge questions being significantly different. Whilst there could be positives to take from this finding, such as coaches feeling more comfortable in initiating open dialogue, this can cause issues when considering the potentially inflated confidence, passing on what could be incorrect information to subjective individuals such as adolescent players. Perception of knowledge cannot be interchanged with knowledge itself, and a notable point to ensure education occurs continually to address these points (Persky, Lee and Schlesselman, 2020).

Pre-intervention statements regarding coach comfort in communication and supportive practices had median scores of between 3.0 – 4.0. Comfort in communication on menstrual-related matters is known to be limited from coaches within women's sport (Bergström, Rosvold and

Sæther, 2023; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). This is often rooted in cultural stigmas and taboos that portray menstruation as a private or even shameful matter (Haidar, Solhi, & Khanjari, 2020). These attitudes can lead to environments where athletes feel uncomfortable discussing their menstrual health as their coach does not show willingness to discuss such matters, a narrative already voiced by athletes (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Höök *et al.*, 2021; McHaffie *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023; Taim *et al.*, 2023b). This could have negative consequences when severe symptoms do not receive the recognition and subsequent support they require and thus have a negative impact on performance and wellbeing. Coaches have discussed not wanting to speak about MC related topics due to fear of saying the wrong thing, offending the individual, or speaking out of turn (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024; Chapter 4). Following the intervention, however, responses rating from the statement “*If a player was affected by their cycle during training or a match, I would feel confident in knowing how to support them*” significantly improved, highlighting the positive use of education to promote confidence in communication and supportive practices. With confidence regularly cited as a key limitation to opening discussion with athletes (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021; Höök *et al.*, 2021), the importance of menstrual health education is highlighted through this significant finding. Having a coach who is comfortable in communication and creates a safe space for the athletes to relay their MC experiences has been cited by athletes as being more important than the gender of the coach (Donnelly *et al.*, 2025; Chapter 3)

Upon assessing participants ability to recognise myths and misconceptions regarding the MC within a sporting context, the statement “*The MC has a negative impact on sporting performance ability in **all** females*” saw a statistically significant drop in agreement. The individual nature of MC experiences is commonly identified within the literature, making it difficult to provide guidelines for coaches to follow for ensuring players receive sufficient accommodation, where required. Whilst limiting daily activities due to MC experiences is found within the general population (Gopalan *et al.*, 2020; Schoep *et al.*, 2019), work within elite sport suggests this occurs less frequently due to the commitments and pressures to perform (Findlay *et al.*, 2020). When asked if they avoid or alter their training load due to their cycle, 75% of naturally menstruating adolescent football players reported they did not (Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). Whilst this can be perceived in creating difficulties in coaches knowing how to support their team

due to varying experiences, it again highlights the importance of creating an open environment where athletes believe they can discuss their personal experiences, and their coach can recognise potential issues worth escalating (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). Furthermore, ensuring the culture is not based on the negative aspects related to the MC is crucial; athletes have reported positive aspects to their MC (Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Armour *et al.*, 2020a). Work within this thesis highlights that pre-pubescent athletes perceive having a period will negatively impact their performance because they “*never hear anything positive*” around the MC (Donnelly *et al.*, 2025 (Chapter 3)). Adult elite athletes often validate this, with reasons such as being fearful of bleeding and its associated implications (Findlay *et al.*, 2020); highlighting the importance of setting a positive and supportive culture that younger girls can see. This is especially true in sport which can be shown from management level, with support strategies such as considering sports kit and uniform colours and providing accessible period products (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021). There were still misconceptions which did not significantly improve post-intervention, such as agreement with the statement “*Light to moderate exercise can help symptoms related to periods*” which was 4 and 4.5 pre- and post-education, respectively, highlighting aspects the education failed to sufficiently target. This result highlights the complexities in changing established beliefs or perceptions, especially when they may be influenced by personal experiences, cultural beliefs or long standing misconceptions perpetuated by society (Johnston-Robledo and Chrisler, 2020; Olson *et al.*, 2022). This therefore highlights the need for future education to focus on practical ways to help players manage symptoms and be performed long-term to ensure these long-standing beliefs can be changed over time.

The post-education reflective evaluation of the education reinforced the positive importance of educating coaches on practical tips to ensure players receive appropriate support. It has previously been identified within the literature that MHE should not be solely biology focussed and instead remain relevant to the sport and aspects the coach can work to help (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)). The format of education is crucial to this (Walker, Thomas and Driska, 2018; Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4), 2025 (Chapter 3)), with a recent review by McGawley and colleagues highlighting the importance of both formal, informal and non-formal methods of learning to improve MHL and utilizing the knowledge in practical settings (McGawley *et al.*, 2023). The dissemination format has previously been found to be important in regard to MHE,

with a systematic review collating results from MHE to adolescent girls within the general population, and found that education which involved interaction had the highest effect size upon knowledge improvements, compared to books, or pamphlets which had the lowest (Evans *et al.*, 2022b). The majority of this work has been performed in low-moderate -income countries, and thus little is known as to the considerations upon MHE within more developed, and further, in developed sporting communities.

Furthermore, the pedagogical approach to the education performed is a consideration, with this study utilising a constructivist approach to learning (Donnelly *et al.*, unpublished (Chapter 5)), focused on the collaborative elements such as questioning and initiating discussion. Therefore, it may be interpreted that participants feel more comfortable within the learning environment, but this may not translate to knowledge attained, or the ability to convey this information outwith the “safe space” of the education. Furthermore, coaches recognised the importance of setting the culture within the team, and that “*normalising the conversation*” (P1, P3) will allow players to feel safe in discussion. This has been previously recognised within adult and adolescent football, in work from McHaffie and colleagues where this has been driven from the top “seniority” (i.e. head coach) and welcomed by players (McHaffie *et al.*, 2023). There are also educational aspects the coaches believed they could use to support players, such as encouraging the use of MC tracking to improve athlete awareness and understanding of their own MC. A recent study within elite rugby showed that players believed that sharing information via a MC tracking app improved the coach-athlete relationship due to the enhanced communication and allow resultant supportive practices, such as tailoring training sessions to player needs (Verrier, Knight and Brown, 2024). Setting clear scope of practice is crucial within sporting organisations (McGawley *et al.*, 2023), as too is the understanding that some athletes may only want to discuss with a medical professional may not change despite coach education potentially improving (Findlay *et al.*, 2020; Brown, Knight and Forrest Née Whyte, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022). Finally, coaches cited that even the act of highlighting they have undergone education on the MC will hopefully open conversations within a team setting and improve their athlete's ability to relay their experiences.

6.5 Limitations and Future Work

There are a number of limitations which limit the ability to generalise findings across sports, countries and cultures. The small sample size was due to the maximum number of coaches within one academy but limits the power of results, thus further research with larger sample sizes is required to ensure the resources can be scalable. The environment this education performed in meant the participants were familiar with the educator and with each other, potentially encouraging the discussion throughout. The researchers' involvement with the club for 3 years, plus the advertisement of the researchers' work across the club may have helped the initial scores due to increased awareness on the topic. With many coaches citing the informal social learning to be preferential (Walker, Thomas and Driska, 2018), this may have aided engagement and thus knowledge markers. Furthermore, two participants involved had previously been involved in a study by this research group (Donnelly *et al.*, 2024 (Chapter 4)), which, whilst it did not involve education, it discussed menstrual-related factors within a football context and may have initiated a curiosity to learn more and biased questions regarding comfort in communication. Therefore, future work may involve understanding the efficacy of education with coaches from other clubs who may not possess the same baseline knowledge.

In addition, the lack of a validated MHL questionnaire for those who play a supportive role within sport limits the ability to compare findings to other research studies. Whilst this study attempted to ensure a well-rounded assessment, utilising questions from previous work within the literature (Larsen *et al.*, 2020; Mkumbuzi *et al.*, 2023, Forrest *et al.*, unpublished), the lack of a universal measure leaves difficulties in comparing findings. Future work could also include longitudinal studies to assess the retention of in knowledge and attitudes over time, with athlete's perspectives on whether any improvements in coaches' knowledge translates to improved support. Currently, only one study has shown a follow up within athlete education, with 6 months post course showing significantly higher knowledge markers than pre-education (Clarke *et al.*, 2024). Future interventions should consider a more holistic approach that incorporates not only education but also ongoing support, practical resources, and opportunities for coaches to engage with the material in real-world contexts.

6.6 Conclusions

This study found that a MHE intervention saw positive post-intervention reflective evaluation from football coaches despite a lack of significance in many assessed markers of knowledge, comfort in communication, and recognition of myths or misconceptions. Confidence in symptom management and overall ability to support players with MC matters was significantly improved. This highlights the worthwhile use of education programmes in improving MHL to improve confidence to help manage symptoms and thus support players within football. Sporting bodies should facilitate the organisation and funding of such programmes to ensure coaches have the toolkit to open discussion, recognise issues and impacts to players, and help management of the MC within sport.

7. Chapter 7

General Discussion

7.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to provide an overview of all findings within this thesis upon reflection of its original aims and objectives. By conducting four studies, this thesis sought to fill what was considered a gap in the research, with the aim to provide a valuable contribution to improving the discussion, culture and policies within sport regarding menstrual support to women and girls. *Section 7.2* will outline the main aims and findings of this thesis through each study included. *Section 7.3* will then explore these findings in greater detail, focusing on the contribution to the existing body of knowledge within the field. The significance of this contribution and implications the findings have upon practice is outlined in *Section 7.4*. Following this, in *Section 7.5*, the general limitations to consider within this research are outlined. This chapter concludes by highlighting potential use of this research to drive future work within the field (*Section 7.6*), and general conclusions of the PhD (*Section 7.7*).

7.2 Summary of Study Findings

This thesis aimed to develop an understanding of the current landscape of MC experiences within football, from both a players and coaches' perspective (Chapters 3, 4) to allow the identification of areas of knowledge, understanding, and support of MC health and experiences, with later chapters documenting approaches to improve said areas (Chapters 5, 6). These aims were achieved through the completion of four studies, independent in nature yet interrelated in their narration of key findings.

Chapter 3, Study 1:

Prior to understanding the support players may require managing their MC, it was necessary to first establish players experiences and perceptions they held of the MC, both personally and generally within society and sport. Therefore, the first study within this thesis aimed to 1) investigate the adolescent and adult elite football players experiences and perceptions of the MC and the perceived impact on performance, and 2) to understand communication practices and perceived support to adolescent and adult elite players. To achieve this, a sample of both elite and adolescent football players completed an online questionnaire composed of key topics including MC characteristics, symptoms, experiences, management strategies and communication practices.

In addressing aim 1, findings of the questionnaire demonstrated that symptom prevalence was not significantly associated by age category (adults and adolescents). There was a significant association between age category and the perception of performance being impacted by the MC. In relation to aim 2, it was found that communication practices amongst adolescents was limited. Athletes believed that coach knowledge on the MC was limited, which hindered support and discussions about their experiences. In general, adolescents reported challenges in communicating their MC experiences, and within sport, the gender of coach coupled with the perceived lack of knowledge were key reasons players did not share their experiences and thus gained little support in return.

Therefore, Chapter 3 found both elite adult and adolescent football players report wellbeing and performance impacts due to their MC. Furthermore, the inclusion of adolescents improved the understanding of a youth perspective, highlighting the requirement of support structures to equip players with tools to manage and communicate about their MC.

Chapter 4, Study 2:

Following the findings from Chapter 3 that players perceived that coach knowledge was limited, and they would be unable to support them, the author decided to focus work within coaches to expand their understanding on this topic. Therefore, Study 2 aimed to: 1) investigate elite adult and adolescent football coaches' awareness and perceptions of the MC relative to football performance; and 2) explore the lived experience of football coaches and the influence this has on MC knowledge and communication between coach and athlete. This was achieved through semi-structured interviews with football coaches, with reflexive thematic analysis identifying key themes to summarise findings.

The environment, first generally within society but also that within sport, was seen to limit awareness of the MC due to the lack of visibility and discussion of the topic. Coaches reported embarrassment to hinder discussion of the MC with players, and perceived players to feel similar. The coach-athlete dynamic found a series of factors that could affect the coaches' experiences of support to players, such as the relationship developed due to time spent together and trust gained.

This familiarity was found to impact the comfort in communication. Finally, the lack of knowledge was highlighted by coaches alongside the need for education to ensure players receive the targeted support required. The coaches' awareness and understanding of the MC both generally and within sport influenced their perceived ability to support players. Coaches identified they play a crucial role in the development of young females and currently do not support this aspect of their maturation.

Therefore, findings highlight the need to support coaches to provide them the toolkit to facilitate discussion, improving comfort in both players and coaches and ensure players receive adequate and practical support within their sporting environment.

Chapter 5, Study 3:

Through the identification that coaches require education on the MC to ensure they can provide appropriate support within football from both players (Chapter 3), and coaches (Chapter 4), the creation of education resources was documented within Chapter 5. Study 3 aimed to develop a sport-specific MHL intervention following a DT approach targeted to coaches of elite and adolescent football players. This involved collaborating with key stakeholders within the women and girls' game through a number of data collection methods to ensure a considered, relevant approach was taken. Data collection includes a needs analysis, player interviews, stakeholder engagement and feedback, resource creation, piloting the intervention and attaining feedback.

Key findings from this process included the need for consideration on individual complexities related to the MC characteristics and experiences, highlighted by players, alongside the need for coaches to learn how to address personal matters in an empathetic manner. During the process of defining the key problems to be addressed through resource creation, key stakeholders offered recommendations on how this should be carried out. Firstly, the aim of education highlighted by all coaches was that of creating an open culture and discussion. The format was also highlighted, with a need for clear simple content which at its heart focused on the practical solutions/ advice to give to coaches to ensure they have the toolkit to address challenges players may experience in regard to their MC. Two key problems were defined: 1) Coaches of women and girls' football did not have enough knowledge to support players in regard to their

menstrual health experiences, and 2) Coaches were not comfortable in communication and lacked the sport-specific understanding of support strategies. Education resources were then designed based around tackling these issues and underwent feedback from stakeholders. The education intervention was then piloted, documented within Study 4, with feedback attained from users and the author reflecting upon the process to ensure constant evaluation and iteration.

Chapter 6, Study 4:

Chapter 6 was a direct follow-up from the chapter previous, as it follows the first prototype of an education intervention created on Chapter 5. Study 4 aimed to 1) evaluate the effectiveness of a novel pilot performance focused MHE intervention in improving menstrual health knowledge in football coaches, and 2) understand the perceived effectiveness of the MHE from football coaches in regard to their comfort in communication and supportive practices to players. This was performed through the analysis of pre-post questionnaires within a 4-week pilot intervention study of eight football coaches.

In addressing aim 1, total knowledge scores were not significantly improved following the education intervention, yet median scores pre-and post-intervention were seen to be correct for a number of measures including age of menarche and typical MC lengths. Participant ability to identify myths and misconceptions was also queried, with a significant improvement in the ability to recognise the individual nature of MC experiences within sport. However, in relation to aim 2, a number of significant improvements were identified. This includes coaches perceived knowledge of reducing MC symptoms or feelings, and feeling confident in supporting players impacted by their MC. Following the education, coaches identified their take home messages to be the importance of creating open, supportive environments within sport to facilitate discussion further. The education programme was well received and deemed as a valuable exercise, despite the limited improvements in markers of knowledge.

7.3 General Discussion Summary

Athletes are known to report health, wellbeing and performance impacts as a result of their MC (McNulty *et al.*, 2023; Oester *et al.*, 2024). This self-reported evidence has highlighted the need for improved support to athletes to manage menstruation within a performance environment (McGawley *et al.*, 2023). Despite the growing recognition of these complications, support for menstrual-related issues within sport remains limited due to several barriers, including limited knowledge, communication and other inter-personal challenges identified between both coach and athlete (von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023). This has often been investigated at the elite level, but little data capturing the development of youth athletes throughout the sporting environment. With adolescents known to face unique physiological considerations and social challenges, ensuring support is targeted without relevant supporting evidence within sport is difficult. Furthermore, it is cited that coaches' require education on menstrual health topics, and work has shown that this can prove successful in improving knowledge of coaches in broader sporting contexts (Clarke *et al.*, 2024). As regularly discussed within this thesis, however, such efforts require further documentation and assessment to consider the age and sport-specific considerations within football, which remain limited. Therefore, the purpose of this thesis was to 1) understand the current landscape of MC experiences and perceptions within football; and 2) to develop and assess the effectiveness of targeted MHE resources in improving the knowledge and support from football coaches. The findings of this work will hopefully strengthen the narrative that sporting organisations require further focus on supporting their elite and youth athletes, in both individual support and broader consideration of adopting a positive culture around sharing experiences and normalising the conversation of menstrual health. The findings from the four studies reveal a significant gap in the understanding of menstrual health within football, and a discomfort around discussing the topic both generally and within sport.

7.3.1 Interpretation of Findings

This thesis provides contributions to the research field and practical landscape within sport through findings of four studies. When understanding the overarching conclusions which can be drawn from this work and subsequently impact practice, two key areas can be further discussed to elicit key understanding of findings within the context of the existing literature. Firstly, this thesis aimed to understand the current landscape of experiences and perceptions of the MC within football (Section 7.3.1.1), through the lens of both players and coaches. Upon completion of these studies

and thus improved understanding of the areas requiring further development within sport, discussion turns to the support for players within football, through the aim of developing and assessing the effectiveness of MHE resources (Section 7.3.1.2). This section therefore provides further detail on the key findings within the context of sport.

7.3.1.1 Understanding the Current Landscape of Experiences and Perceptions of the MC within Football

Chapter 3 of this thesis reported significant age-related associations between adolescent and adult athletes regarding their perceptions of the MC impacting football performance, and in communication strategies to discuss these experiences. Firstly, this finding was interesting when it is known that adolescent physiology can often lead to high rates of menstrual dysfunctions, such as HMB (3 - 42% of athletes; Bruinvels *et al.*, 2016; Vannuccini *et al.*, 2020; Taim *et al.*, 2023a), dysmenorrhoea (71.1%; Armour *et al.*, 2019) or PMS (29.6%; (Steiner *et al.*, 2011). However, there is still a lack of comparative research within adults to determine if this difference is significantly greater. As discussed in Chapter 3, there may be a positive conclusion to draw from the finding that fewer adolescents view their MC to impact football performance, in that the current focus of improving support within society and sporting environments may be benefitting the younger generation. This follows trends such as the dialogue within media highlighting athlete experiences (*BBC Sport*, 2022a; *BBC Sport*, 2022b), or sporting policies providing more consideration towards the effects of bleeding (The Guardian, 2023; *BBC Sport*, 2023). This was noted within Scottish Swimming, with swimmers perceiving the culture around menstruation was improving with time (Hyde and Zipp, 2023). However, with Chapter 3 also recognising that communication amongst adolescents was very limited, it is difficult to understand where they have gained this support. Furthermore, with 28.8% of adolescents utilising social media as a source of information, this also creates difficulties in understanding what information is being presented. Whilst social media can be viewed positively as a means to challenge the discourse regularly portrayed within general society to improve visibility of important topics (Manduley *et al.*, 2018), the lack of verification of information and the rising trend of spreading disinformation, especially in the wake of issues such as COVID-19 pandemic and the 2020 Presidential election (Li and Chang, 2022) leads to the possibility that young women are receiving wrong and potentially harmful or fear-invoking information. The point raised by one pre-menarcheal player that they “*never hear anything positive*” about having a period may continue this narrative. Moreover, the

lack of easily accessible factual information available through online means was highlighted from coaches in Chapter 4, with conflicting and indecipherable information making it difficult to upskill themselves on topics relating to menstrual health. Overall, the findings of Chapter 3 remain that the majority of athletes, adult or adolescent, report that their MC impacts their football performance in some capacity. The reported prevalence was greater than previous survey-based studies in adults (Bruinvels *et al.*, 2016; Ekenros *et al.*, 2022; Armour *et al.*, 2020a), and adolescents (G. Brown *et al.*, 2024; Taim *et al.*, 2023b), and therefore brings to light the need for age-and sport-specific education and support.

In general, communication on topics related to menstrual health was found to be a significant challenge within both players (Chapter 3) and coaches (Chapter 4). The idea that players perceived their coach to lack the knowledge, or comfort in communication to support them has been corroborated within other sports by adults (Höök *et al.*, 2021; von Rosen *et al.*, 2022; Bergström, Rosvold and Sæther, 2023) and adolescents (Taim *et al.*, 2023b). Similarly, coaches within Chapter 4 reported they had a lack of knowledge on key topics, supporting previous evidence in Australian sport (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021). However, Chapter 6 saw pre-education knowledge scores on average to be 16.6 out of 20, which poses a question in the confidence of coaches in their knowledge, rather than their knowledge itself, or the level of the questionnaire, discussed throughout this thesis. Key influences on this knowledge were found to lie in the limited visibility of discussion, prompting the topic to feel secret, or inappropriate to have (Chapter 5). The topic of menstruation has long been considered a taboo in society and across a range of cultures globally (Roberts *et al.*, 2002; McHugh, 2020), and remains true to date in many. Furthermore, other factors were also cited by both players and coaches as limiting the support players received. Discussed in Chapter 4, the dynamic established between coach and athlete encompassed a range of influential considerations impacting the likelihood of conversing on the topic of the athletes' menstrual experiences, enabling the coach to understand their personal perception and accommodate this within their scope of practice. This includes the age of the athlete, with younger athletes providing complications to the coach in understanding what may be appropriate, especially when parents are heavily involved in the sporting community. The lack of consideration of adolescents within football research may have impacted this, with a lack of understanding around why they may need to be understood or discussed. The nature of the

relationship itself was also noted and reinforced by players within Chapter 3. Being able to discuss more personal matters of any topic relied on key inter-personal skills displayed by coach and athlete. Similarly, Singaporean athletes within the work of Taim *et al.* (2023b) reported a lack of trust with their coach limited the ability to voice any issues experienced, and felt misunderstood or disregarded by their coach. In a practical sense, this highlights that whilst educating coaches is important (McGawley *et al.*, 2023), coaches need to create a safe space for athletes to perceive they can utilise their support.

In summary, we can conclude that the majority of athletes, both adult and adolescent, are impacted by their MC, and perceive this to impact their football performance. There are significant difficulties, however, in conveying this information to receive the support they may require. Similarly, football coaches report little knowledge on the topic of menstrual health, impacted by the culture within general society and football, leaving them uncomfortable in communication. They reported wanting more education on the topic in a practical, sport-specific manner to ensure players received appropriate support. However, this must be integrated within an environment where athletes understand they can trust and utilise this support. The practical significance of these findings is reported in Section 7.3.2.

7.3.1.2 Supporting Coaches to Support Athletes; Development and Assessment of MHE Resources

The work within Chapter 3 provided key insights into the perspectives of footballers that their coach lacked the knowledge to engage them in conversation or support them in any capacity. Coaches supported this finding with a perceived lack of knowledge and want for further education (Chapter 4). These findings propelled the demand for a focus on this education, in order to ensure this thesis provided a practical application and outcome. Thus, the fulfilment of this need was documented within Chapters 5 and 6 of this thesis. Chapter 5 found a design-thinking approach to the development of menstrual health resources targeted to football coaches highlighted several inclusion factors identified by stakeholders in the women and girls' game. Namely, the critical need for practical examples and actionable outcomes to ensure coaches engage with the work but have a clear toolkit to utilise and ensure they are not overwhelmed by the role they perceive they play. This finding agrees with previous work by (Clarke, Govus and Donaldson, 2021), and outlined in a review by McGawley and colleagues (McGawley *et al.*, 2023) through the

requirement of fulfilling functional, interactive and critical literacy needs. The inclusion of players within the education to provide opportunities to practice discussion and improve comfort of coaches was deemed a valuable exercise, with future suggestions being to involve coaches who potentially integrate support strategies frequently within their practice, to allow for an understanding of what may be considered “gold-standard” within the practical environment. There remains discourse on what this may actually look like and remains a point of contention about what strategies may need put in place to ensure athletes feel supported and that they can manage their MC alongside their training or match play. This is namely due to the mixed objective evidence linking MC phase to markers of performance (McNulty *et al.*, 2020; Meignié *et al.*, 2021), or injury risk (Martin *et al.*, 2021; MacMillan *et al.*, 2024). Systematic reviews continually highlight the volume of low-quality evidence within the literature, due to methodological inconsistencies. Academics have since worked to provide clear protocols to ensure quality and consistency of research improves (Janse De Jonge, Thompson and Han, 2019; Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021, 2024). Despite the focus of practical outcomes, however, findings from Chapter 6 found most responses relating to comfort in knowledge did not significantly improve following a 4-week education intervention. One response which did significantly improve was coaches’ confidence in knowing what to do if their athletes were struggling with their MC. This is a critical finding and alone highlights the significance of performing such work, and the format of which education is conducted.

It is important to acknowledge the pilot nature of the work performed in Chapter 6, and as outlined in the chapter previous, these findings allow feedback to continually develop the model and provide reflection to allow for iterations and adaptations. The lack of improvement of total knowledge regarding menstrual health was in contrast to that found in recent work in a greater population within Australian sport (Clarke *et al.*, 2024). Lesson aims and outcomes between both education interventions followed a similar structure, with the work of Clarke *et al.* (2024) being longer in duration, with a similar four week ‘taught’ block (albeit 30-minutes longer in each lesson), however with the addition of additional online resources for a further four weeks to allow for coach practice and reflection. However, this knowledge was found not to be retained 6-months post intervention, highlighting the potential need for ongoing learning and skill development.

Furthermore, the need for a universal questionnaire to assess knowledge within sport would allow valid comparisons between such interventions.

From an applied perspective, it is important to consider that athletes may not wish to discuss their menstrual experiences with their coach, and the often referenced ‘support strategies’ may not be required for some, which must be respected by sporting bodies. Some athletes may also wish this to be through other means, such as through MC-tracking apps to avoid in-person discussion. MC-tracking often has mixed evidence; Verrier, Knight and Brown (2024) interviewed 12 elite rugby players who considered the use of tracking apps to be beneficial in increasing conversation between coach and athlete, or to improve their own knowledge and understanding of their cycle. Work within football, however, sees players considering the use of sharing tracking information within the club to be unnecessary due to the lack of practical outcomes as a result of them inputting potentially sensitive information (McHaffie *et al.*, 2022). Support may purely be in the form of recognising the player is struggling, referenced by players themselves in Chapter 5, and may benefit situations such as acknowledging information placed into tracking apps to ensure players feel heard. However, this requires sporting organisations to have clear protocols for referral services, either in house through club doctors, or in instances where this is not possible such as adolescent or amateur football, external services including GPs. This may also influence who views any information sent by players; tracking apps should only be utilised in environments where there is a clear knowledge and understanding of those collecting the information (Carmichael *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, the discussion at youth level may be solely between coach and parents if any potential impacting factors have been noticed by the coach.

To conclude, findings from Chapter 5 and 6 highlight the usefulness of coach education in improving coach confidence in supporting players in regard to their MC experiences, despite the lack of significance in total knowledge following a 4-week intervention. Overall, it was considered important for coach education to be concise, clear and include the practical content to support players in managing their MC within a performance environment.

7.4 Significance of Research

The findings of this thesis hold several critical implications for both the academic understanding and the practical landscape within football regarding the link between the MC, sporting performance, and athlete support. Firstly, the work performed within Chapter 3 highlights the importance of age-related variations in football players experiences within the sport. This revealed that whilst adults and adolescents may have similar menstrual profiles or characteristics, considering the age of an athlete is crucial when developing support protocols within sport. This is firstly due to the finding that there was a significant association between athlete age and the perceived impact of the MC to sporting performance. This study was the first within the literature to document this association, contributing the insight to the field to consider adolescent individuals when developing club, or sport specific resources to target education or support. Secondly, the lack of communication on MC experiences was identified, particularly from adolescents, suggesting a discomfort in discussing menstrual health within both home and sport. This led to limited support from coaches, teammates and medical professionals, thus potentially leaving girls without the necessary guidance to manage menstrual health challenges. Thus, the inclusion of age-specific considerations is required when designing both the content and delivery of menstrual health support practices.

The findings from the first study in this thesis highlights the importance of holistic support frameworks that address health, wellbeing and performance within sport. This is particularly crucial as players may not have safe spaces within their home environment to receive appropriate support for their MC experiences. This requires a shift in the culture of sport to facilitate such programmes or frameworks and ensure those delivering it have the confidence and comfort to do so. This was reiterated within Chapter 4 of this thesis, where coaches of the women and girls' game had a limited awareness of the MC, which they perceived to be due to the limited visibility of information within society, and thus sport. The need for education of those within supportive roles was widely recognised by players and coaches within Chapters 3,4,5 and 6. This may involve a wider structure involving National Governing Bodies to set clear requirements, reiterated within Chapters 4 and 5. It is advised, however, no matter the context of where this education is delivered, it be practical in nature, considering the role the coach may have to play within training and matches.

Finally, the need for education highlighted within this thesis was fulfilled by the creation and delivery of education resources following a design-thinking protocol, piloted within women and girls' football coaches. Documenting the process of coach education aids the collaboration between researchers to develop suitable sport-specific frameworks and allow comparison of findings. The findings that following a 4-week education intervention, total knowledge did not improve, whilst perceived knowledge and comfort did highlight the importance of performing such work within sport. Ensuring this knowledge is not misguided and thus impact player support through misconceptions or misinformation is critical. However, it is also crucial to advise those within sport that this should not be a singular event and should fit into a wider framework for developing support within sport.

7.5 Practical Recommendations

When considering the practical applications of this work, the audience must be considered and their role in improving the landscape of menstrual support within sport. Firstly, the importance of involvement from senior level has been addressed throughout this thesis. This includes NGBs establishing clear sport-wide guidelines regarding education strategies, and mandating minimum education standards across coaches and players. Key policy makers are required to invest in this process, through both the time dedicated to this education process, and in the resources required throughout. This education must be a continual process, and not a one-off box ticking exercise. This can be established through multi-disciplinary coach involvement in development stages, revisited regularly. Sporting bodies should therefore consider the role they wish coaches to have within this, the level of responsibility in dealing with athletes and the accessibility to medical professionals within sport to collaborate on these processes. Furthermore, as mentioned in Chapters 5 and 6, this must continually evolve to deal with the changing landscape of the game, and the available research. The education must target not only key knowledge pieces regarding menstrual health, but practical support strategies including referral processes, and help in conversation with players. For players, being involved in this process may ensure coaches understand preferences for support.

This investment must continue down to club level, where visibility of discussion must continue to improve comfort within both coaches and players. This is through clear signage throughout the club, and period management products clearly available, which senior management at club-level should implement. For coaches, this thesis highlights a number of practical strategies to consider. Firstly, attending education and being actively involved in this process ensures basic knowledge is achieved. This includes the understanding of the individualised nature of MC characteristics, experiences and perceptions, plus some wider age-specific considerations. The need for clear communication and comfort in communication is required to encourage and hold conversation with players, even as an acknowledgement and recognition, rather than within a guidance capacity. Therefore, the education provided must be revisited, and practiced regularly to ensure a coach will feel comfortable when a player does approach them.

7.6 Limitations

Whilst this thesis makes several contributions to the field, there are a number of limitations within the work. Whilst each chapter references the specific limitations within the data collection process and findings, there are further considerations when understanding the thesis in the context it was produced. These limitations will help to drive the direction of future research within the topic.

7.3.3.1 Sample Sizes and Generalisation of Findings

Firstly, due to the author's position of research, with a studentship funding the period of study and thus the authors' place of work alongside research, this limited the sample size to the homogenous samples outlined throughout each chapter. This remained a challenge throughout the work due to the limited pool, and voluntary capacity of the work performed. This is especially true as this work was performed in-season and may impact willingness to participate due to the focus on the football schedule. This therefore impacts the ability to generalise these findings due to the collection within one club within Scotland. Whilst this is considered an elite organisation which competes at European level, findings may not be indicative of other clubs, countries or cultures. This is also considered true of those within the academy set up of the club. It is important to note that coaches involved in the youth development of the club were not employed in a full-time capacity, whereas those working at the elite first-team were. This may therefore influence the knowledge and comfort

of participants, due to the time spent in the environment. However, the part-time coach allows understanding of what will be a more commonplace structure at youth and grassroots level.

7.3.3.2 Self-reported information

The studies presented within this thesis primarily focus on the self-reported experiences and perceptions of athletes and coaches. While this approach offers valuable insights into the experiences, perceptions and management of MCs, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of the data collected. The qualitative, but more importantly, quantitative data summarising athletes MC characteristics was self-reported. This approach may induce errors, as athletes may not always provide accurate responses due to recall bias, or as reported within the work, discomfort of the topic due to the visibility of discussion. All data was also collected in a singular snapshot event, and thus capturing any longitudinal variability of participants MC. This includes the potential for data to be collected at any point within the participants MC and introduce recall bias due to their current MC status. There remains an emerging priority within the literature for ‘gold-standard’ practice for obtaining objective data on ovulation and phase-based calculations, which are essential in ensuring this information is valid and reliable to draw conclusions (Elliot-Sale *et al.*, 2021). Whilst achieving objective data was often not the primary aim behind the work performed, it is important to acknowledge the significant focus of advancing our understanding of the physiological underpinnings of the MC, the individual nature, and the response within sport.

7.6 Future Work

Previous recommendations for future work were identified within Chapters 3 to 6, however three key considerations were identified within this chapter to advance the research within this field. The inclusion of adolescents within this work was a notable strength, contributing to the novel insights within this thesis. However, with a lack of comparative data within football few conclusions can be drawn as to the youth experiences and perceptions. Expanding this work is a crucial next step to ensuring youth athletes are understood and support structures can target needs effectively. This could involve the further segmentation of participants by age categories, pubertal stages, or footballing squads to understand if the needs of adolescent athletes vary as they mature. Furthermore, the inclusion of pre-menarcheal players was also a worthwhile point of note within

this study. Again, ensuring their voices are heard is valuable to understand the factors which shape the understanding and perception of menstruation. This also allows further exploration of the potential societal expectations, media representations, and cultural narrations which may influence the mindset of young women. This not only improves current understanding but also highlights the need for early education to address any potential influences identified, thus hopefully alleviating future barriers to participation within sport.

As discussed, the lack of validated testing to support the MC characteristics self-reported information is a key focus for future research, with emerging evidence showcasing methodologies to guide practice within research and considering the practicalities within sport. With coaches identified to be overwhelmed with the mixed evidence available, ensuring such protocols are employed within sport in practical, simple formats are crucial to ensure engagement and endorsement from sporting organisations. However, it is important this information be used in conjunction with each other to ensure a balanced consideration of the scientific evidence and physiological underpinnings of MC characteristics, but also of individual experiences and impacts noted within daily home environments, and within sporting capacities. Upskilling sporting practitioners, including doctors, physiotherapists, sport scientists and coaches on the use of data would then allow for tailored approaches for athletes.

Lastly, ensuring research utilising means to assess knowledge is a crucial consideration for future research within the field. This includes validated questionnaires or other data collection methods for objective and self-reported data within sport. This thesis highlighted an inability to compare key findings due to the varying approach utilised throughout the collection and analysis. This is with the recognition adaptations may be required to employ sport-specific lines of questioning, or to consider the audience (e.g. athletes, coaches etc), but having a working version to allow for wider conclusions to be drawn would benefit academics, practitioners, and organisations to target key findings and create actionable outcomes.

7.7 Conclusions

Previous understanding within sport has drawn the conclusions that female athletes commonly perceive to be affected by their MC within both daily life and wellbeing, and within performance parameters (McNulty *et al.*, 2023; Oester *et al.*, 2024). This thesis has studied the effects of the MC and subsequent symptoms both within and outwith a sporting environment, firstly within both elite and adolescent football players, and then within coaches of the women and girls' game, before targeting identified limitations within their knowledge and experiences through education programmes. Chapter 3 provided the first evidence within football separating elite adult athletes to adolescent players in the quest for understanding MC experiences and perceptions. This work demonstrated the understanding that at present, age influences the perception of the MC impacting football performance may provide some positive light on the increased visibility of topics surrounding menstruation within sport and society in general, contributing to changes in policy and club workings. However, the limited communication of adolescents to convey their MC experiences within their personal life and throughout their sporting involvement demonstrates the taboos or awkwardness still present. Challenges in communication within sport were often considered to be influenced by the coach, in both the perceived knowledge from players, but the relationship they share and the gender. Further work expanded upon this support role, with coaches' identifying the limited knowledge and understanding of menstrual health topics, recognising the need for practical advice to ensure athletes can recognise a safe space within sport to share their experiences (Chapter 4). Chapter 5 was the first of its kind to document the creation of targeted resources based on findings throughout the thesis and throughout collaborative processes to work towards relevant, appropriate education tackling identified gaps in knowledge, understanding and support. Finally, Chapter 6 found that whilst markers of total knowledge of football coaches did not significantly improve following a MHE intervention, key markers of confidence in support significantly improved, and evaluation exercises highlighted the worthwhile use of education to improve comfort in communication, and setting cultures within sport where athletes have clear support.

In conclusion, this PhD not only reaffirms previous findings that adult and adolescent athletes perceive their sporting performance is impacted because of their MC, but also highlights the barriers faced by athletes and coaches alike on communicating on such matters within a football environment. This thesis contributes further to these findings by working to provide a

solution to the limited knowledge and comfort in communication through the creation of education programmes, deemed to be worthwhile in improving the landscape within sport of a normalised discussion on female athlete health topics. Ultimately, this PhD makes a significant contribution to advancing menstrual health awareness in football and addresses challenges identified by offering practical and meaningful solutions to the persistent lack of knowledge and discomfort surrounding menstrual health, thus paving the way for a more inclusive and progressive sporting culture.

8. References

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9. Appendices

Appendix A. Chapter 3: Player Questionnaire regarding MC characteristics, experiences and perceptions upon performance.

We are interested in finding out the lived experience of menstruation in female athletes, and the perceptions and attitudes they have towards their menstruation in sport. At present, this is an extremely under-researched area, and this study aims to actively benefit women and girls in sport by increasing the research knowledge and informing applied practice in this area. The research team consists of Julia Donnelly, Dr. Laura Forrest at the University of the West of Scotland and Dr Andy White at Glasgow City F.C. When answering the questions, please select the response that best reflects your personal opinion, attitude or lived experience, using the rating scale provided. When asked to provide a written answer in your own words, please describe using as much detail as you are willing and able to provide, in as many words as you deem fit. You will be required to answer all questions before moving on to the next section in the questionnaire, but if you do not wish to provide an answer to a question, please select 'Other' as your answer choice and write 'N/A' when prompted. If the question requires a written answer, please write 'N/A' within the comment box. Please be reminded that you are under no obligation to finish this questionnaire, and you are free to stop or withdraw at any point. You may also save and continue this questionnaire at a later date, there is no requirement to complete it in one sitting. If you have any questions about the study, or would like any further information, please contact the principal researcher Julia Donnelly: [REDACTED], or research project supervisor: Dr. Laura Forrest: [REDACTED].

Please copy the link below into your browser window to access the Participant Information Sheet. This should already have been sent to you via email. Once you have read the sheet, saved and printed a copy for your future reference, please read the following statement and tick the box to

indicate you consent to take part in the study, and wish to access the questionnaire. Link to Participant Information Sheet: [insert link]

1. I have read the information sheet provided and I am happy to participate. I understand that by completing and returning this questionnaire I am consenting to be part of this research study and for my data to be used as described in the information sheet provided.

Section 1: Participant Information

What age are you?

What squad are you in?

1. U13
2. U14
3. U15
4. U16
5. U18
6. U19
7. 1st Team

Section 2: Menstrual Cycle

Have you started menstruation? Menstruation is the routine vaginal bleeding which occurs as part of a women's menstrual cycle. This can also be known as menses, or period)

1. Yes
2. No

What do you think it will be like to have a period? Please explain, in your own words:

Do you think there will be positive things about having a period?

1. Yes
2. No

Do you think there will be negative things about having a period?

1. Yes
2. No

Do you think having a period will help your sporting performance?

1. Yes
2. No

Do you think having a period will have a negative impact on your sporting performance?

1. Yes
2. No

Section 3: Knowledge and Understanding

What age do you think females typically get their first period? Please select one option:

1. 9-10
2. 10-11
3. 11-12
4. 12-13
5. 13-14
6. 14-15
7. 15-16
8. 16-17
9. 17-18
10. Unsure

How long does the average period (i.e. how long you bleed) last?

1. 1-2days
2. 3-4days
3. 5-6days
4. 7-8days
5. 9-10days
6. Unsure

How long does the average menstrual cycle last? This is the duration of time between the first day of your period (Day 1 of bleeding) and the first day of your next period (Day 1 of bleeding).

1. 12-19 days
2. 20-27 days
3. 28-35 days
4. 36-43 days
5. 44-51 days
6. Unsure

At what age should you seek medical advice (e.g. go to your doctor) if you have not started your period?

1. 13
2. 14
3. 15
4. 16
5. 17
6. 18
7. 19
8. 20
9. Unsure

Can you name symptoms which may be due to the menstrual cycle?

1. Yes
2. No

Have you heard of PMS?

1. Yes
2. No

Do you know what PMS stands for?

1. Yes
2. No

What does PMS stand for?

What do you know about PMS?

A large, empty rectangular box with a black border, intended for the user to provide their answer to the question about PMS.

Please provide any methods you know about, or have heard about that can help manage menstrual cycle related symptoms (i.e. help reduce the symptoms or make you feel better)? If you are not aware of any, please answer 'Unsure'.

A large, empty rectangular box with a black border, intended for the user to provide their answer regarding methods to manage menstrual cycle symptoms.

Occasionally, females may miss one or more periods. Please provide reasons as to why a girl/women may miss her period. If you are not aware of any, please answer 'Unsure'.

A large, empty rectangular box with a black border, intended for the user to provide their answer regarding reasons for missed periods.

Can you please name period (sanitary) products you know or are aware of: If you are not aware of any, please answer 'Unsure'.

Can you please name all the methods of hormonal contraception you know or are aware of: If you are not aware of any, please answer 'Unsure'.

For the methods of hormonal contraception, you know or are aware of, can you please explain how these may be taken and/ or located in the body: If you are not aware of any, please answer 'Unsure'.

Please provide any reasons you can think of as to why women may choose to use hormonal contraception: If you are not aware of any, please answer 'Unsure'.

Where do you learn or gain information regarding the menstrual cycle? Please select all that apply

- 1. Friends
- 2. Mother
- 3. Sister
- 4. Other Family Members
- 5. School
- 6. GP/Nurse
- 7. Internet
- 8. Other: Where else do you learn your information _____

Section 4: Personal Menstrual Cycle Information

What was your approximate age at which you experienced your first period?

On average, what is the length of your menstrual cycle? This is the duration of time between the first day of your period (Day 1 of Bleeding) and the first day of your next period (Day 1 of Bleeding). Range= 10-90+days

On average, how many days do you bleed for each month? Range=1-14+ days

Does the time between one period and your next period change each time?

1. Yes
2. Somewhat
3. No

Please state how many days (on average) your menstrual cycle length may vary by.

Have you ever experienced missing a period for a duration of 90days in a row or more? This is called Amenorrhoea

1. Yes
2. No

Are you currently experiencing amenorrhoea? Please note: If you are currently experiencing amenorrhoea, it is advisable that you speak to a doctor or other medical professional as soon as possible.

1. Yes
2. No

Do you know the reason as to why you experienced/are currently experiencing amenorrhoea?

1. Yes
2. No

Please select one option from the list below that you feel best describes your menstrual bleeding experience: My bleeding is...

1. Very Heavy
2. Heavy
3. Moderate
4. Light
5. Very Light

What sanitary protection do you use? Select all that apply:

1. Tampons
2. Sanitary Towels/Pads (Reusable/Disposable)
3. Menstrual Cups (e.g. Moon Cups)
4. Menstrual Underwear (e.g. Modibodi)
5. Menstrual Discs (e.g. FLEX)
6. Other: Please state what sanitary protection you use _____

Do you ever use more than one sanitary protection products at a time (e.g. combining tampons and sanitary towels)?

1. Yes
2. Sometimes
3. No

In your own words, please describe any experiences whilst training or competing in your sport where you felt like you had to hide or conceal the fact that you were menstruating/bleeding:

In your own words, please describe any experiences whilst training or competing in your sport where you felt like you behaved, dressed, spoke or acted in a way with the intention of concealing your menstruation:

Section 5: Personal Hormonal Contraception

Do you currently use any type of Hormonal Contraception? Hormonal contraceptives (e.g. the pill, the patch, injections/implant etc.) contain a small amount of estrogen and/or progestin. These hormones work to inhibit the body's natural cyclical hormones, so as to prevent pregnancy.

1. Yes
2. Sometimes
3. I have only used it in the past and do not currently use it
4. No

What type of hormonal contraception do you use? Please select all that apply

1. Oral contraceptive (e.g. contraceptive pill)
2. Implant
3. Contraceptive injections
4. Intrauterine device/non-copper coil
5. Contraceptive patch
6. Other: Please specify the type and name of the hormonal contraception you use

What type of hormonal contraception have you used in the past? Please select all that apply

1. Oral contraceptive (e.g. contraceptive pill)
2. Implant
3. Contraceptive injections
4. Intrauterine device/coil
5. Contraceptive patch
6. Other: Please specify the type and name of hormonal contraceptive you have used in the past _____

Why did you choose the hormonal contraceptive method you are currently using? Please select all that apply

1. Contraception/birth control
2. Period/PMS symptom management
3. To regulate my menstrual cycle

4. To manipulate my period duration
 5. To delay or stop my period in relation to an important event (e.g. competition)
 6. For dermatological reasons (e.g. to help with acne)
 7. Other: Please specify why you chose to use your current hormonal contraceptive method
-

Why did you choose the hormonal contraceptive method you previously used? Please select all that apply

1. Contraception/birth control
 2. Period/PMS symptom management
 3. To regulate my menstrual cycle
 4. To manipulate my period duration
 5. To delay or stop my period in relation to an important event (e.g. competition)
 6. For dermatological reasons (e.g. to help with acne)
 7. Other: Please specify why you chose to use your prior hormonal contraceptive method
-

Section 6: Symptoms

Do you experience symptoms in relation to your menstrual cycle?

1. Yes
2. Sometimes
3. No

Looking at the list of common menstrual cycle symptoms below, for every symptom you experience, please tick the box to indicate how often you experience it. For the purposes of this study, migraines have been given the following definition: A migraine is usually a moderate or severe headache felt as a throbbing pain on one side of the head. Many people also have symptoms such as feeling sick, being sick and increased sensitivity to light or sound. Further advice on migraines can be found at: <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/migraine/>

	Every month	Most months	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	I'm unsure if I have experienced this symptom
Abdominal pain/cramps	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Backache	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Headache	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Migraines	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Nausea	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Vomiting	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Bloating	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Weight gain	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Water retention	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Tiredness/Fatigue	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lack of co-ordination	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Sleep disturbances	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Hot flushes/Sweating	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Breast tenderness	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Upset stomach (changes to normal bowel habits)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Appetite disturbances	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Flooding/leaking	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Blood clots	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Mood changes/Mood swings	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Feeling irritable/angry	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Feeling sad/teary	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Feeling worried/anxious	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Feeling distracted	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Reduced ability to concentrate	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lack of motivation	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lack of focus	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Reduced sex drive	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Increased sex drive	<input type="checkbox"/>					
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Please use the space below to name any other symptoms you experience not listed above, and how frequently you experience them. If you do not experience symptoms outside of those listed above, please write 'N/A' in the space below.

Looking at the list of common menstrual cycle symptoms below, for every symptom you experience, please tick the box to indicate how severe you perceive it to be, with regards to your own lived experience.

	Not at all	Very mild	Mild	Average	Severe	Very severe	I'm unsure if I've experienced this symptom
Abdominal pain/cramps	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Backache	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Headache	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Migraines	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Nausea	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Vomiting	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Bloating	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Weight gain	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Water retention	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Tiredness/Fatigue	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Lack of co-ordination	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Sleep disturbances	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Hot flushes/Sweating	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Breast tenderness	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Upset stomach (changes to normal bowel habits)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Appetite disturbances	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Flooding/leaking	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Blood clots	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Mood changes/Mood swings	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Feeling irritable/angry	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Feeling sad/teary	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Feeling worried/anxious	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Feeling distracted	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Reduced ability to concentrate	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Lack of motivation	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Lack of focus	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Reduced sex drive	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Increased sex drive	<input type="checkbox"/>						

Please use the space below to name any other symptoms you experience not listed above, and how severe you find them. If you do not experience symptoms outside of those listed above, please write 'N/A' in the space below.

Do you think your menstrual cycle impacts your performance?

1. Yes
2. No

Please explain, in your own words, why you answered yes/no:

Do you take any medication (excluding hormonal contraception) to control your menstrual cycle symptoms? E.g. Prescribed medication, painkillers, supplements etc.

1. Yes
2. Sometimes
3. No

Do you use any non-medication-based methods to control your menstrual cycle symptoms? E.g. Hot water bottles/cold patches, physical exercises, eating comfort foods, meditation/relaxation exercises, homeopathy etc.

1. Yes
2. Sometimes
3. No

Section 7: Activity Levels

Do you ever avoid, reduce or change your exercise/sporting habits during your period?

1. Yes
2. Sometimes

3. No

Do you track your menstrual cycle and/or menstrual symptoms in relation to your sporting performance, by using a period-tracking app or similar software?

1. Yes
2. Sometimes
3. No

Please state the reason(s) you use a period-tracking app or similar software

Section 8: Menstrual Communication

Where do you go to find and access information about your menstrual cycle? Please select all that apply

1. Internet
2. Books
3. Journal articles
4. Social Media
5. Health professionals
6. Friends and family
7. Period-tracking Apps
8. Other: Please specify where you access information about your menstrual cycle

Have you ever spoken to a fellow player about your menstrual cycle symptoms?

1. Yes
2. No

Have you ever spoken to a doctor or other medical/health professional about your menstrual cycle symptoms?

1. Yes
2. No
3. I do not experience menstrual cycle symptoms

Who would you usually approach to discuss any issues you may experience relating to your menstrual cycle in your sport? Please select all that apply

1. GP (General Practitioner)
2. Sports Doctor
3. Physiotherapist
4. Coach
5. Fellow athletes/teammates
6. Physiologist
7. Sports Psychologist
8. Clinical Psychologist
9. Nutritionist
10. Sport Scientist
11. Friends and family
12. No-one
13. Other: Please state your answer _____

Please select the people you would feel comfortable approaching the following people to talk about your menstrual cycle, and the effect it may have on your ability to perform in your sport.

Please select all that apply

1. GP (General Practitioner)
2. Sports Doctor
3. Physiotherapist
4. Coach
5. Fellow athletes/teammates
6. Physiologist
7. Sports Psychologist
8. Clinical Psychologist
9. Nutritionist
10. Sport Scientist
11. Friends and family
12. No-one
13. Other: Please state your answer _____

In your own words, please describe any reason(s) as to why you may not feel comfortable approaching someone from the above list to talk about your menstrual cycle

Which of the following characteristics may make you more likely to approach someone, in order to talk about your menstrual cycle? Please select all that apply

1. They are female
2. They are male
3. They also experience menstruation themselves

4. They have a lot of medical, physiological and/or psychological knowledge and understanding of how menstruation may affect sporting performance
5. I know them well/I have known them for a long time
6. I do not know them well/I have known them for a short time
7. They will be more likely to reduce what is expected of me at training/competitions
8. They will be more likely to push me and encourage me to carry on, despite difficulties
9. They have a lot of knowledge and experience in my sport
10. They help me feel emotionally comforted
11. They will provide me with problem-solving solutions
12. They have a similar religious/cultural background to me
13. Other: Please state your answer _____

Does the gender of your coach (if they are a man or a woman) affect how comfortable you feel talking to them about your period and its effect on your ability to perform in your sport?

1. Yes
2. Somewhat
3. No

How happy or satisfied are you with the current resources, help or support you receive related to your menstrual cycle, from other people supporting you in your sport?

	Extreme ly happy and satisfied	Very happy and satisfied	Somewh at happy and satisfied	Neither happy nor satisfied	Somewh at unhappy and unsatisfi ed	Very unhappy and unsatisfi ed	Extreme ly unhappy and unsatisfi ed
I feel...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Please explain in your own words, your reason(s) for the answer you selected for the previous question

Have you experienced situations in which you found it challenging to communicate or were not able to communicate to others that you were menstruating?

1. Yes
2. Sometimes
3. No

Please describe experiences in which you found it challenging to communicate or were not able to communicate to others that you were menstruating. How did this impact upon your performance and well-being?

In your own words, please describe any experiences whilst training or competing in your sport where you felt you found it difficult or were unable to communicate to others that you were menstruating:

In your own words, please explain what could be improved in women's football to recognize the impact of menstruation on performance:

Thank you for completing this questionnaire! These questionnaires will help to explore this research area in greater detail and may influence future menstruation-related policy and protocol, to the benefit of women, girls and menstruating people in sport in the UK. Your role as a participant in this questionnaire will directly inform the continuing research and applied knowledge and understanding of menstruation in sport. Club and team-level findings will be explained by Julia in the following months. In the meantime, please contact Julia if you have any questions/ would like to discuss any answers.

Appendix B. Chapter 3: Symptom frequency reported by adults and adolescents who were naturally menstruating

<i>Symptom</i>	Adolescents		Adults	
	Naturally Menstruating (n)	Naturally Menstruating (%)	Naturally Menstruating (n)	Naturally Menstruating (%)
<i>Do you experience symptoms/ side effects?</i>				
<i>Yes</i>	38	62.3	22	73.3
<i>Sometimes</i>	15	24.6	6	20.0
<i>No</i>	8	13.1	2	6.7
<i>Abdominal pain/cramps</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	23	50.0	17	63.0
<i>Most months</i>	9	19.6	4	14.8
<i>Sometimes</i>	9	19.6	5	18.5
<i>Rarely</i>	4	8.7	1	3.7
<i>Never</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Appetite disturbances</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	5	10.9	6	22.2
<i>Most months</i>	10	21.7	7	25.9
<i>Sometimes</i>	16	34.8	5	18.5
<i>Rarely</i>	4	8.7	3	11.1
<i>Never</i>	11	23.9	6	22.2
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Backache</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	5	10.9	7	25.9
<i>Most months</i>	4	8.7	5	18.5
<i>Sometimes</i>	14	30.4	6	22.2
<i>Rarely</i>	7	15.2	7	25.9
<i>Never</i>	16	34.8	2	7.4
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Bloating</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	11	23.9	13	48.2

<i>Most months</i>	9	19.6	6	22.2
<i>Sometimes</i>	15	32.6	6	22.2
<i>Rarely</i>	4	8.7	0	0.0
<i>Never</i>	7	15.2	2	7.4
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Blood clots</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	6	13.0	1	3.7
<i>Most months</i>	5	10.9	4	14.8
<i>Sometimes</i>	5	10.9	6	22.2
<i>Rarely</i>	11	23.9	3	11.1
<i>Never</i>	17	37.0	12	44.4
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	2	4.4	1	3.7
<i>Breast tenderness</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	5	10.9	10	37.0
<i>Most months</i>	6	13.0	8	29.6
<i>Sometimes</i>	9	19.6	2	7.4
<i>Rarely</i>	12	26.1	2	7.4
<i>Never</i>	14	30.4	4	14.8
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7
<i>Feeling distracted</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	7	15.2	4	14.8
<i>Most months</i>	10	21.7	8	29.6
<i>Sometimes</i>	13	28.3	8	29.6
<i>Rarely</i>	5	10.9	5	18.5
<i>Never</i>	11	23.9	2	7.4
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Feeling irritable/angry</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	15	32.6	9	33.3
<i>Most months</i>	13	28.3	8	29.6
<i>Sometimes</i>	11	23.9	7	25.9
<i>Rarely</i>	6	13.0	2	7.4
<i>Never</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0

<i>Feeling sad/teary</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	14	30.4	11	40.7
<i>Most months</i>	9	19.6	9	33.3
<i>Sometimes</i>	12	26.1	6	22.2
<i>Rarely</i>	5	10.9	0	0.0
<i>Never</i>	6	13.0	1	3.7
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Feeling worried/anxious</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	12	26.1	7	25.9
<i>Most months</i>	7	15.2	8	29.6
<i>Sometimes</i>	10	21.7	9	33.3
<i>Rarely</i>	8	17.4	1	3.7
<i>Never</i>	9	19.6	2	7.4
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Flooding/leaking</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	3	6.5	2	7.4
<i>Most months</i>	8	17.4	5	18.5
<i>Sometimes</i>	10	21.7	8	29.6
<i>Rarely</i>	11	23.9	7	25.9
<i>Never</i>	12	26.1	5	18.5
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	2	4.4	0	0.0
<i>Headache</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	11	23.9	4	14.8
<i>Most months</i>	10	21.7	3	11.1
<i>Sometimes</i>	11	23.9	4	14.8
<i>Rarely</i>	8	17.4	12	44.4
<i>Never</i>	6	13.0	4	14.8
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Hot flushes/Sweating</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	3	6.5	3	11.1
<i>Most months</i>	5	10.9	5	18.5
<i>Sometimes</i>	13	28.3	11	40.7
<i>Rarely</i>	9	19.6	6	22.2

<i>Never</i>	15	32.6	2	7.4
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Increased sex drive</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7
<i>Most months</i>	0	0.0	5	18.5
<i>Sometimes</i>	3	6.5	15	55.6
<i>Rarely</i>	2	4.4	3	11.1
<i>Never</i>	21	45.7	1	3.7
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	20	43.5	2	7.4
<i>Lack of co-ordination</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	3	6.5	3	11.1
<i>Most months</i>	3	6.5	3	11.1
<i>Sometimes</i>	12	26.1	6	22.2
<i>Rarely</i>	9	19.6	6	22.2
<i>Never</i>	18	39.1	7	25.9
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	1	2.2	2	7.4
<i>Lack of focus</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	3	6.5	1	3.7
<i>Most months</i>	12	26.1	8	29.6
<i>Sometimes</i>	14	30.4	11	40.7
<i>Rarely</i>	5	10.9	4	14.8
<i>Never</i>	12	26.1	3	11.1
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Lack of motivation</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	6	13.0	2	7.4
<i>Most months</i>	11	23.9	10	37.0
<i>Sometimes</i>	16	34.8	11	40.7
<i>Rarely</i>	6	13.0	2	7.4
<i>Never</i>	7	15.2	2	7.4
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Migraines</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	3	6.5	1	3.7
<i>Most months</i>	3	6.5	2	7.4

<i>Sometimes</i>	12	26.1	1	3.7
<i>Rarely</i>	11	23.9	9	33.3
<i>Never</i>	16	34.8	13	48.2
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
<i>Mood changes/Mood swings</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	14	30.4	8	29.6
<i>Most months</i>	18	39.1	13	48.2
<i>Sometimes</i>	7	15.2	5	18.5
<i>Rarely</i>	5	10.9	1	3.7
<i>Never</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Nausea</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	3	6.5	2	7.4
<i>Most months</i>	5	10.9	2	7.4
<i>Sometimes</i>	12	26.1	5	18.5
<i>Rarely</i>	12	26.1	9	33.3
<i>Never</i>	14	30.4	9	33.3
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Reduced ability to concentrate</i>				
<i>Every month</i>				
<i>Most months</i>	9	19.6	1	3.7
<i>Sometimes</i>	11	23.9	9	33.3
<i>Rarely</i>	9	19.6	11	40.7
<i>Never</i>	5	10.9	5	18.5
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	12	26.1	1	3.7
	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Reduced sex drive</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Most months</i>	1	2.2	3	11.1
<i>Sometimes</i>	3	6.5	12	44.4
<i>Rarely</i>	2	4.4	6	22.2
<i>Never</i>	18	39.1	4	14.8
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	21	45.7	2	7.4

<i>Sleep disturbances</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	7	15.2	5	18.5
<i>Most months</i>	7	15.2	5	18.5
<i>Sometimes</i>	7	15.2	13	48.2
<i>Rarely</i>	13	28.3	1	3.7
<i>Never</i>	10	21.7	2	7.42
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	2	4.4	1	3.7
<i>Tiredness/Fatigue</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	22	47.8	14	51.9
<i>Most months</i>	14	30.4	8	29.6
<i>Sometimes</i>	7	15.2	5	18.5
<i>Rarely</i>	2	4.4	0	0.0
<i>Never</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Upset stomach (changes to normal bowel habits)</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	6	13.0	12	44.4
<i>Most months</i>	10	21.7	3	11.1
<i>Sometimes</i>	7	15.2	5	18.5
<i>Rarely</i>	13	28.3	2	7.4
<i>Never</i>	10	21.7	5	18.5
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Vomiting</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7
<i>Most months</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Sometimes</i>	3	6.5	1	3.7
<i>Rarely</i>	6	13.0	5	18.5
<i>Never</i>	36	78.3	20	74.1
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Water retention</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	3	6.5	2	7.4
<i>Most months</i>	2	4.4	10	37.0
<i>Sometimes</i>	8	17.4	7	25.9

<i>Rarely</i>	5	10.9	2	7.4
<i>Never</i>	15	32.6	4	14.8
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	13	28.3	2	7.4
<i>Weight gain</i>				
<i>Every month</i>	2	4.4	3	11.1
<i>Most months</i>	4	8.7	6	22.2
<i>Sometimes</i>	12	26.1	9	33.3
<i>Rarely</i>	6	13.0	4	14.8
<i>Never</i>	17	37.0	4	14.8
<i>Unsure if ever</i>	5	10.9	1	3.7

Appendix C. Chapter 3: Symptom severity reported by adults and adolescents who were naturally menstruating

Symptom	Adolescents		Adults	
	Naturally Menstruating (n) (n = 46)	Naturally Menstruating (%)	Naturally Menstruating (n) (n = 27)	Naturally Menstruating (%)
Abdominal pain/cramps				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	2	7.4
<i>Severe</i>	16	34.8	13	48.2
<i>Average</i>	19	41.3	7	25.9
<i>Mild</i>	6	13.0	4	14.8
<i>Very Mild</i>	3	6.5	1	3.7
<i>Not at all</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
Appetite disturbances				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Average</i>	12	26.1	12	44.4
<i>Mild</i>	10	21.7	6	22.2
<i>Very Mild</i>	9	19.6	3	11.1
<i>Not at all</i>	12	26.1	6	22.2
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
Backache				
<i>Very Severe</i>	2	4.4	2	7.4
<i>Severe</i>	3	6.5	2	7.4
<i>Average</i>	8	17.4	12	44.4
<i>Mild</i>	10	21.7	4	14.8
<i>Very Mild</i>	4	8.7	3	11.1
<i>Not at all</i>	19	41.3	4	14.8
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0

Bloating				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	5	10.9	2	7.4
<i>Average</i>	13	28.3	17	63.0
<i>Mild</i>	5	10.9	3	11.1
<i>Very Mild</i>	11	23.9	4	14.8
<i>Not at all</i>	10	21.7	1	3.7
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
Blood clots				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
<i>Average</i>	8	17.4	6	22.2
<i>Mild</i>	5	10.9	4	14.8
<i>Very Mild</i>	11	23.9	2	7.4
<i>Not at all</i>	20	43.5	13	48.2
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
Breast tenderness				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	3	6.5	6	22.2
<i>Average</i>	9	19.6	13	48.2
<i>Mild</i>	5	10.9	2	7.4
<i>Very Mild</i>	10	21.7	3	11.1
<i>Not at all</i>	17	37.0	3	11.1
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	2	4.4	0	0.0
Feeling distracted				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	6	13.0	0	0.0
<i>Average</i>	11	23.9	7	25.9
<i>Mild</i>	11	23.9	8	29.6
<i>Very Mild</i>	9	19.6	7	25.9

<i>Not at all</i>	9	19.6	4	14.8
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7
<i>Feeling irritable/angry</i>				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	12	26.1	3	11.1
<i>Average</i>	17	37.0	16	59.3
<i>Mild</i>	9	19.6	4	14.8
<i>Very Mild</i>	5	10.9	2	7.4
<i>Not at all</i>	2	4.4	2	7.4
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Feeling sad/teary</i>				
<i>Very Severe</i>	5	10.9	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	8	17.4	9	33.3
<i>Average</i>	13	28.3	13	48.2
<i>Mild</i>	8	17.4	4	14.8
<i>Very Mild</i>	6	13.0	0	0.0
<i>Not at all</i>	6	13.0	1	3.7
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Feeling worried/anxious</i>				
<i>Very Severe</i>	4	8.7	1	3.7
<i>Severe</i>	6	13.0	4	14.8
<i>Average</i>	10	21.7	10	37.0
<i>Mild</i>	10	21.7	7	25.9
<i>Very Mild</i>	7	15.2	1	3.7
<i>Not at all</i>	9	19.6	4	14.8
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Flooding/leaking</i>				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	3	6.5	2	7.4

<i>Average</i>	8	17.4	6	22.2
<i>Mild</i>	11	23.9	5	18.5
<i>Very Mild</i>	8	17.4	8	29.6
<i>Not at all</i>	14	30.4	5	18.5
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
Headache				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	11	23.9	1	3.7
<i>Average</i>	15	32.6	9	33.3
<i>Mild</i>	9	19.6	4	14.8
<i>Very Mild</i>	5	10.9	4	14.8
<i>Not at all</i>	5	10.9	9	33.3
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
Hot flushes/Sweating				
<i>Very Severe</i>	3	6.5	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	2	7.4
<i>Average</i>	5	10.9	6	22.2
<i>Mild</i>	10	21.7	6	22.2
<i>Very Mild</i>	6	13.0	5	18.5
<i>Not at all</i>	20	43.5	8	29.6
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
Increased sex drive				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7
<i>Average</i>	4	8.7	11	40.7
<i>Mild</i>	1	2.2	8	29.6
<i>Very Mild</i>	3	6.5	4	14.8
<i>Not at all</i>	18	39.1	2	7.4
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	20	43.5	1	3.7

Lack of co-ordination

<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Average</i>	6	13.0	4	14.8
<i>Mild</i>	8	17.4	5	18.5
<i>Very Mild</i>	8	17.4	5	18.5
<i>Not at all</i>	20	43.5	11	40.7
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	2	4.4	2	7.4

Lack of focus

<i>Very Severe</i>	2	4.4	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	3	6.5	0	0.0
<i>Average</i>	12	26.1	7	25.9
<i>Mild</i>	10	21.7	10	37.0
<i>Very Mild</i>	6	13.0	5	18.5
<i>Not at all</i>	12	26.1	4	14.8
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7

Lack of motivation

<i>Very Severe</i>	3	6.5	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	5	10.9	1	3.7
<i>Average</i>	12	26.1	15	55.6
<i>Mild</i>	13	28.3	6	22.2
<i>Very Mild</i>	4	8.7	3	11.1
<i>Not at all</i>	9	19.6	2	7.4
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0

Migraines

<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	6	13.0	4	14.8
<i>Average</i>	10	21.7	2	7.4
<i>Mild</i>	4	8.7	1	3.7
<i>Very Mild</i>	3	6.5	2	7.4

<i>Not at all</i>	22	47.8	18	66.7
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
Mood changes/Mood swings				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	11	23.9	1	3.7
<i>Average</i>	20	43.5	23	85.2
<i>Mild</i>	9	19.6	1	3.7
<i>Very Mild</i>	4	8.7	1	3.7
<i>Not at all</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
Nausea				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
<i>Average</i>	9	19.6	4	14.8
<i>Mild</i>	8	17.4	0	0.0
<i>Very Mild</i>	11	23.9	11	40.7
<i>Not at all</i>	15	32.6	10	37.0
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7
Reduced ability to concentrate				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	6	13.0	1	3.7
<i>Average</i>	11	23.9	7	25.9
<i>Mild</i>	11	23.9	9	33.3
<i>Very Mild</i>	8	17.4	5	18.5
<i>Not at all</i>	10	21.7	4	14.8
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7
Reduced sex drive				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0

<i>Average</i>	1	2.2	6	22.2
<i>Mild</i>	3	6.5	7	25.9
<i>Very Mild</i>	5	10.9	7	25.9
<i>Not at all</i>	18	39.1	6	22.2
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	19	41.3	1	3.7
<i>Sleep disturbances</i>				
<i>Very Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	5	10.9	2	7.4
<i>Average</i>	9	19.6	8	29.6
<i>Mild</i>	8	17.4	9	33.3
<i>Very Mild</i>	12	26.1	5	18.5
<i>Not at all</i>	10	21.7	3	11.1
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Tiredness/Fatigue</i>				
<i>Very Severe</i>	5	10.9	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	12	26.1	6	22.2
<i>Average</i>	14	30.4	16	59.3
<i>Mild</i>	8	17.4	3	11.1
<i>Very Mild</i>	2	4.4	1	3.7
<i>Not at all</i>	5	10.9	1	3.7
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Upset stomach (changes to normal bowel habits)</i>				
<i>Very Severe</i>	3	6.5	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	7	15.2	6	22.2
<i>Average</i>	7	15.2	11	40.7
<i>Mild</i>	9	19.6	3	11.1
<i>Very Mild</i>	8	17.4	1	3.7
<i>Not at all</i>	11	23.9	6	22.2

<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
Vomiting				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Average</i>	2	4.4	1	3.7
<i>Mild</i>	2	4.4	0	0.0
<i>Very Mild</i>	5	10.9	3	11.1
<i>Not at all</i>	35	76.1	23	85.2
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
Water retention				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Average</i>	5	10.9	7	25.9
<i>Mild</i>	4	8.7	8	29.6
<i>Very Mild</i>	3	6.5	6	22.2
<i>Not at all</i>	22	47.8	5	18.5
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	11	23.9	1	3.7
Weight gain				
<i>Very Severe</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Severe</i>	1	2.2	0	0.0
<i>Average</i>	10	21.7	6	22.2
<i>Mild</i>	7	15.2	7	25.9
<i>Very Mild</i>	3	6.5	7	25.9
<i>Not at all</i>	22	47.8	6	22.2
<i>I'm unsure if I have ever experienced this</i>	3	6.5	1	3.7

Appendix D. Chapter 3: Content analysis of symptom management methods

		<i>Adolescents (n = 46)</i>		<i>Adults (n = 27)</i>		
		n	%	n	%	
Medication	<i>Paracetamol</i>	19	41.3	11	40.7	
	<i>Ibuprofen</i>	18	39.1	11	40.7	
	<i>General “Painkillers”</i>	3	6.5	3	11.1	
	<i>Co-codamol</i>	1	2.2	1	3.7	
	<i>Antispasmodics</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7	
	<i>Targeted Period-Pain Medication (e.g. Feminax)</i>	2	4.4	3	11.1	
	<i>Lymecycline</i>	0	0.0	1	3.7	
	Non-medication	<i>Hot water bottle</i>	32	69.6	21	77.8
		<i>Exercise</i>	9	19.6	4	14.8
<i>Chocolate/ sweet</i>		2	4.4	2	7.4	
<i>Drinking water</i>		1	2.2	0	0.0	
<i>Drinking other liquids</i>		0	0.0	2	7.4	
<i>Warm bath</i>		2	4.4	1	3.7	
<i>Anti-inflammatory food</i>		1	2.2	1	3.7	
<i>Comfort food</i>		10	21.7	1	3.7	
<i>Nap</i>		2	4.4	3	11.1	
<i>Vitamins</i>		1	2.2	1	3.7	

Appendix E, Chapter 3: Content Analysis on participants responses to MC performance impacts.

Do you think your menstrual cycle impacts your performance?	Adolescent (n = 46)	Adult (n = 27)
YES	n	n
Concept 1: Psychological Symptoms		
<i>Reduced concentration</i>	2	2
<i>Distracted by pain</i>	3	0
<i>Worried about leaking</i>	2	2
<i>Reduced motivation</i>	5	1
<i>Less focused</i>	2	5
<i>Irritable</i>	1	1
<i>Anger</i>	2	0
<i>Less tolerable</i>	0	1
Concept 2: Energy levels		
<i>Sluggish</i>	1	0
<i>Tiredness</i>	7	4
<i>Reduced reaction time</i>	1	2
<i>Feel 'off'</i>	1	1
<i>Not as active on pitch</i>	1	0
<i>Feel heavy</i>	2	0
<i>Feel weaker</i>	1	2
<i>Less effort</i>	1	0
<i>Longer to recover</i>	0	1
<i>Fatigued</i>	0	4
<i>Can't push my body as hard</i>	0	1
Concept 3: Physical Symptoms		
<i>Stomach cramps/ sore stomach</i>	8	6
<i>Headaches</i>	3	0
<i>Sore/ heavy legs</i>	2	1
<i>Nausea</i>	2	2
<i>Uncomfortable</i>	2	1
<i>Unwell</i>	2	1
<i>Coordination</i>	2	1
<i>Feel restricted</i>	1	0
<i>Not as fast</i>	3	1
<i>Can barely move</i>	0	1
NO		
<i>I do not suffer from severe symptoms</i>	1	
<i>No change in performance</i>	2	
<i>Just get on with it as normal</i>	1	

Appendix F. Chapter 3: Comfort in communication of players, and perceived support strategies offered.

Question	Adolescents (n) (n = 61)	Adolescents (%)	Adults (n) (n = 30)	Adults (%)
<i>Who Would You Usually Approach To Discuss Any Issues You May Experience Relating To Your Menstrual Cycle In Your Sport? Please Select All That Apply</i>				
<i>GP (General Doctor)</i>	7	11.5	10	33.3
<i>Sports Doctor</i>	2	3.3	16	53.3
<i>Physiotherapist</i>	0	0.0	2	6.7
<i>Coach</i>	2	3.3	2	6.7
<i>Fellow Player</i>	14	23.0	17	56.7
<i>Physiologist</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Sports Psychologist</i>	0	0.0	1	3.3
<i>Clinical Psychologist</i>	0	0.0	0	0.0
<i>Nutritionist</i>	0	0.0	1	3.3
<i>Sport Scientist</i>	4	6.6	10	33.3
<i>Friends And Family</i>	41	67.2	15	50.0
<i>No-One</i>	10	16.4	1	3.3
<i>Please Select The People You Would Feel Comfortable Approaching The Following People To Talk About Your Menstrual Cycle, And The Effect It May Have On Your Ability To Perform In Your Sport? Please Select All That Apply</i>				
<i>GP (General Doctor)</i>	17	27.9	16	53.3
<i>Sports Doctor</i>	9	14.8	21	70.0
<i>Physiotherapist</i>	3	4.9	15	50.0
<i>Coach</i>	8	13.1	7	23.3
<i>Fellow Player</i>	20	32.8	22	73.3
<i>Physiologist</i>	2	3.3	5	16.7

<i>Sports Psychologist</i>	6	9.8	5	16.7
<i>Clinical Psychologist</i>	3	4.9	6	20.0
<i>Nutritionist</i>	5	8.2	8	26.7
<i>Sport Scientist</i>	12	19.7	17	56.7
<i>Friends And Family</i>	47	77.0	22	73.3
<i>No-One</i>	6	9.8	0	0.0
<i>Which Of The Following Characteristics May Make You More Likely To Approach Someone, In Order To Talk About Your Menstrual Cycle? Please Select All That Apply</i>				
<i>They Are Female</i>	46	75.4	23	76.7
<i>They Are Male</i>	0	0.0	2	6.7
<i>They Also Experience Menstruation</i>	34	55.7	15	50.0
<i>They Have A Lot Of Medical, Physiological And/ Or Psychological Knowledge And Understanding Of How Menstruation May Affect Sporting Performance</i>	21	34.4	22	73.3
<i>I Know Them Well/I Have Known Them For A Long Time</i>	38	62.3	22	73.3
<i>I Do Not Know Them Well/I Have Known Them For A Short Time</i>	1	1.6	1	3.3
<i>They Will Be More Likely To Reduce What Is Expected Of Me At Training/Competitions</i>	7	11.5	3	10.0
<i>They Will Be More Likely To Push Me And Encourage Me To Carry On, Despite Difficulties</i>	5	8.2	2	6.7
<i>They Have A Lot Of Knowledge And Experience In My Sport</i>	12	19.7	9	30.0
<i>They Help Me Feel Emotionally Comforted</i>	18	29.5	14	46.7
<i>They Will Provide Me With Problem-Solving Solutions</i>	15	24.6	12	40.0
<i>They Have A Similar Religious/Cultural Background To Me</i>	1	1.6	0	0.0

Appendix G. Chapter 3: Findings from open-text responses on whether gender impacts comfort in communication.

Adolescents	n	Adults	n
<i>Males do not have enough knowledge/ Would not understand</i>	12	<i>Female experiences it too</i>	7
<i>Men cannot relate</i>	6	<i>Believe the male coach would be uncomfortable</i>	4
<i>Females experience it too</i>	4	<i>Would feel uncomfortable speaking to a male coach</i>	3
<i>Believe the male coach would be uncomfortable</i>	4	<i>Males do not have enough knowledge/ would not understand</i>	3
<i>Too awkward to talk to a man</i>	4	<i>Easier to speak to a female</i>	2
<i>Easier to speak to a female</i>	3	<i>Females have more understanding</i>	2
<i>Would feel uncomfortable speaking to a male coach</i>	2	<i>Female coach will not judge me</i>	1
<i>Would be embarrassed to talk to a male coach</i>	2	<i>Don't want it to sound like an excuse</i>	1
<i>Male coach would not know how to support me</i>	1	<i>It more-so depends on how approachable the coach is</i>	1
<i>I'm not confident enough</i>	1	<i>Men would be put off by the conversation</i>	1
<i>It's too personal to talk about</i>	1	<i>Cannot go into detail the same way I can with a female coach</i>	1
<i>Just personal preference</i>	1		
<i>Would rather speak to my mum about it</i>	1		

<u>Descriptive Information and Coaching Background</u>
What age are you?
What was your assigned sex at birth?
Can you tell me about your coaching experience? E.g., how many years of coaching experience and specifically coaching females, timelines around coaching pathway, level of coaching certificate and academic underpinning?
<u>Knowledge and understanding</u>
Please describe what you know of the menstrual cycle.
What is your understanding of menstrual cycle symptoms?
What is your understanding of menstrual cycle dysfunctions?
Where, do you think, you gained this knowledge from?
Can you tell me what you know of the menstrual cycle and sports performance?
What is your understanding of hormonal contraceptives?
What is your understanding of hormonal contraceptive use in athletes?
What is your understanding of hormonal contraceptive use and the impact on performance?
<u>Experiences of the Menstrual Cycle/ Hormonal Contraception and Coaching Practices</u>
Please tell me of any experiences you have of the menstrual cycle within or outside of sport.
Can you tell me of any experiences you have had with athletes' performance being impacted by their menstrual cycle?
How did the situation(s) arise?
How did you deal with the situation with the athlete(s)? e.g., comfort in communication.
Can you tell me of any experiences you have, within or outside of sport, of hormonal contraceptives?
<u>Further Education Requirements</u>
What do you think can be changed to prompt further education and discussion on the topic within female sport?
What knowledge do you feel that you need about the menstrual cycle and sports performance?
What support do you think you need to allow this education / understanding to happen?

Appendix I. Chapter 4: Further supportive evidence including example data regarding categorisation of themes and sub-themes

Theme	Sub-theme	Higher Order Codes	
Environment and Culture (i.e., how is player support influenced?)	Society	Taboo limits visibility	<i>“It, it’s still something that I think, it’s still quite an embarrassing thing, like I think brilliant in Scotland now that we have free sanitary products and stuff like that. But I remember in school, it just wasn’t talked about [the MC]. And you go, it’s literally 50% of the population, probably slightly more.”</i> (P1, Male)
		Historically hidden (“it’s just how it is”)	<i>“I don’t really think a lot of people would bring it up. I think if it was like a there was more material to like to normalize it if you will, then aye, maybe coaches might, but again [...] I’ve always been that way, but it’s like private stuff keep private and you just like, not ignore it, but you just like don’t mention it until or unless you need to.”</i> (P13, Male)
	Club and/or Sporting Environment	Awkwardness around starting conversation	<i>“Eh, I don’t know I probably just feel a bit awkward, em [starting discussion]. Probably lack of knowledge as well, yeah is the main thing is no wanting to say the wrong thing or, yeah probably a lack of knowledge from me.”</i> (P4, Male)
		Believes players wouldn’t initiate a conversation	<i>“I would leave that for them to tell me. I wouldn’t turn to them and say are you on your period or anything like</i>

			<p><i>that because they would probably. Eh. I don't know, they would probably take offence to me saying something like that or be embarrassed".</i></p> <p>(P2, Male)</p>
<p>Coach-Athlete Dynamic</p> <p>(i.e., how do coaches support players?)</p>	<p>Relationship Affects Support</p>	<p>Gender implications/ Females better in communication</p>	<p><i>"I think me and [Head Coach] are good at like can I communicate with the girls? But are other coaches, do they know kinda what to say [about the MC], what not what to say, how to interact. Cause, other coaches might be embarrassed about it. Like if you had a male coach, are you gonna be embarrassed about it?"</i></p> <p>(P10, Male)</p> <p><i>"Obviously the female would have been in that position [having a MC]. Yeah, it's also sometimes a female who's older as well. Yeah, who's been through where they are especially been an ex-footballer as well. Em, whereas talking to me, it's still quite a young age. I won't have experienced that playing football there and I've certainly won't have experienced it in general, so I think they will they feel like they can relate more to a female, especially a female who plays football with still going through the exact same thing".</i></p> <p>(P12, Male)</p>
		<p>Time spent with player impacts comfort in communication</p>	<p><i>"[Researcher]</i> <i>And how comfortable do you like you feel having those conversations [regarding the MC]?</i> <i>[Participant]</i></p>

			<p><i>Uh, I feel comfortable with any of the older ones. And probably the younger ones now have been there a few weeks, so I wouldn't hesitate to have a conversation."</i></p> <p>(P7, Male)</p>
		Age of athlete affects communication	<p><i>"I just think the younger ones are kinda, maybe no aware of what's kinda happening yet [regarding bleeding] or whatever. I don't know. Just don't like to kind of show that that's happening, I don't know, that's maybe I'm totally wrong with that, but that's just kind of my thoughts".</i></p> <p>(P7, Male)</p> <p><i>"Maybe it's because I'm a male, but even if it's young girl, if it's young ones as well, I don't think they would talk to a female coach as well [regarding their MC]".</i></p> <p>(P2, Male)</p>
	Coach Interpersonal Skills	Coach recognises being trustworthy as important	<p><i>"I thought that was a really good level of trust and communication from that player to tell me that [they were on their period], they could have just said that they felt unwell, they could have said anything in that moment, but they were honest enough to say this is what's happened, I need to come off. And that was it, there was no, there is no issue, there was nothing there. I think I mentioned that previously, if you've got an understanding of what's happening, it makes it a lot easier to deal with."</i></p>

			(P1, Male)
		Coach values person over performance	<p><i>“Em, straight away try to communicate with the player yeah [if they are showing MC symptoms on the pitch], and ask them are they OK, yeah, and make sure that they OK are they OK. Instances there have been, like you can see them physically, like you can see them swaying a wee bit and at that point, I just tell the player to go down. Yeah, and we can come on, and speak to them, emm, because health and safety, your health is the main priority. It’s a game of football. It’s not that important. Especially the Level I was coaching. It’s no life or death so. [...] the main priority is that they’re OK.”</i></p> <p>(P12, Male)</p>
	Coach Experience	Coach can recognise impact of MC in soccer	<p><i>“You can tell that it’s their time [period]. You can like notice that it’s like, the effort drops or, like they just seem like moody, or they just seem like no, Aye, they just look like disinterested. Even though they are still interested. And but like maybe the efforts there or whatever. Em. On like the flip side of that, of course, they look like they’re trying to overcompensate like it’s just like. Not erratic behaviour, but like different behaviour to what you would usually have.”</i></p> <p>(P13, Male)</p> <p><i>“Yeah, but you could see at least get a clear change [when players are on their period], mood was mostly</i></p>

			<p><i>the change that I was dealt with, and say what we could see psychologically as well because there are players who have been fantastic for weeks, and weeks, and then you can just notice, There's that one game every couple of weeks that they're just not in the game and they just seem a wee bit off, they're not themselves."</i></p> <p>(P12, Male)</p>
		<p>Experience of players participation impacted by MC</p>	<p><i>" I was quite naïve to the situation as it happened, but[...]I had a player [...]said she was injured and had to come off[...]And my experience of that time during the game was that nothing had happened during the game to cause her to be injured, and so was kind of questioning her with you know, what injury it was it[...]I think it was a little bit of embarrassment on her behalf, and maybe not willing to say because she was a little younger and ehh [...] essentially the player had had her period during the game[...]was a big turning point for me in terms of understanding that they were going through different things from what they had previously emmm. At that moment I think as a coaching we decided for a female coach or a female member of staff into the coaching team on board to help with situations like that, and not that it was [...] not that it felt like we couldn't do anything or I couldn't do anything at that time, but it was just an uncomfortable situation because I probably wasn't at that moment experienced enough in the best possible manner to help that player, and that's always something that's stuck</i></p>

			<p><i>with me. It's been a number of years since it, but I think I learned a lot of form that and I've tried to always kinda be aware if a player then is asking to come off or is asking for specific things that just because an injury isn't visible doesn't mean it's something that's. Ehh. you know bothering them or someone else."</i></p> <p>(P1, Male)</p>
		Limited experience in supporting players	<p><i>[Participant]</i> <i>No, not that I can think of anyway [discussions regarding the MC].</i> <i>[Researcher]</i> <i>Yeah, do you think there's any reasons for that?</i> <i>[Participant]</i> <i>I don't know, eh [pause]. I really don't know. Just that it's something that eh[.] I've not picked up in it if it is something that has been, or conversations have been going on. Not that I'm scared to have they conversations or anything, but I just don't think [.] just [player names] maybe they just don't feel comfortable to say that in front of a man or, I just don't know.</i></p> <p>(P4, Male)</p>
Coach Support (i.e., how do we support coaches?)	Need for Education	Limited understanding of basic biology	<p><i>"[Researcher]</i> <i>And could you talk to me a bit about why? People have a period in the first place.</i> <i>[Participant]</i> <i>No idea."</i></p> <p>(P7, Male)</p>

			<p><i>“[Researcher] And what’s your understanding of the use of hormonal contraceptives or birth control in athletes? [Participant] Ehh, I don’t know, it’s that’s never something that I’ve come across, to be honest. ehh, that’s never something that. No.” (P13, Male)</i></p>
		Recognition of lack of knowledge	<p><i>“I’m not afraid to admit, I don’t really understand much about it [the MC], but I would happily sit and listen and learn about it, yeah to then be able to have discussions with other individuals about it”. (P12, Male)</i></p>
		Recognise they may be an integral support structure for players	<p><i>“You just don’t know what support they’re getting at home either, you do think sometimes. You do just wonder what support at home, you know they bring themselves to training, there’s never any mum or dad about. So even as they’re injured, they do see it as a club and having a support mechanism, having their friends here, so even if they are injured, they do still turn up.” (P8, Male)</i></p>
		Lack of knowledge due to personal experiences	<p><i>“It’s had nothing to do with any courses or any college thing, cause we even done human biology in the college, and nothing was mentioned [regarding the</i></p>

			<p><i>MC], it was more physiological for injuries and Heart rate and stuff like that, and it's never really been mentioned, yeah throughout my coaching career.”</i> (P12, Male)</p>
Willingness to Learn	to	Coach wants players to start a conversation	<p><i>“We’re slowly starting to see a little bit more [discussion around the MC] and hopefully to be more honest, like that day, like “I started my period, I might feel crap, can I just start on the bench and then I’ll obviously see how I feel and I’ll make I’ve got like whatever I need to have enough energy or, or tablets or, or whatever it is to make sure they’re able to, to do that would be a better, better idea. But as, as I said, like if that wasn’t one of the characters, in the team, then 90% of them would have just continued on that game and felt awful and then we would have probably went “nah we won’t start her next week ‘cause she wasn’t very good for us this week”, um, so yeah.</i> (P9, Female)</p>
		Coach wants to be able to support players	<p><i>“I completely, well no, I don’t understand. I’m quite happy to say I don’t understand the fear, I guess maybe of having to go and talk to a man about it [the MC]. Especially like when you’re 16, 17 and we’re in our late twenties and have kind ultimately decisions to be made about you and her and stuff like that. So, I understand that. But for me there’s an issue there if they can’t tell you even in that scenario and yeah, so that kind of really brings to mind, ‘because I went, Oh,</i></p>

			<p><i>this isn't like, you know, that's, that's not a good place to be in."</i> (P10, Male)</p>
Comfort in Communication	Knowledge affects communication		<p><i>"I mean, I think the thing that makes me uncomfortable at times is not knowing. I don't know what I'm talking about. Yeah, like I'm basically coming up and just being someone to talk to, but I can't give any advice [on the MC]. I can't come down and help them give an answer to it. But certainly, at times, I feel like I can come up and try Give them give them an out to talk or at least let them know that someone is there to talk to him or who's making sure that they're OK"</i> (P12, Male)</p> <p><i>"Don't really think it would matter how comfortable I was like talking to them about something I don't know [the MC]. So, like I can't really talk to them about it".</i> (P12, Male).</p>
		Coaches don't know how to communicate	<p><i>I wouldn't. I wouldn't feel uncomfortable with it if [discussing the MC with a player]</i> <i>If you were allowed to? Are you allowed to do? Are you? I think that would be the kind of scary things.</i> <i>You don't want to get into their privacy. But if it was a thing that was maybe taught over the years to everybody, even the girls that you, you're allowed to. If it's your coach or your schoolteacher, or just anything</i></p>

			<p><i>like that can open up. If you're feeling like that. I don't know a percentage on it, but I would think it would be quite high that they don't open up about that".</i></p> <p>(P6, Male)</p>
		Education should be practical	<p><i>"Just how it would affect the girls [the MC], like I don't need to know like everything about it, just how it's gonna affect them, because the information on the internet, it's kind of contradicting. So, are the girls able to push themselves more or are they gonna be lethargic? Are they gonna need different training? Is there a chance of them getting injured more when they're on it? Like there's just so many different aspects"</i></p> <p>(P7, Male)</p>
	Education Methods	Led by players experiences	<p><i>"Yeah, it would even be good to have some role models, even in the National Team to come out and see, like here's my experience when I got my period [...] Just to know that she gets a period, they probably think she's superhuman. She doesn't get, she doesn't get like acne or like, or her period, or she, she probably just loves herself. We have the normal emotions that everyone else does. Like somebody just telling you that they have that Yeah. Is just massive and probably could make a massive impact. So, it's just, as you said, it could be silly questions like, I know the media team do lots of like funny questions. But that question, that's a normal question.</i></p>

			<p><i>Yeah. What do you like to do? What's your time of month like? What you like to do to Relax yourself."</i></p> <p>(P9, Female)</p>
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Player Interview Guide Script

Hi everyone, thank you for being here today and taking part in this education series.

The aim of this is to try and prove awareness and understanding of our academy and senior coaches on the menstrual cycle and the impacts it may be having on our players. To give you some background, our previous research which was our surveys to the 1st team and academy seen only 17.5% (n = 7) of adults and 6.7% (n = 4) of adolescents would be open to approaching a coach in the future, and the main reasons being it felt awkward, or they thought coaches wouldn't know enough.

We also interviewed coaches as to what they knew about the MC, and they all said they wanted more education as they didn't know enough. But that education has to be practical, it's not just a biology lesson, they want to know how it impacts performance and how they should communicate on the topic. So, with that in mind, I have a series of discussion points I want to bring up to understand your experience, and then any information we think would be helpful for coaches to know.

- How does your menstrual cycle impact your daily life
- How does it impact you on the pitch?
- How do you manage your menstrual cycle around your performance?
- Has this changed as you've gotten older? What were your younger experiences?
- How have you found communicating this and the support you've had?
- What is best practice for you in regard to education?
- What would you like coaches to know?

Appendix K. Chapter 5: Design Thinking Model: Stakeholder Questionnaire

Please complete these short questions to understand your thoughts ahead of coach education regarding the menstrual cycle and female athlete health. These answers will help form the education resources we will collaborate on to ensure we create a well-rounded education piece targeted to support players and their performance.

What should the aims of this education be?

What do you think should be included in this education?

What support do you think players need from coaches?

What format should this education take?

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for a response to the question below.

What is the best way to promote discussion on this topic within these sessions?

A large, empty rectangular box with a thin black border, intended for a response to the question above.

Stakeholder Interview Guide Script

Thank you for your time spent reviewing and feeding back on the education resources you received. These resources were made with your initial proposed ideas integrated with player interviews to ensure both coaches and players would find this a useful process. In regard to the resources, I have a number of questions I would like to receive your feedback on. This will allow the research team to create a finalised version to then commence coach education.

- What do you like about the resources you have viewed?
- What do you think may require reworked or changed? Why?
- How appropriate do you think this is for the coaches?
- How can we make sure coaches engage in this education work?
- How do we make sure this education process leads to changes regarding communication and support?
- Do you have any final thoughts regarding the education resources you wish to explain?

Appendix M. *Chapter 5: Design Thinking Model: Final Resource Creation*

Due to the nature of the resource content (i.e. inclusion of videos), each resource can be found through available links below. These are stored electronically.

Draft Resources:

Resource 1: <https://figshare.com/s/c4808e6ee07cadc4e50a>

Resource 2: <https://figshare.com/s/fbfb30e68bf2c465eeb>

Resource 3: <https://figshare.com/s/df133beb6590bd0ba0d4>

Resource 4: <https://figshare.com/s/e2150285acb71d1ec15c>

Final Resources:

Resource 1: <https://figshare.com/s/846ee8534e1edfc33974>

Resource 2: <https://figshare.com/s/95755280a47e59c9c36a>

Resource 3: <https://figshare.com/s/4f045c7323ee2531c820>

Resource 4: <https://figshare.com/s/8cc2e7b747d35960e04b>

Appendix N. Chapter 6: Participant Pre-Post MC Knowledge and Experiences Questionnaire

At Glasgow City F.C we are looking to understand current knowledge of coaches of the menstrual cycle and understanding of how this impacts performance. This will help to improve our support to our players through targeting resources aimed at improving knowledge and communication on the topic. We appreciate you completing this questionnaire and helping to improve the landscape of menstrual cycle education within adolescent sport.

Section 1: Menstrual Cycle Knowledge

For the next questions, please rate how much knowledge you currently have in the following areas.

1.

	No Knowledge	Very Poor	Poor	Average	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	Your knowledge of what the menstrual cycle is?	<input type="checkbox"/>					
2	Your knowledge of what a normal menstrual cycle is?	<input type="checkbox"/>					
3	Your knowledge of symptoms can be experienced during a menstrual cycle?	<input type="checkbox"/>					

4	Your knowledge of ways to reduce menstrual cycle symptoms or feelings?	<input type="checkbox"/>						
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2.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1 I feel comfortable discussing the menstrual cycle if a player was to approach me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2 I feel comfortable starting a discussion with a player on their menstrual cycle	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3 I could identify if a player was struggling with symptoms associated with their menstrual cycle	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4 If a player was affected by their cycle during training or a match, I would feel confident in knowing how to support them	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5 I would know the right people to direct a player to if they required further	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

support regarding their
menstrual cycle

Please write an answer the following questions in boxes provided:

1. What age do people in the United Kingdom typically get their first period? (a period is

when a girl bleeds during her menstrual cycle)

2. How long does a period normally last (a period is when a girl bleeds during their menstrual cycle)?

3. How many days is average for one complete menstrual cycle? One menstrual cycle is the duration of time between the first day of your period (day 1 of bleeding) and the first day

of your next period (day 1 of bleeding).

4. What is the normal range of days a menstrual cycle should last?

5. At what age should a female go to speak to a doctor if they have not started their period?

6. Name three symptoms which may be due to the menstrual cycle.

7. Name three period (sanitary) product options that collect or absorb blood during a period?

8. Name three methods that people who have periods can use to reduce their menstrual cycle symptoms/feelings

9. Name three ways a player's football performance could be impacted because of their menstrual cycle.

10. Name three ways you could support a player who has told you they are experiencing problems due to their menstrual cycle.

For the following questions, please rate how strongly you agree/disagree with the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Unsure
1 Regular periods are an indicator of good health	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2 Experiences of the menstrual cycle are very individual (e.g. symptoms will be different from one person to the next)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3	The menstrual cycle has a negative impact on sporting performance ability in all females	<input type="checkbox"/>					
4	It is normal for a female to lose their period if they are doing lots of exercise training	<input type="checkbox"/>					
5	Exercising whilst having a period is not recommended for most girls or women	<input type="checkbox"/>					
6	Players are more likely to be injured on their period than at any other point in their cycle	<input type="checkbox"/>					
7	Light to moderate exercise can help symptoms related to periods	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Section 2: Menstrual Cycle Education Experiences (post education intervention only)

For the next questions, please rate how strongly you agree/disagree with the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I felt engaged/interested in the menstrual cycle education and lessons	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	I feel more confident in my knowledge about the menstrual cycle since the menstrual cycle education	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	I believe I have a better understanding of the impact of the menstrual cycle on	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

football
performance since
the menstrual cycle
education

4 I believe the
menstrual cycle
education has given
me the tools I need
to feel comfortable
in discussion with
players regarding
the menstrual cycle

Is there anything that you think was missing from the menstrual cycle education?

What are your key take-home messages from the menstrual cycle education?

How will you use this education within your future coaching?

